
Technical Note

D4.6 – Operations Procedures Test Report

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EDEN ISS

D4.6 – Operations Procedures Test Report

prepared for

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Executive summary

The Operation Procedures Test Report document, describes how the preliminary version of the EDEN ISS procedures have been obtained from the Ops Mode and Test Plan (deliverable of the WP 2.5), following the step-by-step approach as defined in the defined procedures development process. This process is aimed at the collection of information, comments and suggestions as coming from the different project phases.

In particular, the document highlights the desktop review sessions and familiarization activities, and also describes the deviations with respect the defined process, and what it has been achieved with respect to what planned.

Finally all the procedures developed before the start of the Antarctica operations are provided as annex.

Remark: The desktop review was originally foreseen in the WP5.3, but since it represents one of the first step in the procedures preparation, it has been anticipated to this WP as logical consequence of the applicable procedures development process, as defined in the Ops Mode ad Test Plan.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
AIT	Assembly, Integration and Test	MTF	Mobile Test Facility
CDR	Critical Design Review	PODF	Payload Operations Data File
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	SW	Software
FRR	Final Readiness Review	TPZ	Telespazio
HW	Hardware	UoG	University of Guelph
ISPR	International Standard Payload Rack	WUR	Wageningen University and Research
ISS	International Space Station		
LIT	Limerick Institute of Technology		

1 Introduction

All the systems, designed and realized for a final customer, is provided with a user guide (or operations manual), which includes the procedures for to operate it.

The complexity of such procedures is strictly linked to the complexity of the system to be operated, and to the operational environment, requiring in some case the adherence to a standard language, and to a step-by-step development and validation process, which includes several review sessions and the involvement of several actors, like for example subsystems and/or matters experts. That, for example, is the case of the ISS operations procedures, whose development follows the so called PODF process.

However, besides the formal process, a good procedure is capturing information's that are not contained in the official documents, but rather are coming from the several phases of the system development process. For example the AIT phase, the operators training, and ad-hoc organised hands-on session.

From procedures development point of view, EDEN ISS falls in the complex system category and that for two main reasons:

- EDEN ISS is close to a space system. It is a complex system to be operated in an harsh environment by a trained, but not expert, operator.
- The EDEN ISS operations deals not only with the system operations (i.e. set a light intensity, a temperature, etc.), but also with procedures for plants management (seedling, pruning, harvesting, etc.), and for the assessment of the quality and safety of the food produced.

Therefore, exactly as said above, rather than asking to the operator to deal with different operations manuals, it has been decided to follow an ISS-like approach, with the preparation of detailed procedures, all of them with the same language (PODF-Like) and following a process similar to the one in place for the ISS procedure preparation. A procedure Engineer has been appointed with the responsibility to manage such a process.

1.1 Applicable and Reference Document

1.1.1 Applicable Document

[AD1] - D2.7 Ops Mode and Test Plan v1.4

1.1.2 Reference Document

[RD1] - D 4.3 Food Quality and Safety Planning Document for FEG sampling procedures during the test phase in Bremen.

2 Procedures Development Process

Figure 1: Procedure Development Process

The above figure 1 shows the procedures development process as defined in the early phase of the EDEN ISS project. The process is based on several cornerstones:

- **Desktop Review**, aimed at the revision of the draft procedures by a panel of experts and to the implementation of the received comments and recommendation in an new version of the procedures (Preliminary)
- **Procedures Validation**, aimed at the testing of the procedures using the HW/SW developed for the mission, or an alternate model having the same functionalities (Engineering Model)
- **Training Session**, aimed one hand at operators training, and on the other hand in collecting and implementing all the comments (if any) coming from it.

The process has been defined in order to have all the procedures ready, in their final status, before the start of the Antarctica operations, but for several reasons it was not possible to follow it as defined.

In fact, the delay in the hardware development, in documentation availability and in inputs provision, have affected the possibility to have the procedures ready as necessary. For example, it was not possible to do one single desktop review, but more than one, it was not possible to have one dedicated procedure training session, but rather the Antarctica operator has done several training session, sometimes without using the procedures themselves. Finally, because the delay, it was not possible to validate the procedures and promote them to the final status, because the MTF was not available for that, and on the other hand, no Engineering Model has been foreseen in the project. As matter of fact the finalization of integration and testing activities and of the preparation of the HW for shipment to Antarctica were more important of the procedures validation.

Nevertheless, despite all the troubles, a good set of procedures was available before the start of the operations even if in the only preliminary status, covering all the nominal and science activities. Some missing procedure were those related to maintenance and/or malfunctions management.

2.1 Desktop Review Sessions

Several desktop review sessions have been done in the period coming from March to November 2017, all of them managed by TPZ as responsible of the EDEN ISS procedures development. The interactions have occurred mainly via email, with the comments to the procedures provided directly in the body of the procedures or in the email itself. When necessary a telecon has been set to discuss on the most critical points.

An indicative list is provided below, with the periods and the name of the participants, but with also the remarks that continuous interactions have occurred since the early stage of the procedure preparation and then for procedures update and /or fine-tuning. Such interactions have not been tracked.

The result of all the iterations will be described in Chapter 2.3, with the list of procedures delivered before the start of the operations. It is worth to underline that this list differs from the list provided in [AD 1], since some procedures have been combined, other added as new, other deleted because considered not necessary anymore. As already explained in [AD 1], that is normal in the long process for procedures preparation that starts when the HW is still in its design phase and is completed only when all the components are assembled, integrated and tested.

March 2017, iteration with the University of Wageningen (WUR) for the Plant Cultivation Procedures

Participants: Antonio Ceriello (TPZ), Esther Meinen (WUR), Tom Dueck (WUR)

The objective of this activity was to finalize the procedure for crop management, i.e. all the procedure to be used in the FEG to handle the plants, from the early stage to the harvesting, providing the needed information to correctly perform each activity. The review activities concerned the following procedures:

- 2.100 Plant Sowing
- 2.105 Plant Thinning
- 2.110 Plant Transfer to Growth tray
- 2.120 Crop Management
- 2.130 Plant Harvesting

April 2017 iteration with Airbus for the E-Nose and TransMADD Procedures

Participants: Antonio Ceriello (TPZ), Viktor Fettel (Airbus)

The interaction with Airbus served to finalise the procedures for the utilisation of the E-Nose instrument for the measurement of microbial contamination and of the TransMADD equipment for the ambient decontamination. The affected procedures are:

- 3.300 E-Nose Operations
- 3.320 TransMADD Operations

July 2017, Interaction with CNR for the Food Safety Analysis procedures

Participants: Antonio Ceriello (TPZ), Filomena Nazzaro (CNR)

That interaction represents a follow on of the familiarization activities occurred in May timeframe, and is aimed at the finalisation of the procedures for the Safety Analysis. The affected procedures are:

- 3.210 Growth Media Preparation for Safety Analysis

- 3.211 Samples Collection and Storage for Safety Analysis
- 3.212 Safety Analysis – Vial Operations

May/June 2017: interaction with CNR for the Quality Sampling Procedures

Participants: Antonio Ceriello (TPZ), Simona Proietti (CNR)

This activity was aimed at the preparation of the procedure for sample collection and storage in view of quality analysis done at the CNR lab, on the plant samples returned from the Antarctica site. The affected procedure is the following:

- 3.220 Sample Collection and Storage for Safety Analysis

July 2017, iteration with DLR for the Microbial Sampling Procedures

Participants: Antonio Ceriello (TPZ), Simon Barczyk (DLR)

Activity aimed at the finalisation of the procedures for microbial sampling (on the MTF surfaces, plants and liquid) in view of laboratory analysis done on the returned samples. The affected procedures are:

- 3.310 Microbial Sampling_Micro
- 3.311 Microbial Sampling_Molecular
- 3.312 Microbial Sampling_Liquid

July 2017: Interaction with DLR for the Plant Health Monitoring and NDS procedures

Participants: Antonio Ceriello (TPZ), Domenico De Simone (TPZ), Conrad Zeidler (DLR), Matthew Bamsey (DLR)

This activity is aimed at the finalisation of the procedures for the Plant Health Monitoring, i.e. the setup of the FEG camera's and of the SW for images automatic acquisition and distribution. Moreover in this period also the procedure for NDS maintenance has been managed. The affected procedures are:

- 2.500 Videocameras Configuration for Plant Monitoring
- 2.510 EDEN ISS Datalog and Images Automatic Transfer to MCC
- 4.200 Nutrient Distribution system Bulk Solution Tank Refill
- 4.220 NDS Sensors Calibration

October/November 2017, iteration with TAS-I for the ISPR procedures

Participants: Antonio Ceriello (TPZ), Giovanni Marchitelli (TAS-I)

Several interaction occurred in this timeframe with TAS-I for the preparation of the ISPR Rack procedures. The affected procedures are:

- 1.120 ISPR Configuration
- 1.140 ISPR Rack Activation and Checkout
- 2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth
- 3.410 ISPR Nutrient Solution Sample Collection
- 3.420 ISPR Air Sample Collection
- 4.530 ISPR CO2 Bottle Replacement
- 4.540 ISPR Light Panel Replacement
- 4.550 ISPR Subsystem Inspection
- 4.560 ISPR NDS Concentrated Nutrient Tanks Replacement
- 4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps Replacement

- 4.570 ISPR NDS Tanks Water Refill
- 4.590 ISPR Root Module Replacement
- 4.600 Relay Replacement
- 5.630 ISPR NDS Pumps Failure Management

October/November 2017: interaction with University of Guelph (UoG) and DLR for the EDEN ISS procedures

Participants: Antonio Ceriello (TPZ), Mike Stasiak (UoG), Matthew Bamsey (DLR)

Following the familiarization session with the ARGUS system and displays capabilities the following procedures have been developed and iterated with UoG and DLR

2.000 EDEN ISS Daily System Check

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth

October/November 2017: Interaction with LIT for the Quality Analysis Procedures

Participants: Antonio Ceriello (TPZ), Michelle Bennet (LIT)

This activity was aimed at the finalisation of the procedures for the usage of tool,s for on siste quality analysis. The affected procedures are:

- 3.230 Quality Measurement_Refractometer Operations
- 3.231 Quality Measurement_Penetrometer Operations
- 3.232 Quality Measurement_colourimeter Operations
- 3.233 Quality Measurement_Clorophylmeter Operations
- 3.234 Quality Measurement_Nitrate Ion Meter Operations
-

The following pictures provides the evidence on how the comments have been provided and the procedures iterated. Three examples are provided, covering the three different ways the inputs have been provided: Comments on the word format, comments on the pdf format, comments in the body of email.

Figure 2: Comments from WUR in the body of a procedure in word format

3.310 Sampling for Microbial Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/DRAFT)

OBJECTIVE
Collection of samples and storage for off-line microbial analysis.

DURATION
TBD

TOOLS
N/A

ITEMS
42 Eppendorf Tubes (2ml)
42 Centrifuge tubes (15ml)
42 Nylon flocked swab with container
Markers
3 Sterile Nitrile Gloves
Sterile Water (TBD ml)

Comments:
 - **barc_si** (25/07/2017 15:59:33): filled with 2.5 ml PBS
 - **barc_si**: should we mention: all consumables are labeled with set 1/2 for microbial and set 2/2 for molecular analysis and additional with the number of the sampling event from 1/11 to 11/11?

Figure 3: Comments from DLR in the body of a procedure in pdf format

RE: E-Nose/Transmadd operations - Messaggio (HTML)

mercoledì 19/04/2017 13:59
FETTER, Viktor <viktor.fetter@airbus.com>
 RE: E-Nose/Transmadd operations

A Ceriello Antonio

Cc Daniel.Schubert@dlr.de; Matthew.Bamsey@dlr.de; Paul Zabel; Roldugin, Christina

L'utente ha risposto al messaggio in data 21/04/2017 12:54.

start button the cleaning process is performed automatically. Just at the beginning of one session the E-Nose needs to be cleaned for a dedicated period (this process is already started automatically after the machine is turned ON). As the first measurement within one session a measurement of the environmental air should be performed to have a negative control.

3. For sample taking on the plants has been decided what is the methodology? [VF] The sample taking unit is modular – with the handle samples can be taken on leaves (left), without the handle on various surfaces (right).

We discussed this topic already with DLR-ME and the other involved colleagues and it seems to be more important to perform measurements on the

Figure 4: Interaction with Airbus via email

2.2 Familiarization Sessions

Several familiarization sessions have been done along the project. The most part of them had the objective to train the Antarctica operator on the tools and methodologies to be used during the EDEN ISS mission. These sessions even if not tailored for procedures verifications have provided to the some valuable information for the procedures development.

2.2.1 EDEN ISS Familiarization Sessions

May 2016 and August 2016: Familiarization on the cultivation procedures at WUR

Participants: Paul Zabel (DLR), Esther Meinen (WUR), Tom Dueck (WUR)

The EDEN ISS operator (Paul Zabel) was at WUR 2 times for training, and more specifically in May 2016 and in August 2016. In both periods, he spent 2 to 3 days in hands-on sessions with the support of the WUR experts, working on the several steps of cultivation (sowing, plant management and harvest) and lighting in a climate chamber. For example, he did the harvest of all crops of the first experiment carried out in the project EDEN-ISS to get him acquainted with the crops. Also he familiarized on the different plant species and in particular on how should a healthy crop look like, what are symptoms of diseases, how to manage the plants (pruning, pollination), how to correctly use the nutrient solution. The following pictures shows Paul Zabel during the training session.

Figure 5: Paul Zabel in the training Session at WUR

August 2017: Familiarization Session on the Quality and Safety procedures at DLR

Participants: Paul Zabel (DLR), Alberto Battistelli (CNR), Paul Downsey (LIT)

During the one-day visit to Bremen a fast review of equipment and consumable received by the DLR from CNR and IT was performed. Even if there was no time to test single equipment functioning (as matter of fact, most equipment were already packed and stored ready for transfer to Antarctica), a review of the functioning of volumetric automatic pipettes was performed with Paul Zabel. Doubts about the use of water solutions, and liquid with high vapour pressure or affinity for the plastic tip, as well as on the sampling procedures were clarified. . Final packing for some equipment and consumable was finalized. Detailed informations on this training session are reported in [RD1]. Fig. 6 shows the

execution of some steps of a sampling procedure, performed by the matter expert A. Battistelli and reported in the document prepared in view of the familiarization session.

Figure 6: Some steps of a sampling procedure

However, apart this face-to-face training session, several on spot instructions have been provided to the EDEN ISS operators, via email and/or via phone call, on the correct way to perform the Food Quality and Safety procedures.

2.2.2 Procedure Engineering familiarization

Other familiarization sessions have been done specifically for procedure development, in particular to collect info and material for a correct procedures authoring.

March/April 2017: Interaction with University of Guelph (UoG) and DLR to familiarize with Argus monitoring and commanding capabilities

Participants: Antonio Ceriello (TPZ), Mike Stasiak (UoG), Conrad Zeidler (DLR)

The ARGUS SW works in autonomy as per automatic procedures defined by the operator. Nevertheless, it provides the possibility to interact with all the equipment/subsystems in terms of telemetry monitoring and commanding, via dedicated displays. This capability is done not only to the on site operators but also to those remote operators provided on one hand with the needed tools and privileges to do that, on the other hand with procedures.

On this respect, apart the Argus documentation, some example have been provided by UoG to show how similar project have been managed in terms of displays and procedures preparation, as well as explanation on how the Argus system has been customized for the EDEN ISS operations.

In addition, an Argus Client has been provided to TPZ, with the instruction to configure it, and the privilege to remotely access the MTF during the AIT phase in monitoring only, i.e. without the capability to send commands. In this way, it was possible to navigate through the displays and familiarize with their structure and capabilities. Also, it was possible to take snapshot for procedure preparation.

May 2017: Familiarization session at CNR for the Procedure Engineering, in view of the finalization of the procedures for Safety Analysis

Participants: Antonio Ceriello (TPZ), Filomena Nazzaro (CNR)

This session was aimed at familiarize with the tools and laboratory procedures for food safety analysis and to collect information and pictures for the authoring and finalisation of the related procedure for the EDEN ISS operations. In a one-day session, the CNR expert showed the entire sequence of sample

preparation for safety analysis, from the preparation of the plants, to the culture media preparation, for the sample preparation, to the preparation of the culture plate. The following pictures give an idea of what done

Figure 7: Plants and tool used

Figure 8. Preparation and result of the tomato sample analysis

May 2017: Familiarization session at DLR for the Procedure Engineer

Participants: Antonio Ceriello (TPZ), other (DLR)

The Procedure Engineer (Antonio Ceriello) spent two days in DLR for hands on session on the EDEN ISS HW, to collect information for procedures finalisation. In that two days he had not only the possibility to familiarize with the EDEN ISS environment and system, but most of all to discuss with the several persons involved in the integration activities on the most critical aspects of the EDEN ISS operations. In this working session. He also had the chance to collect pictures of the most recent configuration of EDEN ISS and the pictures of several tools to be used during the operations, not available before. The following figures give an idea of what collected and subsequently used to improve the procedures.

Figure 9: Pictures of tools and substrate

Figure 10: Some pictures of EDEN ISS subsystems

2.3 Results achieved

The following lines describe what achieved before the start of the mission. i.e. how many procedures have been delivered in PRE Status, and in principle what remains to complete the job. As remark, it was not possible to develop the procedures for the MTF commissioning (four in the list) because lack of inputs. The team for the integration at the Antarctica Site have used the procedures as developed for the AIT phase.

In this chapter a summary of what done is provided. More detailed information are provided in Annex A. All the developed procedures are provided as Annex B.

EDEN ISS (MTF/FEG) Procedures

Total Number: 38

Developed PRE: 26

Developed DRAFT: 0

To be developed: 12 (6 maintenance, 6 malfunction)

ISPR procedures

Total Number: 20

Developed PRE: 13

Developed DRAFT: 1

To be developed: 6 (3 maintenance, 3 malfunction)

Several procedures have been deleted along the development process. Some of them because not necessary anymore (those for example for robotic arm), other because combined with other procedures. However, the Annex A provides the list of the deleted procedures and the reason for their deletion.

As described in [AD 1] and presented in the CDR/FRR, the procedures have been provided to the EDEN ISS operators as single files, organized in book/chapters and available in electronic format on the EDEN

ISS PC's. They are provided in separate folders, one for the EDEN ISS, the other for the ISPR procedures, having a common structure as defined below:

- Commissioning
- Nominal
- Science
- Maintenance
- Malfunction

For time being, the procedures development is on hold waiting for inputs coming from the EDEN ISS operator. As matter of fact, the Antarctica Operations will serve as final validation of the procedures themselves.

ANNEX A: EDEN ISS Procedures Status at December 2017

MTF procedures

#	Nr	Title	Book	Chapter	Category	Note	Status
1	2.000	EDEN ISS Daily System Check	EDEN ISS	Crew/UHB	Nominal	The most part of the parameters to be checked have been indicated "as required" because missing inputs. That issue has to be solved in the next release. In the meantime MCC has to provide the list with the reference parameters or range to the Antarctica Operator	Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
2	2.100	Plant Sowing	EDEN ISS	Crew	Nominal		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
3	2.105	Plant Thinning	EDEN ISS	Crew	Nominal		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
4	2.110	Plant Transfer to Growth Trays	EDEN ISS	Crew	Nominal		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
5	2.120	Crop Management	EDEN ISS	Crew	Nominal	picture 1 and 2 to be replaced with new ones showing early disease signals. Inputs required	Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
6	2.130	Plant Harvesting	EDEN ISS	Crew	Nominal		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
7	2.200	FEG Configuration for Plant Growth	EDEN ISS	Crew	Nominal	Step 2.18 still TBW. It will be finalised with inputs coming from the early operations days	Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
8	2.500	Videocameras Configuration For Plant Monitoring	EDEN ISS	Crew/UHB	Nominal		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)

9	2.510	EDEN ISS datalog and Images Automatic Transfer to MCC	EDEN ISS	Crew/UHB	Nominal	Title changed. Old : Remote vide-camera configuration for plant monitoring Title changed once again and fixed	Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
10	3.210	Growth Media Preparation for Safety Analysis	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science	Evolution of the following procedures: - 3.200 Safety Sample Collection and Storage	Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
11	3.211	Samples Collection and Storage for Safety Analysis	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science	- 3.210 Sample Safety Analysis	Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
12	3.212	Safety Analysis Using the Micro Biological Survey Method	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science	Remark: Procedure 3.212 refers to a NMIII procedure for laboratory waste management. Check with NMII people if this procedure exist.	Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
13	3.220	Sample Collection and Storage for Quality Analysis	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
14	3.230	Quality Measurement_Refractometer Operations	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science	Evolution of the procedures: - 3.230 Sample Quality Analysis - 3.230 On Site Quality Measurement	Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
15	3.231	Quality Measurement_Penetrometer Operations	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
16	3.232	Quality Measurement_Colourimeter Operations	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
17	2.233	Quality Measurement_Clorophylmeter Operations	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
18	3.234	Quality Measurement_Nitrate Ion Meter Operations	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
19	3.300	E-Nose Operations	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science	Some TBD to be solved	Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
20	3.310	Microbial Sampling_micro	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)

21	3.311	Microbial Sampling _molecular	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
22	3.312	Microbial Sampling _plants	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
27	3.313	Microbial Sampling _liquid	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
28	3.320	TransMADD Decontamination		Crew	Science		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
29	4.100	AMS Filters Replacement	EDEN ISS		Maintenance		Inputs required
30	4.150	Thermal Cooling Lines refill	EDEN ISS		Maintenance		Inputs required
31	4.200	Nutrient Distribution System Bulk Solution Tank Refill	EDEN ISS		Maintenance	Title changed from "NDS tanks water refill"	Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
32	4.210	NDS waste water tank emptying	EDEN ISS		Maintenance		Inputs required
33	4.220	NDS Sensors Calibration			Maintenance		Verified and promoted to PRE (19/12/2017)
34	4.300	Fresh Water Tank Filling	EDEN ISS		Maintenance		On hold. Inputs will come from the Antarctica team
35	4.310	Waste water tank emptying	EDEN ISS		Maintenance		On hold. Inputs will come from the Antarctica team
36	4.400	LED Panel Maintenance	EDEN ISS		Maintenance		Inputs required
37	5.100	Overtemperature/Undertemperature Management	EDEN ISS		Malfunction		Inputs required
38	5.200	AMS Failure Management and Repair	EDEN ISS		Malfunction		Inputs required
39	5.300	NDS Pump Failure Management And Repair	EDEN ISS		Malfunction		Inputs required
40	5.400	Sensor Failure Management and Repair	EDEN ISS		Malfunction		Inputs required
41	5.500	Building System Failure Management and Repair (doors, lighting, electrical)	EDEN ISS		Malfunction		Inputs required
42	5.600	NDS pH and EC setting failure			Malfunction	NEW!!! (09/11/2017)	Inputs Required

ISPR Rack Procedures

#	Nr	Title	Book	Chapter	Category	Notes	Status
1	1.120	ISPR Configuration	ISPR Rack	Crew	Commissioning	Mechanical configuration of the Rack during the commissioning phase (drawer insertion, removal of mechanical blocks, cabling etc.)	Verified and promoted to PRE (20 December 2017)
2	1.140	ISPR Rack Activation and Checkout	ISPR Rack	Crew/UHB	Commissioning	First activation of the rack and S/S check	Verified and promoted to PRE (20 December 2017)
3	2.300	ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth	ISPR Rack	Crew	Nominal	Combined with 3.400 in order to have all the steps from seeding (pillow preparation) to Rack configuration via Labview in one single procedure.	Verified and promoted to PRE (20 December 2017)
4	3.410	ISPR Nutrient solution sample collection	ISPR Rack	Crew	Science		Verified and promoted to PRE (20 December 2017)

6	4.510	ISPR THC Replacement	ISPR Rack	Crew	Maintenance		Inputs Required
7	4.520	ISPR TCCS Replacement	ISPR Rack	Crew	Maintenance		Inputs Required
8	4.530	ISPR CO2 Bottle Replacement	ISPR Rack	Crew	Maintenance		Verified and promoted to PRE (20 December 2017)
9	4.540	ISPR Light panel replacement	ISPR Rack	Crew	Maintenance		Verified and promoted to PRE (20 December 2017)
10	4.550	ISPR Subsystems inspection	ISPR Rack	Crew	Maintenance		Verified and promoted to PRE (20 December 2017)
11	4.560	ISPR NDS concentrated nutrient tanks replacement	ISPR Rack	Crew	Maintenance		Verified and promoted to PRE (20 December 2017)

12	4.561	ISPR NDS Pumps Replacement	ISPR Rack	Crew	Maintenance	NEW!!!	Verified and promoted to PRE (20 December 2017)
13	4.570	ISPR NDS tanks water refilling	ISPR Rack	Crew	Maintenance	Procedure number changed	Verified and promoted to PRE (20 December 2017)
14	4.580	ISPR NDS waste water tank emptying	ISPR Rack	Crew	Maintenance	Procedure number changed	Inputs Required
15	4.590	ISPR Root Module Replacement	ISPR Rack	Crew	Maintenance	NEW!!!	Verified and promoted to PRE (20 December 2017)
16	4.600	Relay Replacement	ISPR Rack	Crew	Maintenance		Verified and promoted to PRE (20 December 2017)
17	5.610	ISPR Overtemperature/ Undertemperature management	ISPR Rack	Crew	Malfuction		Inputs Required
18	5.620	ISPR AMS failures management	ISPR Rack	Crew	Malfuction		Inputs Required (only partial inputs available)
19	5.630	ISPR NDS pumps failure management	ISPR Rack	Crew	Malfuction		Verified and promoted to PRE (20 December 2017)
20	5.640	ISPR Illumination system failure management				NEW!!!	Inputs Required

Deleted procedures

#	Nr	Title	Book	Chapter	Category	Note
MTF						
1	1.100	MTF Installation at NMII	EDEN ISS	Crew	Commissioning	Not ready for commissioning.AIT procedures used
2	1.110	MTF Internal Configuration	EDEN ISS	Crew	Commissioning	Not ready for commissioning.AIT procedures used
3	1.130	MTF Activation and Checkout	EDEN ISS	Crew/UHB	Commissioning	Not ready for commissioning.AIT procedures used
4	1.200	Ground Network Setup	EDEN ISS	Crew/UHB	Commissioning	No need for it. Commanding capability only on DLR.Data/images exchange only via ftp
5	1.160	Plant Health Monitoring Sytem Checkout	EDEN ISS	Crew/UHB	Commissioning	Deleted. The procedures 2.500 and 2.510 will be used for that.
6	1.210	MTF Remote Control Verification	EDEN ISS	UHB	Commissioning	Combined with 1.130
7	1.230	Robotic Arm Remote Test	EDEN ISS	UHB	Commissioning	Robotic Arm discarded
8	1.240	Plant Images Remote Acquisition and processing	EDEN ISS	UHB	Commissioning	Deleted. A simple ftp protocol will be used for images retrieval @UHB's
9	1.250	Videoconferencing System Test	EDEN ISS	Crew/UHB	Commissioning	Use AWI videocon system.
10	1.260	EDEN ISS Data Management Test	EDEN ISS	Crew/UHB	Commissioning	Data distribution included in procedure 2.510
11	2.400	Robotic Arm Control	EDEN ISS	Crew	Nominal	Robotic Arm not implemented
12	2.410	Remote Robotic Arm Control	EDEN ISS	UHB	Nominal	Robotic Arm not implemented
13	2.600	Videoconferencing System Operations	EDEN ISS	Crew/UHB	Nominal	Use AWI videocon system.
14	2.700	Argus System Operations	EDEN ISS	Crew/UHB	Nominal	Not necessary. It is supposed to describe how to use the ARGUS Display and that is matter of training and not of operational procedures.
15	3.250	Organoleptic Sample Preparation and Sensory evaluation	EDEN ISS	Crew	Science	Not necessary. It more matter of training than of procedure.

16	4.000	FEG Interior and Exterior Cleaning	EDEN ISS	Crew	Maintenance	We do not need a procedure for that
17	4.230	NDS Cleaning	EDEN ISS		Maintenance	Deleted. Combined with procedure 4.200
ISPR						
1	2.310	Remote ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth	ISPR Rack	UHB	Nominal	Deleted from list. The procedure 2.200 developed for on site operations can be used for such UHB's with the ARGUS Client connection capability.
2	3.400	ISPR Pre-seeded pillow transfer to root module	ISPR Rack	Crew	Science	Deleted from list (combined with the 2.300)
3	3.420	ISPR Air sample collection	ISPR Rack	Crew	Science	Deleted as per TAS-I input (Jan 2018). Since Air parameters are already monitored it is not necessary to spill out Air samples.
4	3.430	ISPR Tomatoes pollination	ISPR Rack	Crew	Science	Deleted from list. The tomatoes pollination is the same to be done for the FEG. The only difference stands on the fact that the drawer has to be opened before (could be a problem and crew time consuming, since it should be done very day. To be checked if the mechanical operations can be replaced by an increase of the ventilation inside the growth chambers).
5	3.440	ISPR Crop harvest (crop-specific)	ISPR Rack	Crew	Science	Deleted from list. The harvesting is well described for FEG and, apart the drawer opening, the same actions are required for the ISPR Rack.

ANNEX B: EDEN ISS Procedures

This Annex contains all the available procedures in their preliminary status.

2.000 EDEN ISS Daily System Check

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Daily check of the EDEN ISS status in terms of both S/S Telemetries and Plant Health Status of the MTF/FEG and the ISPR Rack.

DURATION

120 min

TOOLS

N/A

ITEMS

N/A

NOTE

THIS PROCEDURE DEFINES A CHECKLIST FOR THE ON SITE OPERATOR FOR THE DAILY VERIFICATION OF THE HEALTH AND STATUS OF EDEN ISS S/S, AND FOR PLANT GROWTH MONITORING. SUCH A VERIFICATION CAN BE DONE WITHOUT GOING TO THE MTF BUT RATHER USING THE TOOLS AND DISPLAYS AVAILABLE AT NMIII

NMIII 1 Daily EDEN ISS S/S STATUS CHECK

NOTE

THE ANALYSIS OF THE TELEMETRIES IN THE MAIN PANEL PROVIDES A HIGH LEVEL VIEW OF THE STATUS OF THE MAIN SUBSYSTEMS OF THE MTF AND THE CONFIRMATION THAT SOME S/S (IN PARTICULAR THE **AMS** AND THE **TCS**) ARE CORRECTLY WORKING. FOR OTHERS LIKE THE **NDS** AND THE **ILS** FURTHER VERIFICATION ARE DAILY REQUIRED, TO ASSESS FOR EXAMPLE THE CORRECTNESS OF THE PH AND EC, OR THAT THE LED PANELS UNITS ARE ACTIVE AS REQUIRED.

1.1 High Level Telemetries Verification

Figure 1: Argus Main Screen

2.000 EDEN ISS Daily System Check

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

On the EDEN ISS Homescreen Display

In the **POWER DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM** box

Verify ILS LEFT-POWER ENABLE = Enabled
Verify ISPR-POWER ENABLE = Enabled
Verify ILS RIGHT-POWER ENABLE = Enabled
Verify TCS-POWER ENABLE = Enabled
Verify AMS-POWER ENABLE = Enabled
Verify NDS SES-POWER ENABLE = Enabled
Verify NDS FEG-POWER ENABLE = Enabled

In the **ALARM/SYSTEM CONTROL** box

Verify ATMOSPHERE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM = no alarm
Verify THERMAL CONTROL SYSTEM = no alarm
Verify LED LIGHTING SYSTEM = no alarm
Verify NUTRIENT DELIVERY SYSTEM = no alarm
Verify COMMUNICATION = no alarm

In the **MTF Picture** Part

Verify CPO; Temperature = as required
Verify CPO; Humidity = as required
Verify FW Fill Status = High
Verify FW Overfill = Low
Verify WW Level = Low

Verify SES; TEMP AIR IN = as required
Verify SES; TEMPERATURE = as required
Verify SES; HUMIDITY = as required
Verify SES; PAR LIGHT = as required
Verify SES; CO2 = as required
Verify SES; CALCULATED VPD = as required

Verify SAF; SMOKE DETECTORE SES = Off
Verify RECIRC PUMP TANK 1 = 100%
Verify FLOW METER 1 = Flow
Verify RECIRC PUMP TANK 2 = 100%
Verify FLOW METER 2 = Flow

Verify SES; DOOR STATUS = Off

Verify FEG; TEMPERATURE = as required
Verify FEG; HUMIDITY = as required
Verify FEG; PAR LIGHT = as required
Verify FEG; CO2 = as required
Verify FEG; CALCULATED VPD = as required

2.000 EDEN ISS Daily System Check (EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Verify FEG; AIR FLOW = as required
Verify FEG; OXYGEN = as required

Verify FEG; L1 HP PUMP = as required
Verify FEG; L2 HP PUMP = as required
Verify FEG; L3 HP PUMP = as required
Verify FEG; L4 HP PUMP = as required

Verify FEG; R1 HP PUMP = as required
Verify FEG; R2 HP PUMP = as required
Verify FEG; R3 HP PUMP = as required
Verify FEG; R4 HP PUMP = as required

1.2 LED Lamp Unit Status Verification

NOTE

THIS ACTION IS AIMED AT VERIFYING IF THE LED PANELS ARE ACTIVE AS REQUIRED FOR THE OPERATION PHASE.

Lamp Unit	Status	BLUE				RED				PAR RED				WHITE			
		Wavelength	MS Power	Desired %	Intensity	Wavelength	MS Power	Desired %	Intensity	Wavelength	MS Power	Desired %	Intensity	Wavelength	MS Power	Desired %	Intensity
L1-01	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-02	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-03	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-04	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-05	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-06	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-07	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-08	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-09	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-10	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-11	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-12	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-13	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-14	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-15	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-16	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-17	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-18	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-19	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-20	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-21	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-22	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-23	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-24	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-25	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-26	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-27	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-28	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-29	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0
L1-30	Automatic	450 nm	3.2 W	0.00 %	0	660 nm	7.2 W	0.00 %	0	730 nm	0.2 W	0.00 %	0	3700 nm	4.8 W	0.00 %	0

Figure 2: LED LIGHTING SYSTEM Main Display

1.2.1 On the LED LIGHTING SYSTEM Display (Fig. 2)

For each LED Lamp Unit

Verify LED Lamp Unit Status = As required (Automatic/Manual On/Manual Off)

1.2.2 If one or more LED Lamp Unit = Not as required Call MCC for action definition

2.000 EDEN ISS Daily System Check

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

1.3 Nutrient Bulk Solution Tank Status

NOTE

THIS ACTION IS AIMED AT VERIFYING IF THE NDS TANKS ARE FILLED AS REQUIRED AND IF THE NUTRIENT SOLUTION COMPOSITION IS IN LINE WITH THE OPERATION PHASE REQUIREMENT

D I L U T E T A N K S					
SENSORS TANK 1		TANK 1 EQUIPMENT CONTROL		Level Setpoint	24.99 cm
EC 1 TANK 1	0.50 mS	BULK NS TANK 1 CONTROLS		Filling Status	0.00 %
EC 2 TANK 1	0.50 mS	EC Setpoint	0.54 mS	Dosing Status	100.00 %
pH 1 TANK 1	7.89 pH	pH Setpoint	7.00 pH		
pH 2 TANK 1	7.81 pH	A Dosing Pump		Automatic	Off 0 %
TEMP 1 TANK 1	19.74 °C	B Dosing Pump		Automatic	Off 0 %
TEMP 2 TANK 1	19.72 °C				
FLOW METER TANK 1	Flow	SOLENOID FW TANK 1		Automatic	Off 0 %
LEVEL SENSOR TANK 1	37.31 cm	REC PUMP TANK 1		Automatic	On 100 %
SENSORS TANK 2		TANK 2 EQUIPMENT CONTROL		Level Setpoint	18.01 cm
EC 1 TANK 2	0.50 mS	BULK NS TANK 2 CONTROLS		Filling Status	0.00 %
EC 2 TANK 2	0.51 mS	EC Setpoint	0.55 mS	Dosing Status	100.00 %
pH 1 TANK 2	7.98 pH	pH Setpoint	6.70 pH		
pH 2 TANK 2	7.70 pH	C Dosing Pump		Automatic	Off 0 %
TEMP 1 TANK 2	19.74 °C	D Dosing Pump		Automatic	Off 0 %
TEMP 2 TANK 2	19.83 °C				
FLOW METER TANK 2	Flow	SOLENOID FW TANK 2		Automatic	Off 0 %
LEVEL SENSOR TANK 2	38.76 cm	REC PUMP TANK 2		Automatic	On 100 %
ADDITIONAL SENSORS		SHARED TANK EQUIPMENT CONTROL			
LEVEL SWITCH FW1	High	ACID DOSING PUMP		Automatic	Off 0 %
LEVEL SWITCH FW2	Low	ACID SOLENOID		Automatic	Off 0 %
LEVEL SWITCH SUMP 1	Off	0%=Tank 1, 100%=Tank 2			
LEVEL SWITCH SUMP 2	Off	BASE DOSING PUMP		Automatic	Off 0 %
LEVEL SWITCH WM1	Low	BASE SOLENOID		Automatic	Off 0 %
LEAK SENSOR FEG	Off	0%=Tank 1, 100%=Tank 2			
LEAK SENSOR SES	Off	PUMP FW		Automatic	Off 0 %
CPO; SUBFLOOR	17.36 °C				

Figure 3: NDS Main Displays – Dilute tanks part

1.3.1 On the NUTRIENT DELIVERY SYSTEM/DILUTE TANKS Display

In the **SENSORS TANK 1** Box

- Verify** EC 1 TANK 1 = as required
- Verify** EC 2 TANK 1 = as required
- Verify** pH 1 TANK 1 = as required
- Verify** pH 2 TANK 1 = as required
- Verify** TEMP 1 TANK 1 = as required
- Verify** TEMP 2 TANK 1 = as required
- Verify** FLOW METER TANK 1 = as required
- Verify** LEVEL SENSOR TANK 1 = as required

In the **SENSORS TANK 2** Box

- Verify** EC 1 TANK 2 = as required
- Verify** EC 2 TANK 2 = as required
- Verify** pH 1 TANK 2 = as required
- Verify** pH 2 TANK 2 = as required
- Verify** TEMP 1 TANK 2 = as required
- Verify** TEMP 2 TANK 2 = as required
- Verify** FLOW METER TANK 2 = as required
- Verify** LEVEL SENSOR TANK 2 = as required

In the **ADDITIONAL SENSORS** Box

2.000 EDEN ISS Daily System Check

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Verify LEVEL SWITCH FW1 = as required
Verify LEVEL SWITCH FW2 = as required
Verify LEVEL SWITCH SUMP1 = as required
Verify LEVEL SWITCH SUMP2 = as required
Verify LEVEL SWITCH WW1 = as required
Verify LEAK SENSOR FEG = as required
Verify LEAK SENSOR SES = as required
Verify CPO; SUBFLOOR = as required

In Tank 1(2) Equipment Control Control box

Verify A Dosing Pump = **Automatic**
Verify B Dosing Pump = **Automatic**
Verify Solenoid FW Tank 1(2) = **Automatic**
Verify Rec Pump Tank 1(2) = **Automatic**

In Shared Tank Equipment Control box

Verify Acid Dosing Pump = **Automatic**
Verify Acid Solenoid = **Automatic**
Verify Base Dosing Pump = **Automatic**
Verify Base Solenoid = **Automatic**
Verify Pump FW = **Automatic**
Verify Ozone Generator = **Automatic**

- 1.3.2 If one or more parameters and/or status is not as expected
Call **MCC** for action definition

1.4 Plants Images Check

NOTE

TWO DIFFERENT KIND OF IMAGES ARE TAKEN DURING THE DAY:

- 32 HD IMAGES
- 16 MULTIWAVE IMAGES

THESE IMAGES ARE STORED ON THE CAMERA-PC IN THE MTF AND AUTOMATICALLY TRANSFERRED ON THE CAMERA-PC IN THE NMIII AND HAVE TO BE DAILY CHECKED FOR PLANT HEALTH ASSESSMENT

- 1.4.1 On the Camera PC (NMIII) open the crop images stored in the following folders:

HD Images (top and side view)

Camera-PC (NM-III)

D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\CropImages\HDTOPVIEW\<camera position1>

Where *<camera position1>* is:

- L1-2C, L1-4C
- L2-1C, L2-2C, L2-3C, L2-4C
- L3-1C, L3-2C, L3-3C, L3-4C

2.000 EDEN ISS Daily System Check

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

- L4-1L, L4-2L, L4-3L
- L4-1R, L4-2R, L4-3R, L4-4C
- R1-2C, R1-4C
- R2-2C, R2-4C
- R3-4C
- R4-2C, R4-4C

D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\CropImages\HDSIDEVIEW\<camera position2>

Where *<camera position2>* is:

- L12-1S, L12-3S, L34-1S, L34-3S
- R12-1S, R12-3S, R34-1S, R34-3S

Multiwave Images

Camera-PC (NM-III)

D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\CropImages\UFIMAGERS\<ufimager camera position>

Where *<ufimager camera position>* is:

- UImager1, UImager2, UImager3, UImager4

- 1.4.2 If anomalies are detected
Call **MCC** for action definition

2 ISPR RACK STATUS CHECK

NOTE

FIRST LEVEL TELEMETRY CHECK CAN BE DONE USING THREE DISPLAYS:

- THE RUCOLA SW MAIN PAGE
- THE GCS CONTROL DISPLAY
- THE GCT CONTROL DISPLAY

OTHER S/S DISPLAY CAN BE USED IF REQUIRED

2.1 ISPR Telemetry Verification

2.000 EDEN ISS Daily System Check

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Fig.4: RUCOLA SW Main Page

2.1.1 In RUCOLA SW Main Page

In the **ILL** Box

- Verify** Power LED = **Green**
- Verify** Camera Status = as required
- Verify** Lamp Status = as required
- Verify** Color Field = as required

In the **ILR** Box

- Verify** Power LED = **Green**
- Verify** Camera Status = as required
- Verify** Lamp Status = as required
- Verify** Color Field = as required

In the **GCS** Box

- Verify** Temperature (°C) = as required
- Verify** RH (%) = as required
- Verify** Fertigation Status = as required
- Verify** Atmosphere Control Status = as required

In the **GCT** Box

- Verify** Temperature (°C) = as required
- Verify** RH (%) = as required

2.000 EDEN ISS Daily System Check

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Verify Fertigation Status = as required

Verify Atmosphere Control Status = as required

In the **Services And Control** Box

Verify Temperature PCDH (°C) = as required

Verify Board Status = as required

Verify GCS Cooling Status = as required

Verify GCT Cooling Status = as required

In the **NDS** Box

Verify pH = as required

Verify EC(mS/cm) = as required

Verify Delivery H2O = as required

Verify Delivery Nut = as required

Verify Condensate Recovery = as required

Verify A Level = within the range

Verify B Level = within the range

Verify Acid = within the range

Verify Nutr. Sol Level = within the range

Verify Water Level = within the range

- 2.1.2 If one or more parameters and/or status is not as expected
Call **MCC** for action definition

2.000 EDEN ISS Daily System Check

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

RUCOLA	ILL	ILR	GCS	GCT	NDS	PCDH	RELAYS	SET	LOG	STOP
Temp. Chamber (°C)			21.790						14/09/2017 15:14:49	REFRESH
Humidity Chamber (%RH)			60.000						14/09/2017 15:14:50	REFRESH
CO2 (ppm)			702.347						14/09/2017 15:14:51	REFRESH
O2 (%)			20.827						14/09/2017 15:14:52	REFRESH
Chamber Pressure (bar)			0.000						12/07/2017 00:00:00	REFRESH
Left Heater Temp. (°C)			40.184						14/09/2017 15:14:52	REFRESH
Left Cooler Temp. (°C)			17.375						14/09/2017 15:14:55	REFRESH
Left THC Temp. (°C)			23.238						14/09/2017 15:14:54	REFRESH
Left THC Humidity (°C)			60.000						14/09/2017 15:14:53	REFRESH
Right Heater Temp. (°C)			42.348						14/09/2017 15:14:56	REFRESH
Right Cooler Temp. (°C)			12.184						14/09/2017 15:14:57	REFRESH
Right THC Temp. (°C)			23.465						14/09/2017 15:14:59	REFRESH
Right THC Humidity (°C)			60.000						14/09/2017 15:14:58	REFRESH
Day(T)/Night(F)			0.000						12/07/2017 00:00:00	REFRESH
pH Solution			5.000						14/09/2017 15:15:01	REFRESH
EC Solution (mS/cm)			1.000						14/09/2017 15:15:04	REFRESH
Temp. Solution (°C)			23.607						14/09/2017 15:15:05	REFRESH
Left Air Flow (slm)			1000.000						14/09/2017 15:15:06	REFRESH
Right Air Flow (slm)			1000.000						14/09/2017 15:15:09	REFRESH
Substrate 1 GS3 Temp. (°C)			25.256						14/09/2017 15:15:07	REFRESH

Fig. 5: GCS/GCT Displays

2.1.3 In the GCS/GCT Display

- Verify** Temp. Chamber(°C) = as required
- Verify** Humidity Chamber (%RH) = as required
- Verify** CO2(ppm) = as required
- Verify** O2(%) = as required
- Verify** Chamber Pressure (bar) = as required
- Verify** Left Heater Temp. (°C) = as required
- Verify** Left Cooler Temp (°C) = as required
- Verify** Left THC Temp (°C) = as required
- Verify** Left THC Humidity (°C) = as required
- Verify** Right Heater Temp. (°C) = as required
- Verify** Right Cooler Temp (°C) = as required
- Verify** Right THC Temp (°C) = as required
- Verify** Right THC Humidity (°C) = as required
- Verify** Day(T)/Night(F) = as required
- Verify** pH solution = as required
- Verify** EC Solution (mS/cm) = as required
- Verify** Temp Solution (°C) = as required
- Verify** Left Air Flow = as required
- Verify** Right Air Flow = as required
- Verify** Substrate 1 GS3 Temp (°C)= as required

2.000 EDEN ISS Daily System Check

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

- 2.1.4** If one or more parameters and/or status is not as expected
Call **MCC** for action definition

2.2 ISPR Plants Images Check

NOTE

THREE IMAGES ARE TAKEN PER GROWTH CHAMBER DURING THE DAY:
THESE IMAGES ARE STORED ON THE ISPR-PC IN THE MTF AND AUTOMATICALLY TRANSFERRED
ON THE CAMERA-PC IN THE NMIII AND HAVE TO BE DAILY CHECKED FOR PLANT HEALTH
ASSESSMENT

On the Camera-PC (NMIII) open the crop images stored in the following folder:

D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\CropImages\<ispr camera position>

Where *<ispr camera position>* is:

- GCScam, GCSUFlcam, GCTcam

If anomalies are detected

Call **MCC** for action definition

2.100 Plant Sowing

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Plant seeds for germination and preparation of plant cultivation

DURATION

20-30 min per tray

TOOLS

Tweezers

Wooden stick

Stanley knife

ITEMS

Plastic Plugs Holder Tray

Rock-wool plugs

Polypropylene tray (2)

Seeds

Vermiculite

Nutrient solution (10 liters per tray)

Water (0.5 liters)

NOTE

THIS PROCEDURE IS APPLICABLE TO TOMATO, PEPPER, CUCUMBER, LETTUCE, SPINACH, RADISH, BASIL. ALL THE OTHER PLANTS WILL BE PLANTED DIRECTLY IN THE ROWS OF THE TRAY USING ROCKWOOL

SS-WB

1.

ROCK-WOOL PLUGS PREPARATION FOR SOWING

CAUTION

TO AVOID SEED CONTAMINATION AND POSSIBLE FUTURE PLANTS DISEASE, CAREFULLY WASH YOUR HAND BEFORE THE OPERATIONS

Fig. 1: Plastic Plugs Holder

2.100 Plant Sowing

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Fig. 2 Plastic Rockwool Plugs Holder Tray

Fig.3: Polypropylene tray

- 1.1 Using the Stanley Knife, cut the Plastic Plugs Holder Tray (fig. 1) down to the size of the polypropylene trays
- 1.2 Insert the Rockwool Plugs in the plastic holder dedicated housings (fig. 2)
- 1.3 Fill one of the the polypropylene tray (fig. 3) with the nutrient solution
- 1.4 Submerge the Plastic Plugs Holder Tray in the nutrient solution until the rockwool plugs are completely wet (wait form 5 to 10 minutes). To be repeated when necessary after visual check
- 1.5 Remove the Plastic Plugs Holder Tray from the nutrient solution and put it in the other polypropylene tray for the nursery compartment

2. SOWING

NOTE
THE NUMBER OF SEEDS TO BE SOWED DEPENDS ON THE PLANT TO BE CULTIVATED. THE OPERATOR WILL BE INSTRUCTED FROM THE MCC BEFORE THE ACTIVITY TAKES PLACE

- 2.1 Sow one or more seeds per plug as per plant requirement. Use tweezers for larger seeds and wooden stick for small seeds (it is recommended to moisten the

2.100 Plant Sowing

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

stick before the operations to facilitate the attachment of the seed to the stick itself)

2.2 Cover the seeds with Vermiculite

FEG

3. TRANFERRING THE TRAY TO THE NURSERY

3.1 Transfer the polypropylene tray in the FEG, in position L12-1S

SS-WB

4. CLOSEOUT

4.1 Clean and stow the polypropylene tray, and all the other objects and items used for the sowing activity as per Stowage Note

4.2 Carefully wash your hands

FEG

5. GERMINATION MONITORING

5.1 Check the plugs status every day. Make sure that it stay moist. Use water as necessary.

2.105 Plant Thinning

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Plant thinning (or spacing) to increase the light interception

DURATION

20-30 min per tray

TOOLS

Large Tweezers

ITEMS

Polypropylene tray for nursery compartment

3D Printed Plastic Plug Holders (number as needed)

Plug Holders Boxes (number as needed)

NOTE

THINNING IS A PROCESS NECESSARY TO INCREASE THE SPACE BETWEEN THE GERMINATED PLANTS IN ORDER TO IMPROVE THE LIGHT INTERCEPTION. CREW IS REQUESTED TO SELECT THE BEST-GERMINATED PLANTS FOR THE NEXT GROWTH PHASE AND TO DISPOSE THE WEAK PLANTS AND THE UNGERMINATED SEEDS.

FEG 1. ROCK-WOOL PLUGS HOLDER BOXES PREPARATION

CAUTION

TO AVOID SEED CONTAMINATION AND POSSIBLE FUTURE PLANTS DISEASE THE HANDS HAVE TO BE CAREFULLY WASHED BEFORE THE OPERATIONS START

Fig. 1 Plastic Rockwool Plugs Holder Tray

2.105 Plant Thinning

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Fig. 2: 3D Printed Plastic Plug Holders

Fig. 3: 3D Printed Plastic Plug Holder Box

- 1.1 Using a large tweezers remove the rockwool plug with the germinated plant from the Plastic Rockwool Plugs Holder Tray (fig.1). Pay attention to not damage the shoot
- 1.2 Insert the rockwool plug into the 3D printed plastic plug holder (fig. 2)
- 1.3 Insert the 3D Printed Plastic Plug Holder in the Box
- 1.4 Repeat for ALL the germinated plants selected for cultivation

FEG 2. TRAY PREPARATION FOR IRRIGATION

2.105 Plant Thinning

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Fig.4: Irrigation system in the polypropylene tray

Fig.5: Boxes inserted in the polypropylene tray

NOTE

THE POLYPROPYLENE TRAY(S) WHERE THE 3D-PRINTED PLASTIC BOX WILL BE INSERTED IS(ARE) CONNECTED TO THE NUTRIENT DELIVER SYSTEM. NEVERTHELESS THE INTERNAL TUBING IS NOT EQUIPPED WITH NOZZLES, SINCE THE OBJECTIVE IS TO ONLY FILL THE TRAY WITH THE RIGHT QUANTITY OF WATER/NUTRIENT SOLUTION IN ORDER TO MAKE THEM AVAILABLE TO THE ROCKWOOL PLANT HOLDER (FIG.4)

- 2.1 Put the boxes in the polypropilene tray in the nursery compartment (fig. 5)
- 2.2 Feed the polypropilene tray with nutrient solution/water by means of the NDS
- 3 CLOSEOUT**
 - 3.1 Reinstall the Plastic Rockwool Plugs Holder Tray with the not germinated seeds in the nursery compartment. If not germination occur after two weeks, just waste them
 - 3.2 Carefully wash the hand
 - 3.3 Stow all the tools as necessary

2.105 Plant Thinning

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

2.110 Plant transplant to the aeroponic system

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Transplant the germinated plants from the styrofoam tray to the aeroponic system

DURATION

Dependent on plant development

TOOLS

Large tweezers

ITEMS

Polypropilene tray for aeroponic system

Tray Lid

Plugs Holder

Latex gloves

NOTE

THIS PROCEDURE IS VALID FOR THE PLANT TO BE TRANSFERRED. IF THE PLANTS ARE NEEDED FOR QUALITY AND SAFETY ANALYSIS THEY HAVE TO BE LABELLED

SS- 1.
WB

PLANTS TRANSPLANTING

CAUTION

TO AVOID CONTAMINATION AND POSSIBLE FUTURE PLANTS DISEASE, THE HANDS HAVE TO BE CAREFULLY WASHED BEFORE STARTING THE OPERATIONS

Fig.1: Germinated seeds with roots ready for the aeroponic system

2.110 Plant transplant to the aeroponic system

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Fig. 2: Four of the six tray lids used for EDEN ISS cultivation project

NOTE

SIX DIFFERENT TRAY LIDS HAVE BEEN DESIGNED FOR SPACING OF TARGETS PLANTS (FIG.2). THE TRAY LIDS OUTLINE THE MAXIMAL SPACING FOR PLANT POSITIONING.

- 1.1 Verify that the roots of the germinated seeds have grown through the plug (fig.1)
- 1.2 Insert the plug holder in the tray lid hole (fig. 2)

2. TRANSFERRING THE TRAY TO THE FEG RACK

NOTE

THE TRAY POSITION DEPENDS ON THE CROP GROWTH AND SHAPE AND THE PLANT CULTIVATION PLAN. THAT INFORMATION WILL BE PROVIDED BY MCC BEFORE THE OPERATIONS STARTS

- 2.1 Install the tray in the rack position as per MCC instructions
- 2.2 Connect the tray to the drainage line
- 2.3 Connect the tray to the water/nutrient solution feeding line

SS- WB 3 CLOSEOUT

- 3.1 Carefully wash your hands

2.110 Plant transplant to the aeroponic system

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

3.2 Clean the workbench

2.120 Crop Management

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE1)

OBJECTIVE

Monitor the crop development and the take the actions for steering plant growth, like pruning, training, pollination and early disease recognition

DURATION

Crop dependent

TOOLS

Pruning Shears or knife

String for supporting Tomato (indeterminate)/Pepper from upper shelf

Wooden sticks and spiral wire Frame (4-6 lengths to be formed as wished)

Foam ties

Brush

Plant vibrator for pollination

ITEMS

Hydrogen peroxide or Virkon-S

NOTE

CROP DEVELOPMENT SHALL BE REGULARLY MONITORED FOR THREE MAIN REASONS:

1. EARLY DISEASE DETECTION.
2. PLANT PRUNING/TRAINING (crop dependent)
3. HARVESTING (IF POSSIBLE)

THE GREENHOSUE OPERATOR SHALL HAVE A VISUAL CHECK WITHIN THE FEG and MONITOR THE PLANT IMAGES AS ACQUIRED BY THE PLANT HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM .

FEG 1. PLANTS HEALTH STATUS CHECK

CAUTION

TO AVOID CONTAMINATION AND POSSIBLE FUTURE PLANTS DISEASE, THE HANDS HAVE TO BE CAREFULLY WASHED BEFORE THE START OF THE OPERATIONS

- 1.1 Check that plants are not affected by any anomaly like spots on leaves (fig. 1) or on the stems (fig. 2) and wilting signals (fig.3)
- 1.2 If abnormal appearance is recognized take additional pictures of the plants affected and send them to MCC
- 1.3 Wait for instructions and coordinate with MCC any corrective action.

Fig. 1: Example of brown spot on leaf (leaf lesion of *Alternaria Solani*)

Fig. 2: Example of sunken spots on stem (stem lesion of *Alternaria Solani*)

Fig.3: Example of a wilted tomato plant

2.120 Crop Management

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE1)

NOTE

1. TRAINING IS THE TERM FOR THE PROCEDURE OF SHAPING THE PLANT INTO A DESIRED OPTIMAL GROWTH ARCHITECTURE IN ORDER TO PROVIDE A SUPPORT TO THE PLANT THEMSELVES AND TO IMPROVE LIGHT INTERCEPTION AND AIR MOVEMENT. TRAINING IS NEEDED FOR TALL PLANTS, THEREFORE FOR INDETERMINATE TOMATOES, PEPPERS AND CUCUMBERS.
2. TOMATO, PEPPER AND CUCUMBER PLANTS TRAINING IS MANAGED USING BY MEANS OF WIRES THAT ARE ATTACHED AT THE PLANT MAIN STEM SUPPORT AND TO HOOKS FIXED TO THE RACK STRUCTURE CLOSE TO THE LED LAMPS.

Fig. 4: Cucumber Training

2.120 Crop Management

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE1)

Fig. 5: Tomatoes training

When plants have reached approximately an height of 60-80 cm, attach string to the stem support structure, wind it around the stem and attach the string to the hook close to the LED lamp. Leave it slack enough so that the plant can hang in it a grow. As the plant continues to grow, keep wrapping the string around the stem to support the whole plant.

3

HAND POLLINATION

NOTE

Hand pollination (also called "mechanical pollination") is a technique used when wind or self-pollination is insufficient, and has the objective to promote the transfer of pollen from the anthers to the stigma of flowers. That applies to closed environment like that of the EDEN ISS operations. Two crops in the FEG in EDEN ISS are affected: tomatoes and peppers. Tomato and Pepper plants are managed in the same way.

3.1

Tomato/Pepper hand pollination

2.120 Crop Management

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE1)

NOTE

1. Tomato and pepper hand pollination requires the only shaking of the flowers in order that the pollen is distributed around. That can be achieved in different ways:
 - Gentle Shaking of the flowers or even of the entire plant (daily)
 - Using a plant vibrator
2. The pollination activity has to be done every day as each individual flower opens

Fig. 6: Example of a plant vibrator

Fig. 7: Shaking Flowers by means of a plant vibrator (4-5 intensity) every day

3.1 Gently shake the flowers by means of the plant vibrator. (Gently shake the flowers by hand or using a brush if the plant vibrator is not available)

3.2 Repeat until all the flowers have been shaken

4 PLANTS PRUNING

NOTE

2.120 Crop Management

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE1)

1. PLANT PRUNING IS AIMED AT THE REMOVAL OF LEAVES AND/OR LATERAL SHOOTS IN ORDER TO ALLOCATE ASSIMILATES TO THE FRUITS INSTEAD OF LEAVES. A SECONDARY AIM IS TO INCREASE THE AIR CIRCULATION AND/OR LIGHT INTERCEPTION. THIS METHODOLOGY APPLIES TO THE FRUITING CROPS (TOMATOE, CUCUMBER AND PEPPER).

4.1 Pruning Tomatoes Plants

NOTE

1. THIS PROCEDURES APPLIES TO INDETERMINATE TOMATO ONLY. A COMPACT 'INDETERMINATE' TOMATO WILL GROW CONTINUOUSLY IN HEIGHT AND SHOULD BE CULTIVATED WITH 2 STEMS. IN THE JUVENILE STAGE, THE MAIN STEM IS CUT JUST ABOVE THE THIRD LEAF; TWO TO THREE SIDE SHOOTS WILL APPEAR. AFTER 10 TO 12 DAYS RETAIN THE 2 BEST SIDE SHOOTS AND REMOVE THE THIRD. TWO STEMS WILL CONTINUE TO DEVELOP AND OTHER SIDE SHOOTS SHOULD BE REMOVED DURING CULTIVATION.
 2. HERE ARE SOME KEY TOMATO PRUNING TERMS:
 - LEADERS: THE LEADER IS THE PRIMARY STEM. WHEN A SECOND LEADER IS ALLOWED TO DEVELOP, BOTH GROW IN A Y-SHAPED PATTERN (FIG.4) .
 - COMPETITORS GROW AT A 45-DEGREES ANGLE FROM WHERE LATERAL GROWTH MEETS THE STALK (FIG.6)
- LEAVES USUALLY GROWS AT A 90-DEGREE ANGLE FROM THE STALK. THIS GROWTH IS THE PHOTOSYNTHESIZING POWERHOUSE OF THE PLANT

Fig. 8: Y shaped pattern, with clearly identified the leaders stems

Fig.9: Lateral (Leaf) growth and emerging competitor

Fig. 10 Leaders vs competitors

2.120 Crop Management

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE1)

Fig. 11: Competitor life cycle

- 4.1.1 Break young competitors (ca. 2 cm) off with you fingers. Do NOT use a knife (Fig. 8)
- 4.1.2 Collect and remove any discarded plant material from the area to reduce the risk of infection or pathogen growth
- 4.2 **Pruning cucumber plants**

NOTE

Once cucumber plants have begun to set fruit, the growth rate increases both in the plant and the fruit. Pruning the plant to remove lateral, or side shoots, redirects this plant energy into the cucumbers themselves, often producing greater yields and healthier fruit.

Fig.12: Main Stem and lateral growths

2.120 Crop Management

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE1)

- 4.2.1 Make sure your pruning shears, or knife are SHARP and CLEAN to avoid any rough cuts, and any transfer of disease. Use hydrogen peroxide as a sanitizer if working with diseased plants
- 4.2.2 Locate the cucumber plant's main stem. You should be able to isolate it easily by going to the base of the plant at soil level and following the single largest stem that hasn't branched out (Fig. 9)
- 4.2.3 Look for any lateral growth in the form of small shoots growing out of the sides of the main stem and cut them off (Fig. 8). If left on the plant, they will grow into competitors and result in smaller yields
- 4.2.4 Remove the first 4 to 6 shoots growing closest to the base of the plant
- 4.2.5 Repeat this process for all individual cucumber plants and tie the remaining stem loosely to the support. Be careful not to crush blossoms or bend stem too sharply, as this will cut off water and nutrients to the cucumbers forming on them
- 4.2.6 Prune all lateral shoots as they appear, which can be as often as once a day once the plants' roots are established and the plant enter their rapid growth stage
- 4.2.7 Remove undersized or damaged cucumbers as well as any that appear diseased

4.3 Pruning Pepper Plants

NOTE

1. PEPPER PLANTS ARE INDETERMINATE PLANTS, THAT IS, THEY CONTINUALLY GROW NEW STEMS AND LEAVES. PLANTS ARE GENERALLY PRUNED EVERY TWO WEEKS. AS NEW LEAVES AND LATERAL SIDE SHOOTS DEVELOP FROM THE AXILS OF THE NEW NODES ON THE GROWING STEMS, THEY HAVE TO BE PRUNED TO MAINTAIN THE TWO MAIN-STEM ARCHITECTURE OF THE PLANT.
2. HEREINAFTER SOME KEY WORDS FOR PEPPER PRUNING
 - NODE: A NODE IS DEFINED AS A POINT ON THE STEM FROM WHICH LEAVES ARISE AND THE LENGTH OF STEM BETWEEN NODES IS CALLED AN INTERNODE.
 - THE TERM "AXIL" REFERS TO THE UPPER ANGLE FORMED BY THE JUNCTION OF A LEAF (OR LATERAL) WITH THE STEM

2.120 Crop Management

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE1)

Fig. 13: Pepper plants – selecting the stem to be grown

Fig. 14: Pepper plants, flowers removal from the first node stems

2.120 Crop Management

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE1)

Fig.15: Pepper Plants: Stem Pruning

- 4.3.1 By the time the plants will have developed 2 to 3 stem shoots at the fork, cut the weakest stem leaving the two strongest (Some plants could develop only two stems. No pruning action is required)
- 4.3.2 By the time the flowers are appearing on the first node extra stems, remove them (fig.10)
- 4.3.3 Remove the lateral stem (fig. 11) on the second and third nodes
- 4.3.4 Remove the competitors (as per tomato pruning, Fig.8)

2.130 Plant Harvesting

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Plant harvesting during and/or at the end of the growth cycle

DURATION

Crop dependent

TOOLS

Pruning Shears or Scissors

ITEMS

Plastic containers (as necessary)

Latex Gloves

Hydrogen peroxide or Virkon-S.

NOTE

TWO DIFFERENT APPROACHES ARE CONSIDERED FOR HARVESTING:

- SINGLE POINT HARVESTING EVENT (LEAFY GREENS AND RADISH)
- MULTIPLE HARVESTING EVENTS (LETTUCE, HERBS, TOMATOES, PEPPER AND CUCUMBER)

FEG 1

PREPARATION

CAUTION

- 1. TO AVOID CONTAMINATION THE HANDS HAVE TO BE CAREFULLY WASHED BEFORE THE OPERATIONS**
- 2. THE PRUNING SHEARS OR CUTTERS SHALL BE STERILISED BEFORE STARTING THE OPERATIONS**

- 1.1** Wash your hand
- 1.2** Sterilize the pruning shears or the scissors
- 1.3** GOTO step 2.1 for Leafy Greens harvesting
GOTO step 2.2 for Radish harvesting
GOTO step 3.1 for Chives harvesting
GOTO step 3.2 for Parsely harvesting
GOTO step 3.3 for Basil harvesting
GOTO step 3.4 for Lettuce harvesting
GOTO step 3.5 for Tomato harvesting
GOTO step 3.6 for Pepper harvesting
GOTO step 3.7 for Cucumber harvesting

2. SINGLE POINT HARVESTING EVENTS

2.1 Leafy Greens Harvesting

NOTE

LEAFY GREENS CAN BE HARVESTED AND EATEN AFTER 4 TO 6 WEEKS AFTER PLANT TRANSPLANTING.

2.130 Plant Harvesting

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Fig. 1: Leafy Green Harvested. From the left: Swiss Chard, Rockets and Red Mustard)

- 2.1.1 Cut each plant at the base by means of the pruning shears, and put an elastic cord around the stems if necessary (fig. 1)
- 2.1.2 Collect the cut plants in the plastic container
- 2.1.3 GOTO step 4

2.2 Radish Harvesting

NOTE

1. RADISH CAN BE HARVESTED AND EATEN AFTER 3 WEEKS AFTER SOWING. AT THIS STAGE THE EXPECTED TAPROOT DIAMETER SHOULD BE IN THE RANGE 20-35 MM
2. BOTH THE TAP ROOT AND THE LEAVES ARE EDIBLE

- 2.2.1 Gently pull the radish plants from the plug and collect them in the plastic container
- 2.2.2 GOTO step 4

3 MULTIPLE POINT HARVESTING EVENTS

3.1 Chives harvesting

NOTE

1. CHIVES CAN BE HARVESTED 6 WEEKS AFTER SOWING. CHIVES CAN BE TOTALLY HARVESTED; PLANTS WILL REGROW VERY EASILY AND CAN BE HARVESTED AGAIN AFTER 4 WEEKS. THIS CAN BE REPEATED AT LEAST 3 TIMES AND PROBABLY MORE.
2. DON'T CLIP TOO CLOSE TO THE BULB OR THEY WON'T REGROW – LEAVE AT LEAST 2 CM ATTACHED TO THE BULB ABOVE THE SOIL. CUT FROM THE OUTSIDE OF THE BUNCH FIRST.

2.130 Plant Harvesting

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Fig. 2: Chives Harvesting

Fig. 3: Harvested Chives

3.1.1 Gather leaves into a bunch and cut with a scissors (fig. 2). Put an elastic cord at the base of the bunch if necessary (fig. 3)

3.1.2 Collect the cut plants in the plastic container

3.1.3 GOTO step 4

3.2 Parsley Harvesting

NOTE

1. WAIT UNTIL FOR HARVESTING THE PLANT IS (15 CM HEIGHT – 4 WEEKS OF PLANT DEVELOPMENT)
2. WHEN HARVESTING PARSLEY; MAKE SURE THAT THE YOUNGEST LEAF IS NOT CUT OFF. THIS GROWING POINT WILL GROW VERY EASILY AND CAN BE HARVESTED AGAIN AFTER 4 WEEKS. THIS CAN BE REPEATED AT LEAST 3 TIMES AND PROBABLY MORE.

2.130 Plant Harvesting

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Fig.4: Parsley – Three Stems

- 3.2.1 Gather stem and leaves in a bunch and cut it using a scissors. Snip your harvest from the base of the plant to encourage more growth. Cut leaves from the outer portions first so your parsley can focus on growing new leaves from the center of the plant
- 3.2.2 Put an elastic cord at the base of the bunch if necessary
- 3.2.3 Collect the bunches in the plastic container
- 3.2.4 GOTO step 4
- 3.3 Basil Harvesting**

NOTE

BASIL CAN BE HARVESTED AS SOON AS THE PLANT REACHES ABOUT 20 CM IN HEIGHT, AND IN ANY CASE BEFORE THE PLANTS START TO BUD AND THE FLOWERS START TO BLOOM (ALSO KNOWN AS “BOLTING”).

Fig. 5: Basil Harvesting

Fig. 6: Basil plant after harvesting

- 3.3.1 Pinch or cut each stem just above the second set of leaves
- 3.3.2 Collect the basil leaves in the plastic container

2.130 Plant Harvesting

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

3.3.3 Pinch off any flower spikes right away

3.3.4 GOTO Step 4

3.4 Lettuce Harvesting

NOTE

LETTUCE SPREAD HARVEST CAN COMMENCE 4 WEEKS AFTER SOWING AT THE MOMENT THAT THE PLANTS TOUCH EACH OTHER AND MAXIMUM SOIL COVER IS REACHED. THE OUTER (1-3) LEAVES CAN BE HARVESTED FROM EACH PLANT AND BE EATEN. SPREAD HARVEST CAN BE CARRIED OUT ONCE OR TWICE WEEKLY UNTIL PLANTS START TO BOLT FOR ANOTHER 7 WEEKS

Fig. 7: Lettuce crispy Green Expertise – 20 plants per trays (left), 1 plant (right)

Fig. 8: Cutting the lettuce leaves

3.4.1 Harvest the outer (1-3) leaves from each plant. Pinch them off with your fingers at the base of the plant (fig. 8)

3.4.2 Collect the leaves in the plastic container

3.4.3 GOTO Step 4

3.5 Tomato Harvesting

2.130 Plant Harvesting

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

NOTE

DWARF TOMATO CAN BE HARVESTED STARTING FROM 12 WEEKS AFTER SOWING . THE PERFECT TOMATO FOR PICKING WILL BE FIRM AND RED REGARDLESS OF SIZE, WITH PERHAPS SOME YELLOW REMAINING AROUND THE STEM. A RIPE TOMATO WILL BE ONLY SLIGHTLY SOFT.

Fig.9 Tomato grapes ready for harvesting

3.5.1 Twist or pinch the tomato from the the stem with your fingers

3.5.2 Collect the tomatoes in the plastic containers

3.5.3 GOTO step 4

3.6 Pepper Harvesting

NOTE

1. PEPPER GROWS VERY SLOWLY AND IT TAKES ABOUT 4 MONTHS TO HARVEST THE FIRST FRUITS
2. BELL PEPPERS GROW IN A RANGE OF COLORS, INCLUDING GREEN, RED, DARK PURPLE, YELLOW AND ORANGE. IN GENERAL, THEY ARE READY TO HARVEST WHEN THEY ARE THE FULL COLOR OF THE VARIETY PLANTED
3. PICKING PEPPERS BEFORE THEY ARE FULLY MATURE WILL ENCOURAGE THE PLANT TO PRODUCE MORE FLOWERS AND, THUS, MORE PEPPERS.

Fig.11: Clipping Pepper using scissors

2.130 Plant Harvesting

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Fig. 12 Harvested Pepper

- 3.6.1 Clip the pepper off at the stem using the pruning shears (fig. 11). Cut as close to the branch as possible. Alternatively, ripe peppers may detach easily from the plant stem with a gentle twist.
- 3.6.2 Collect the Peppers in the Plastic Container
- 3.6.3 GOTO Step 4

3.7 Cucumber Harvesting

NOTE

CUCUMBERS NEED A LONG GROWING SEASON AND ARE READY FOR HARVEST IN 50 TO 70 DAYS. THE FRUITS RIPEN AT DIFFERENT TIMES ON THE VINE, SO IT IS ESSENTIAL TO PICK THEM AS THEY ARE READY. CUCUMBER SHOULD BE HARVESTED WHEN THE FINAL SIZE HAS BEEN REACHED, WHICH IS AROUND 10 CM LONG (AROUND 60GRAM). CUCUMBERS MUST BE PICKED BEFORE THEY SHOW THE FIRST SIGNS OF YELLOWING, WHICH INDICATE THE FRUITS ARE PAST THEIR PRIME.

Fig. 12: Cucumber Harvesting

- 3.7.1 Remove fruits that are stunted and not growing, have rotten ends or are past their prime. This prevents the plant from focusing energy on fruits that are a waste

2.130 Plant Harvesting

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

anyway.

3.7.2 Use pruning shears or scissors when harvesting ripe cucumbers Cut the stem ¼ inch above the fruit (using the garden shears will prevent injury to the vine by twisting or pulling)

3.7.3 Lay gently the cucumber in the plastic container (the cucumbers are sensitive to bruising)

4 CLOSEOUT

4.1 If. no other harvesting are possible)

Remove the drawer from the rack for plant disposal and drawer preparation for new plant cultivation

4.2 Clean the scissors and/or the pruning shears and stow it/them

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

OBJECTIVE

Configure the Future Exploration Greenhouse in preparation of Antarctica Operations.

DURATION

120 min

TOOLS

N/A

ITEMS

Fresh Water (20 litre tank)

Stock Solution A (4 litres bottle)

Stock Solution B (4 litre bottle)

Acid Solution (4 litre bottle)

Base Solution (4 litre bottle)

Protective Glasses

Protective Mask

Protective Gloves

NOTE

1. AT THIS STAGE IT IS SUPPOSED THAT:
 - a. THE MTF IS CONFIGURED AND OPERATIVE, I.E. ALL THE ASSEMBLING ACTIVITIES HAVE BEEN COMPLETED, THE S/S TEST HAVE BEEN DONE WITH SUCCESS, AND THE MTF ENVIRONMENTAL PARAMETERS (TEMPERATURE, HUMIDITY, LIGHTING) ARE UNDER ARGUS CONTROL ALLOWING FOR MTF ABITABILITY
 - b. THE SETUP OF THE TRAYS FOR HAS BEEN DONE AS PER THE FOLLOWING PROCEDURES:
 - i. 2.100 PLANT SOWING
 - ii. 2.110 PLANT TRANSFER TO GROWTH TRAYS
2. THIS PROCEDURE MANAGES TWO MAIN ASPECTS:
 - a. THE PREPARATION OF THE NUTRIENT SOLUTION FOR THE CULTIVATION CYCLE
 - b. THE SETUP OF THE FEG IN TERMS OF:
 - i. ATMOSPHERE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (T, RH AND CO₂, DAY/NIGHT CYCLE)
 - ii. NUTRIENT DELIVERY SYSTEM SETUP (pH AND EC OF THE NUTRIENT SOLUTION, IRRIGATION CYCLE)
 - iii. ILLUMINATION SYSTEM (LIGHT INTENSITY AND COMPOSITION, ILLUMINATION CYCLE)
3. THE INSTRUCTION FOR THE CAMERA SYSTEM SETUP ARE PROVIDED IN THE FOLLOWING TWO PROCEDURES:
 - a. 2.500 VIDEOCAMERAS CONFIGURATION FOR PLANT MONITORING
 - b. 2.510 EDEN ISS DATA AND IMAGES ACQUISITION AND TRANSFER

- SS 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION**
- 1.1 Retrieve the items and tools
 - 1.2 Verify the fresh water tank is filled

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

If the tank is empty than fill it. **PERFORM** Procedure “4.300 Fresh Water Tank Filling”

- 1.3 Verify the waste water is empty

If the tank is filled than empty it. **PERFORM** Procedure “4.310 Waste Water Tank Emptying”

SS 2 NUTRIENT SOLUTION PREPARATION

NOTE

THIS PART OF THE PROCEDURE APPLIES TO BOTH THE BULK SOLUTION TANK #1 AND THE BULK SOLUTION TANK #2. IN FACT, EVEN IF THEY COULD BE FILLED WITH TWO DIFFERENT NUTRIENT SOLUTIONS, THE OPERATION TO DO THAT IS THE SAME FOR THE TWO TANKS.

WARNING

1. POTENTIAL ELECTRICAL SHOCK HAZARD: THE ACTIVITIES HAVE TO BE DONE WITH THE NDS COMPONENT OFF
2. POTENTIAL CHEMICAL HAZARD: THE OPERATOR MUST WEAR INDIVIDUAL PROTECTIVE ITEMS (GLOVES, GLASSES AND MASK) DURING THE OPERATIONS

- 2.1 If the NDS components are active

IRRIGATION SENSORS		IRRIGATION EQUIPMENT CONTROLS				
PUMP PRESSURE 1	0.09 bar	HP PUMP 1	Manual	Off	Off	0 %
PUMP PRESSURE 2	0.00 bar	HP PUMP 2	Manual	Off	Off	0 %
PUMP PRESSURE 3	0.10 bar	HP PUMP 3	Manual	Off	Off	0 %
PUMP PRESSURE 4	0.10 bar	HP PUMP 4	Manual	Off	Off	0 %
PUMP PRESSURE 5	0.08 bar	HP PUMP 5	Manual	Off	Off	0 %
PUMP PRESSURE 6	0.11 bar	HP PUMP 6	Manual	Off	Off	0 %
PUMP PRESSURE 7	0.00 bar	HP PUMP 7	Manual	Off	Off	0 %
PUMP PRESSURE 8	0.00 bar	HP PUMP 8	Manual	Off	Off	0 %
		HP PUMP OUTPUT CONTROLS				
		OVERRIDES (HP PUMPS 1-8) 0.00 %				

Figure 1: Nutrient Delivery System Display – Irrigation Equipment Control

- 2.1.1 In the Irrigation Equipment Control box

Turn **OFF** all high pressure aeroponic *pumps fed from Tank 1(2)* (Fig. 1):

- Cmd HP1 Pump to **Manual Off**
- Cmd HP2 Pump to **Manual Off**
- Cmd HP3 Pump to **Manual Off**
- Cmd HP4 Pump to **Manual Off**
- Cmd HP5 Pump to **Manual Off**
- Cmd HP6 Pump to **Manual Off**
- Cmd HP7 Pump to **Manual Off**
- Cmd HP8 Pump to **Manual Off**

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

TANK 1 EQUIPMENT CONTROL				
	BULK NS TANK 1 CONTROLS	Dosing	Status	0.00 %
EC Setpoint	2.20 mS	A Dosing Pump	Manual Off	Off 0 %
pH Setpoint	5.90 pH	B Dosing Pump	Manual Off	Off 0 %
			Filling Status	100.00 %
	SOLENOID FW TANK 1	Manual Off	Off	0 %
	REC PUMP TANK 1	Manual Off	Off	0 %
SHARED TANK EQUIPMENT CONTROL				
	ACID DOSING PUMP	Manual Off	Off	0 %
	ACID SOLENOID	Manual Off	Off	0 %
	BASE DOSING PUMP	Manual Off	Off	0 %
	BASE SOLENOID	Manual Off	Off	0 %
	PUMP FW	Manual Off	Off	0 %
	OZONE GENERATOR	Manual Off	Off	0 %

Figure 2: Nutrient Delivery System Display – Tanks Equipment Control

2.1.2 Turn OFF the Tanks Actuators (fig. 2):

In Tank 1(2) Equipment Control box

Cmd A Dosing Pump to Manual Off

Cmd B Dosing Pump to Manual Off

Cmd Solenoid FW Tank 1(2) to Manual Off

Cmd Rec Pump Tank 1(2) to Manual Off

In Shared Tank Equipment Control box

Cmd Acid Dosing Pump to Manual Off

Cmd Acid Solenoid to Manual Off

Cmd Base Dosing Pump to Manual Off

Cmd Base Solenoid to Manual Off

Cmd Pump FW to Manual Off

Cmd Ozone Generator to Manual Off

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

Figure 3: Power Rack Interface – NDS Service Section Line

2.1.3 On the Power Rack Interface – NDS Service Section Line (Fig. 3)

Switch OFF the Air Pump 1

Switch OFF the Air Pump 2

Switch OFF the Circ Pump 1

Switch OFF the Circ Pump 2

2.2 Wear appropriate Personal Protective Equipment (Gloves, Mask and Glasses)

Figure 4: NDS Rack – Stock, Acid and Base Solution Tank 2

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

Figure 5: NDS Rack – Bulk Solution Tank 2

2.3 Fill the Stock, Acid And Basic tanks (Fig. 4)

2.4 Remove the Lid Panel from the Bulk Solution Tank 1(2) (Fig. 5)

Remark: The bolts are used to align the cover - no need to unscrew them

2.5 Take out one of the two EC sensors from the Bulk Solution Tank 1(2) lid panel

2.6 Fill Bulk Solution Tank 1(2) to about half way up with fresh water

2.7 Slowly dump into the Bulk Solution Tank 1(2) the pre-made 4 L Stock solution A (B)

NOTE

1. **ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY SETUP.** EC TARGET VALID PARAMETERS ARE:
 - a. Leafy Crops: 2.3 ± 0.2 mS/cm²
 - b. Fruit Crops: 3.5 ± 0.2 mS/cm²
2. **pH Setup.** pH TARGET VALID PARAMETERS ARE FROM 5.2 TO 6.5

Fig. 6: pH and EC transmitters

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

- 2.8 While watching the EC values (Fig. 6) acquired by means of the removed EC sensor, slowly add fresh water into the NDS tank (1/2) until the EC value is close to the required range
- 2.9 Reinstall the lid panel on the Bulk Solution Tank 1(2)
- 2.10 Reinstall the EC sensor in the Bulk Solution Tank 1(2) lid panel
- 2.11 Take off the protective gloves, mask and glasses
- 2.12 On the Power Rack Interface – NDS Service Section Line (Fig. 3)

Switch ON the Air Pump 1
Swicth ON the Air Pump 2
Switch ON the Circ Pump 1
Swicth ON the Circ Pump 2

TANK 1 EQUIPMENT CONTROL			
BULK NS TANK 1 CONTROLS			
EC Setpoint	2.20 mS	A Dosing Pump	Automatic Off 0 %
pH Setpoint	5.90 pH	B Dosing Pump	Automatic Off 0 %
SOLENOID FW TANK 1			
REC PUMP TANK 1			
Filling Status 100.00 %			
Automatic Off 0 %			
Automatic Off 0 %			
SHARED TANK EQUIPMENT CONTROL			
ACID DOSING PUMP			
Automatic Off 0 %			
ACID SOLENOID			
Automatic Off 0 %			
BASE DOSING PUMP			
Automatic Off 0 %			
BASE SOLENOID			
Automatic Off 0 %			
PUMP FW			
Automatic Off 0 %			
OZONE GENERATOR			
Automatic Off 0 %			

Figure 7: Nutrient Delivery System Display – Tanks Equipment Control. NDS Configuration

- 2.13 Turn ON the Tanks Actuators and input the EC and pH Setpoints (Fig. 7):

In Tank 1(2) Equipment Control Control box

Input EC Setpoint = as required

Input pH Setpoint = as required

Cmd A Dosing Pump to **Automatic**

Cmd B Dosing Pump to **Automatic**

Cmd Solenoid FW Tank 1(2) to **Automatic**

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth

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Cmd Rec Pump Tank 1(2) to Automatic

In Shared Tank Equipment Control box

Cmd Acid Dosing Pump to **Automatic**

Cmd Acid Solenoid to **Automatic**

Cmd Base Dosing Pump to **Automatic**

Cmd Base Solenoid to **Automatic**

Cmd Pump FW to **Automatic**

Cmd Ozone Generator to **Automatic**

- 2.14 After 30 minutes, verify on the pH and EC transmitters that the pH and the EC have been adjusted to the defined target

If the EC and/or the pH are out of range

PERFORM procedure 5.600 NDS pH and EC Setting Failure

NOTE

1. EACH OF THE EIGHT NDS RACKS CAN BE SET TO RECEIVE NUTRIENT SOLUTION FROM EITHER TANK 1 OR TANK 2. TO CHANGE THE SOURCE SOLUTION, BOTH THE FEED VALVE AND THE RETURN VALVE MUST BE SWITCHED TO THE APPROPRIATE TANK. TO CHANGE THE FEED VALVE FOR ANY RACK, REFER TO THE DIAGRAM OF VALVE POSITION (FIG. 9)

Figure 8: NDS feed tank valve positions

THE CORRESPONDING WASTE VALVE MUST ALSO BE CHANGED. REFER TO THE VALVE DIAGRAM BELOW FOR THE CORRECT POSITIONING OF THE VALVE HANDLE.

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

Figure 9: NDS waste valve position

2. CREW WILL BE INSTRUCTED BY **MCC** ON THE VALVE CONFIGURATION BEFORE THE ACTIVITY STARTS
3. THE VALVES ARE UNDER THE FEG FLOOR. THE FEG FLOOR HAS TO BE REMOVED TO ACCESS THEM

2.15 Configure the NDS feed tank valve position as required (example in fig. 8)

2.16 Configure the Waste valve position as required (example in fig. 9)

Figure 10: Nutrient Delivery System Display – Irrigation Equipment Control Configuration

2.17 Turn **ON** all high pressure aeroponic pumps fed from Tank 1(2) (Fig. 10):

In the Irrigation Equipment Control box

- Cmd L1** HP Pump to **Automatic**
- Cmd L2** HP Pump to **Automatic**
- Cmd L3** HP Pump to **Automatic**
- Cmd L4** HP Pump to **Automatic**
- Cmd R1** HP Pump to **Automatic**

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

- Cmd R2 HP Pump to **Automatic**
- Cmd R3 HP Pump to **Automatic**
- Cmd R4 HP Pump to **Automatic**

2.18 Irrigation pump timing (TBW – input missing)

3 FEG ATMOSPHERE PARAMETERS SETUP FOR PLANT CULTIVATION

NOTE

1. **TEMPERATURE, RELATIVE HUMIDITY AND CO2 CONTROL** IS DIVIDED INTO DAY AND NIGHT PERIODS. FOR CONSTANT PARAMETERS OPERATION, DAY CONTROL SHOULD BE SET TO ENABLED AND NIGHT CONTROL TO DISABLED. FOR DAY/NIGHT TEMPERATURE DIFFERENCES, BOTH ARE SET TO ENABLE WITH AT LEAST ONE DIFFERENT SETPOINT. SCHEDULE TIMES SHOULD NOT OVERLAP. AN ALARM WILL SOUND IF THIS IS THE CASE.
2. **TEMPERATURE SETUP.** FOR EACH PERIOD THERE IS A COOLING TARGET AND A HEATING TARGET. THE MINIMUM SEPARATION BETWEEN THE TWO VALUES SHOULD BE NO LESS THAN 1.0 C. IF CONTROL IS SET TOO TIGHT, HEATING AND COOLING CONTROL WILL OSCILLATE. FOR EXAMPLE, IF A DAY TIME TEMPERATURE OF 22.0 C IS DESIRED, THE HEATING TARGET SHOULD BE SET TO 21.5 C AND THE COOLING TARGET SET TO 22.5 C
3. **RELATIVE HUMIDITY SETUP.** FOR EACH PERIOD THERE IS A DEHUMIDIFY TARGET AND A HUMIDIFY TARGET. THE MINIMUM SEPARATION BETWEEN THE TWO VALUES SHOULD BE NO LESS THAN 5%. FOR EXAMPLE, IF A DAY TIME HUMIDITY OF 65% IS DESIRED, THE DEHUMID TARGET SHOULD BE SET TO 67.5% AND THE HUMIDIFY TARGET SET TO 62.5%.
4. **CO₂ SETUP.** CO₂ TARGET VALID PARAMETERS ARE FROM 0 TO 2000 PPM. TO ENABLE CO₂ CONTROL, THE CO₂ INJECTION VALVE AUTOMATIC CONTROL HAS TO BE ENABLED IN THE AMS DISPLAY

Figure 11: Atmosphere Management System Display – Navigation to SETPOINT SCHEDULE

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

CONTROL PERIOD:			Period 1	Period 2
Period Name	Day Period		Night Period	
Enable/Disable	Enabled		Enabled	
Period Status	Inactive		Active	
Start Time	0:00 Before Dawn (5:56)		0:00 After Dusk (19:02)	
End Time	2:00 Before Dusk (17:02)		2:00 Before Dawn (3:56)	
Time Status	Outside of Time Window		Within Time Window	
Active Days	Mon Tue Wed Thu Fri Sat Sun		Mon Tue Wed Thu Fri Sat Sun	
Day Status	End Time Only		Start Time Only	
SETPOINTS:			Ramp	Ramp
1 HEATING TARGET	17.78 °C	Okay	18.89 °C	Okay
2 COOLING TARGET	20.00 °C	Okay	21.11 °C	Okay
3 DEHUMID TARGET	80.0 %Rh	Okay	80.0 %Rh	Okay
4 HUMIDIFY TARGET	75.0 %Rh	Okay	75.0 %Rh	Okay
5 CO2 TARGET	300 ppm	Okay	300 ppm	Okay
6 AIR INLET TARGET	5.00 °C	Okay	5.00 °C	Okay
7 Setpoint #007	0	Okay	0	Okay
8 Setpoint #008	0	Okay	0	Okay

Fig. 12: SETPOINT SCHEDULE page.

- 3.1 In the **ATMOSPHERE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM** Display, open the **FUTURE EXPLORATION GREENHOUSE** Page and then click to the **SETPOINT SCHEDULE** tab (Fig. 11). The SETPOINT SCHEDULE page will open (Fig. 12)
- 3.2 In the SETPOINT SCHEDULE page input the **CONTROL PERIOD** parameters, in **both** the fields **Period 1** and **Period 2**, as required

Input Enable/Disable = as required

Input Start time = as required

Input End Time = as required

Input Active Days = as required

Input HEATING TARGET = as required

Input COOLING TARGET = as required

Input DEHUMID TARGET = as required

Input HUMIDIFY TARGET = as required

Input CO2 TARGET = as required

Input AIR INLET TARGET = as required

Input Setpoint #007 = 0

Input Setpoint #008 = 0

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

FEG; CONTROLLED EQUIPMENT					
	AMS; FEG; FANS CIRC 1	Manual Off	Off	0 %	
	AMS; FEG; FANS CIRC 2	Manual Off	Off	0 %	
	AMS; FEG; FANS CIRC 3	Manual Off	Off	0 %	
	AMS; FEG; FANS CIRC 4	Manual Off	Off	0 %	
	AMS; FEG; FANS AIR LOOP 1	Automatic	70.00%	70.00 %	Not Moving
	AMS; FEG; FANS AIR LOOP 2	Automatic	70.00%	70.00 %	Not Moving
	AMS; FEG; HEATER AIR LOOP	Automatic	0.00%	0.00 %	Not Moving
	AMS; FEG; UV LAMP AIR	Manual Off	Off	0 %	
	AMS; FEG; COND PUMP	Automatic	Off	0 %	
	AMS; FEG; UV LAMP COND WATER	User Override	0.00%	0.00 %	
	AMS; FEG; CO2 INJECTION VALVE	Automatic	Off	0 %	
	AMS; FEG; HUMIDIFIER (FEG)	Manual Off	Off	0 %	

Figure 13: FEG Controlled Equipment Box – Enable the automatic Control of the CO2 Injection Valve

3.3 In the FEG; CONTROLLED EQUIPMENT BOX

Cmd AMS; FEG; FANS CIRC 1 to Automatic
Cmd AMS; FEG; FANS CIRC 2 to Automatic
Cmd AMS; FEG; FANS CIRC 3 to Automatic
Cmd AMS; FEG; FANS CIRC 4 to Automatic
Cmd FANS AIR LOOP 1 to Automatic 70%
Cmd FANS AIR LOOP 2 to Automatic 70%
Cmd HEATER AIR LOOP to Automatic
Cmd UV LAMP AIR to Automatic
Cmd COND PUMP to Automatic
Cmd UV LAMP COND WATER to Automatic
Cmd AMS; FEG; CO2 INJECTION VALVE to Automatic
Cmd FEG HUMIDIFER: Manual Off

4 ILLUMINATION SYSTEM SETUP

NOTE

1. THE ILLUMINATION SYSTEM IS OPERATED BY ARGUS PROVIDED THAT IT IS CONFIGURED AND THAT THE AUTOMATIC MODE IS SELECTED. EACH LED LAMP UNIT CAN BE CONFIGURED INDEPENDENTLY IN TERMS OF LED INTENSITY, LIGHT COMPOSITION AND ILLUMINATION CYCLES DEFINITION
2. THE CONFIGURATION PARAMETERS OF THE LED LAMPS UNIT WILL BE PROVIDED BY MCC BEFORE THE OPERATIONS STARTS
3. THE FOLLOWING FIGURES REFERS TO THE LED LAMP UNIT NAMED "L1-2R". THE PROCEDURE STEPS REFERS TO A GENERIC LED LAMP UNIT

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth (EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

Fig. 14: LED Lighting System Display – Main Page

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

Fig. 15: LED Lighting System Display – LED Lamp Unit Configuration

- 4.1 Configure the LED Lamp Units as per MCC instructions (Fig. 15).

On the LED Lighting System Display

Click on the desired LED Lamp Unit. The LED Lamp Unit Window will open

In the LED Lamp Unit Window

For $i = 1$ to 16

Input Enable Step = as required

Input Step Start Time = as required

Input BLUE (Arg. Percent) = as required

Input RED (Arg. Percent) = as required

Input FAR RED (Arg. Percent) = as required

Input WHITE (Arg. Percent) = as required

Input Maximum Increase per hours = as required

Input Maximum Decrease per hours = as required

- 4.2 On the LED Lighting System Display

2.200 FEG Configuration for Plant Growth

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

Cmd LED Panel Unit to Automatic

4.3 Repeat Steps 4.1 and 4.2 for the other LED Lamp Units as required

5 CLOSEOUT

5.1 Stow items and tools

2.500 HD Cameras Configuration for Plant Monitoring

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

To configure the HD camera's system in terms of:

- network parameter's definition
- camera's parameters

DURATION

120 minutes

TOOLS

N/A

ITEMS

N/A

NOTE

- 1) PREREQUISITES TO START THIS ACTIVITY ARE:
 - THE CAMERA'S ARE INSTALLED IN THE MTF AND THE PHYSICAL CONNECTIONS HAVE BEEN DONE
 - THE EDEN ISS NETWORK IS CONFIGURED AND FULLY WORKING
 - THE HIKVISION SADP AND IVMS-4200 SW HAVE BEEN ALREADY INSTALLED ON THE TWO CAMERAS PC' IN THE MTF AND IN NMIII
- 2) THE CONFIGURATION CAN BE DONE ON THE PC CAMERA'S IN BOTH THE MTF AND NMIII

Cameras 1.
a PC

CAMERA ACTIVATION

NOTE

- 1) FOR CAMERA ACTIVATION IT IS **NOT** INTENDED THE PROVISION OF THE POWER, BUT RATHER THE CONFIGURATION OF THE NETWORK PARAMETERS AND THE LOAD OF THE CAMERAS TO THE IVMS-4200 SERVER SW. AS MATTER OF FACT THE PROVISION OF THE ELECTRICAL POWER TO THE CAMERAS IS DONE AS SOON AS THEY ARE CONNECTED TO AN ACTIVE SWITCH.
- 2) THE CONFIGURATION OF THE CAMERA NETWORK PARAMETERS IS DONE USING THE SADP SW

- 1.1 Run the SADP SW. Click on the SADP SW icon on the CameraPC and wait until the SADP main page opens (fig. 1)

2.500 HD Cameras Configuration for Plant Monitoring (EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Figure 1: SADP Main Page

Table 1: Cameras network parameters

Item	Position	IP Address	Server Port	Subnet Mask	Gateway	HTTP Port
Top View Cam	L1-2C	192.168.39.111	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L1-4C	192.168.39.112	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L2-1C	192.168.39.113	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L2-2C	192.168.39.114	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L2-3C	192.168.39.115	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L2-4C	192.168.39.116	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L3-1C	192.168.39.117	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L3-2C	192.168.39.118	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L3-3C	192.168.39.119	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L3-4C	192.168.39.120	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L4-1L	192.168.39.121	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L4-2L	192.168.39.122	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L4-3L	192.168.39.123	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L4-1R	192.168.39.125	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L4-2R	192.168.39.126	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80

2.500 HD Cameras Configuration for Plant Monitoring

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Top View Cam	L4-3R	192.168.39.127	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	L4-4C	192.168.39.128	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	R1-2C	192.168.39.129	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	R1-4C	192.168.39.130	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	R2-2C	192.168.39.131	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	R2-4C	192.168.39.132	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	R3-4C	192.168.39.133	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	R4-2C	192.168.39.134	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Top View Cam	R4-4C	192.168.39.135	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Side View Cam	L1-S	192.168.39.141	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Side View Cam	L2-S	192.168.39.142	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Side View Cam	L3-S	192.168.39.143	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Side View Cam	L4-S	192.168.39.144	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Side View Cam	R1-S	192.168.39.145	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Side View Cam	R2-S	192.168.39.146	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Side View Cam	R3-S	192.168.39.147	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Side View Cam	R4-S	192.168.39.148	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
External Cam.	EAST	192.168.39.171	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
External Cam.	WEST	192.168.39.172	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Observ. Cam.	MTF/CP	192.168.39.181	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Observ. Cam.	MTF/SS	192.168.39.182	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Observ. Cam.	MTF/SS	192.168.39.183	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80
Observ. Cam.	MTF/FEG	192.168.39.184	8000	255.255.255.0	192.168.39.254	80

- 1.2 **Verify** that all the camera's are listed in the main page
- 1.3 **Select** the device to be modified in the device list and the network parameters of the device will be displayed in the Modify Network Parameters panel on the right side
- 1.4 **Modify** the network camera parameters in the "Modify Network Parameters" field as per the table 1
- 1.5 **Enter** the password of the admin account of the device in the Password field and click to save the changes.

2.500 HD Cameras Configuration for Plant Monitoring (EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

1.6 Repeat for all the other cameras.

2 ADDING THE ONLINE CAMERAS TO THE iVMS CLIENT

2.1 **Run** the iVMS-4200 SW. Double click on the iVMS icon on the desktop and wait until the iVMS-4200 main page opens (fig. 2)

Figure 2: iVMS-4200 Main Page

2.500 HD Cameras Configuration for Plant Monitoring (EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Figure 3: Device Management Main Page

Figure 4: Cameras added to Client

2.2 In the Online Device Field Select the devices to be added from the list

2.3 Click **Add to Client** to open the device adding dialog box

2.4 **Input** the required information.

Nickname: Edit a name for the device as you want (it is recommended to have a name that is recalling the position or the function of the camera).

Address: Input the device's IP address. The IP address of the device is obtained automatically in this adding mode.

Port: Input the device port No. The default value is 8000.

User Name: Input the device user name. By default, the user name is *admin*.

Password: Input the device password.

2.5 **Record** the above defined parameters in the log

2.6 **Repeat** for all the other cameras.

3 CREATING GROUPS OF CAMERAS

NOTE

AN IMPORTANT FEATURES OF THE DEVICE MANAGEMENT IS THE POSSIBILITY TO CREATES GROUPS OF CAMERAS. THAT IS VERY IMPORTANT FOR THE EDEN ISS PROJECT WERE WE HAVE A LOT OF CAMERA'S THAT CAN BE ORGANISED BY THEIR

2.500 HD Cameras Configuration for Plant Monitoring (EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

POSITION (RIGHT OR LEFT SIDE OF THE FEG CORRIDOR FOR EXAMPLE), OR BY THEIR DESTINATION (PLANT HEALTH MONITORING OR AMBIENT MONITORING).

Figure 5: Creating a group

Figure 6: Camera importing to group

3.1 Click **“Group”** in the Device Management page to open the group page

2.500 HD Cameras Configuration for Plant Monitoring

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

- 3.2 **Click “Add Group”** to create a new group
- 3.3 **Insert the “Group Name”**, click OK
- 3.4 **Verify** that the group has been created in the Resource Field
- 3.5 **Click “Import”** on the tool bar of the Device Management to open the import page
- 3.6 **Select** the Image (it is possible to click on the image)
- 3.7 **Click** Import
- 3.8 Repeat for the other groups and camera’s as desired

4 CAMERA CONFIGURATION

NOTE

TWO ACTIONS ARE NECESSARY BEFORE STARTING WITH THE IMAGES/VIDEO ACQUISITION:

- THE CONFIGURATION OF THE CAMERA’S PARAMETERS (LIKE RESOLUTION, FRAME RATE, ETC)
- THE CONFIGURATION OF THE VIDEO PARAMETERS (LIKE THE BRIGHTNESS, THE CONTRAST, ETC)
- THE CONFIGURATION OF THE DISPLAYS PARAMETERS (LIKE CAMERA NAME, TIME FORMAT, ETC.)

2.500 HD Cameras Configuration for Plant Monitoring (EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Figure 7: Remote Configuration page- Video and Audio Configuration

Figure 8: Remote Configuration page- Image Configuration

Figure 9: Remote Configuration page- Video Display Configuration

- 4.1 Select the camera to be configured in the Device Management Main page
- 4.2 Click **“Remote Configuration”** in the Device Management page. The Remote Configuration page will be opened (Fig. 7)

2.500 HD Cameras Configuration for Plant Monitoring

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Click Image to open popup menu

- 4.4 **Select “Video & Audio”** in the Popup Menu for Camera parameters configuration. The “Configuring the Image Quality, Resolution and other parameters of the camera” window will open (Fig.7).

Input the desired value

- 4.5 **Select the “Image Setting”** in the popup Menu to define the video parameters of the cameras. The “Configuring the video Parameters of the camera” window will open (Fig. 8).

Input the desired value

- 4.6 **Select the “Video Display”** in the Popup menu to define how the video/images will be displayed and saved. The “Configuring the Display Parameters, including the OSD, privacy mask, etc” will open (Fig. 9).

Input the desired value

5 LIVE VIEW

NOTE

THE LIVE VIEW WILL ALLOW THE USER TO VERIFY IF THE SYSTEM IS SENDING THE IMAGES ON THE CAMERA PC AS VERIFICATION OF THE ABOVE STEPS

Figure 10: Main View Window with four screen

2.500 HD Cameras Configuration for Plant Monitoring

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

- 5.1 On the toolbar, **Select “Main View”**. The main View Window will open (Fig. 10) with four screen as default
- 5.2 **Open** the Standard Window Division and select 32 (See fig. 10). 32 screens will be associated to the Main View Window
- 5.3 In the camera field **Verify** that each camera is online and that all the cameras are divided as per defined groups.
- 5.4 Associate each camera to a window. Select the window, by simply clicking on it, and then the camera with a double click. A small green arrow close to the camera name indicate that the camera is sending a video to the window.
- 5.5 On the screen **Verify** that the camera’s name is correct

2.510 EDEN ISS Datalog and Images Automatic Transfer to MCC

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Configure the C&DH system in order to automatically transfer the datalog and the images generated during the EDEN ISS operations to the NMIII Station and to the EDEN ISS MCC @DLR Bremen.

DURATION

120 minutes (TBC)

TOOLS

N/A

ITEMS

N/A

NOTE

1. SEVERAL DATA ARE GENERATED DURING THE EDEN ISS OPERATIONS:

- FEG/MTF DATA LOG
- MTF/FEG HD IMAGES
- MULTIWAVE IMAGES
- ISPR DATA LOG
- ISPR IMAGES

THESE DATA HAVE TO BE TRANSFERRED FROM THE MTF TO THE NMIII CONSOLES AND TO THE EDEN ISS MCC@DLR BREMEN, AND THEN DISTRIBUTED TO THE UHB'S (SUPPORT CENTERS) FOR OFFLINE ANALYSIS. THE TRANSFER IS AUTOMATICALLY MANAGED BY AD-HOC DEVELOPED SW APPLICATIONS. THESE APPLICATIONS, WITH THE EXCEPTION OF THE HD IMAGES, ARE NOT RESPONSIBLE FOR THE ACQUISITION AND STORAGE OF THE DATA THAT ARE MANAGED BY THE OTHER SYSTEMS IMPLEMENTED AS PART OF THE C&DH AS FOLLOW:

- ARGUS FOR THE MTF/FEG
- GOPRO SW FOR THE MULTIWAVE IMAGES
- LABVIEW FOR THE ISPR DATA/IMAGES

2. THESE PROCEDURE MANAGES THE ONLY NOMINAL ACTIVITIES. FOR FURTHER INSTRUCTIONS AND/OR VERIFICATION REFER TO THE DOCUMENT "INPUT TO D3.11 – PHM DESIGN REPORT: HD CAMERA SYSTEM DESIGN REPORT AND USER GUIDE"

1 PREREQUISITES CHECK

1.1 Verify that the following files/scripts have been copied on the **Camera-PC (MTF)** - C:\File_AcquisitionTransfer\TPZ_SW:

- *edeniss_mkdir.bat*
- *hikvision.py*
- *camera_snapshot_robot.py*
- *camera_ftp_robot_DLR.py*

2.510 EDEN ISS Datalog and Images Automatic Transfer to MCC (EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

- *edeniss_camera_scheduler_DLR.bat*
- *camera_ftp_robot_NMIII.py*
- *edeniss_camera_scheduler_NMIII.bat*

MTF 1.2 Verify that the following scripts have been copied on the the **Argus-PC (MTF)**
C:\File_AcquisitionTransfer\TPZ_SW:

- *edeniss_mkdir.bat*
- *hikvision.py*
- *data_ftp_robot_DLR.py*
- *edeniss_data_scheduler_DLR.bat*
- *data_ftp_robot_NMIII.py*
- *edeniss_data_scheduler_NMIII.bat*

1.3 Verify that the following files/scripts have been copied to the **ISPR-PC (MTF)** -
C:\File_AcquisitionTransfer\TPZ_SW:

- *edeniss_mkdir.bat*
- *hikvision.py*
- *isprcamera_ftp_robot_DLR.py*
- *edeniss_isprcamera_scheduler_DLR.bat*
- *isprcamera_ftp_robot_NMIII.py*
- *edeniss_isprcamera_scheduler_NMIII.bat*
- *isprdata_ftp_robot_DLR.py*
- *edeniss_isprdata_scheduler_DLR.bat*
- *isprdata_ftp_robot_NMIII.py*
- *edeniss_isprdata_scheduler_NMIII.bat*

NMIII 1.4 Verify that the following file has been installed on the **Camera-PC (NM-III)** and
Argus-PC (NM-III) - C:\File_AcquisitionTransfer\TPZ_SW:

- *edeniss_remote_mkdir.bat*
- **FTP Server** (for example **filezilla server**)

Remark: The FTP user account should be ftp_edeniss_dlr, the password "12345", the home directory should be 'D:/FTP_EDEN-ISS/'.

MCC 1.5 Verify that the following file has been installed on the **DLR OPS PC** -
C:\File_AcquisitionTransfer\TPZ_SW:

- *edeniss_remote_mkdir.bat*
- **FTP Server** (for example **filezilla server**)

Remark: The FTP user account should be ftp_edeniss_dlr, the password "12345", the home directory should be 'D:/FTP_EDEN-ISS/'.

1.6 If the above steps are not accomplished, copy all the listed applications as described above. Call **MCC** in case the SW Applications are not available.

2 DIRECTORIES CREATION FOR DATA LOG/IMAGES STORAGE ON THE MTF PC'S

2.510 EDEN ISS Datalog and Images Automatic Transfer to MCC (EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

MTF 2.1 Creating Folder Structure on the MTF Camera-PC for Images Storage

NOTE

1. THE OBJECTIVE OF THIS STEP IS THE CREATION OF THE DIRECTORIES FOR THE STORAGE OF THE FOLLOWING IMAGES TIPOLOGY:
 - HDTOPVIEW
 - HDSIDEVIEW
 - UFIMAGERS (MULTIWAVE) IMAGES
2. IF THE FOLDER STRUCTURE ALREADY EXISTS, THE COMMANDS FOR DIRECTORIES CREATION ARE NOT EXECUTED AND A MESSAGE WILL APPEAR IN THE COMMAND WINDOW STATING THAT THE FOLDERS ALREADY EXIST.

2.1.1 On **Camera-PC (MTF)** Launch the *edeniss_mkdir.bat* batch file in a *Windows CMD command line*

enter [CAM]

2.1.2 **Verify** the following folders have been created:

D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\CropImages\HDTOPVIEW\<camera position1>

Where *<camera position1>* is:

- L1-2C, L1-4C
- L2-1C, L2-2C, L2-3C, L2-4C
- L3-1C, L3-2C, L3-3C, L3-4C
- L4-1L, L4-2L, L4-3L
- L4-1R, L4-2R, L4-3R, L4-4C
- R1-2C, R1-4C
- R2-2C, R2-4C
- R3-4C
- R4-2C, R4-4C

D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\CropImages\HDSIDEVIEW\<camera position2>

Where *<camera position2>* is:

- L12-1S, L12-3S, L34-1S, L34-3S
- R12-1S, R12-3S, R34-1S, R34-3S

- *D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\CropImages\UFIMAGERS\<ufimager camera position>*

Where *<ufimager camera position>* is:

- UFIImager1, UFIImager2, UFIImager3, UFIImager4

2.2 Creating Folder Structure on the Argus PC (MTF) for Argus Data Logs Storage

2.510 EDEN ISS Datalog and Images Automatic Transfer to MCC

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

- 2.2.1** On **Argus-PC (MTF)** Launch the **edeniss_mkdir.bat** batch file in a *Windows CMD command line*

enter [CSVDATA]

- 2.2.2** **Verify** the following folders have been created:

D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\DataFiles

- 2.3** **Creating Folder Structure on the ISPR PC (MTF) for ISPR Data Logs and Images Storage**

- 2.3.1** On **ISPR-PC (MTF)** Launch the **edeniss_mkdir.bat** batch file in a *Windows CMD command line*

enter [ISPRFILES]

- 2.3.2** **Verify** the following folders have been created:

D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\CropImages\<ispr camera position>

Where *<ispr camera position>* is:

- GCScam, GCSUFlcam, GCTcam

D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\DataFiles\<ispr datafile dir>

Where *<ispr datafile dir>* is:

- LOG, VALUES, ERROR

NMIII/
MCC

- 3** **CONFIGURING THE FTP SERVER ON DLR OPS-PC, CAMERA-PC (NM-III) AND ARGUS-PC (NM-III)**

NOTE

THE OBJECTIVE OF THIS STEP IS THE CONFIGURATION OF THE FTP SERVER (FILEZILLA) FOR DATALOG AND IMAGES TRANSFER FROM THE MTF TO NMIII TO THE MCC. IT IS DESCRIBED FOR ONE GENERIC PC.

- 3.1** On the **NMIII Camera-PC, NMIII Argus-PC and on the DLR OPS_PC**

- Open Filezilla Server Interface
- In the Menu Bar/Edit → Users
- In the Users Page/Users → Click on Add Button
- In the Add User Account window → type the name of the ftp user Account: **ftp_edeniss_dlr**
- In the account settings → Click on Password and then enter: **12345** (if another is desired the scheduler batch file has to be updated)
- In Page Select Shared Folders → Click Add and then select '**D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS**' → Click OK

2.510 EDEN ISS Datalog and Images Automatic Transfer to MCC

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

- Select the **privileges** (in Files select Read, Write, Delete, Append; in Directories select Create, Delete, List, Subdirs) → Click on **set as home dir** → Click OK

3.2 In FileZilla Server Interface **verify** the operation has succeeded

NMIII/ 4 DIRECTORIES CREATION FOR DATA LOG/IMAGES STORAGE ON THE NMIII/MCC MCC PC'S

NOTE

1. THE OBJECTIVE OF THIS STEP IS THE CREATION OF THE DIRECTORIES ON THE COMPUTERS AT THE NMIII AND AT THE MCC WHERE THE IMAGES/DATA WILL BE AUTOMATICALLY TRANSFERRED FROM THE MTF.
2. ONLY TWO PC'S ARE AVAILABLE AT NMIII
 - NMIII CAMERA-PC (FOR ARGUS/ISPR DATALOG STORAGE)
 - NMIII ARGUS PC (FOR MTF/FEG AND ISPR IMAGES STORAGE)
3. ONLY ONE PC IS AVAILABLE AT MCC. ALL THE DATA/IMAGES COMING FROM THE MTF WILL BE STORED ON IT.
4. IF THE FOLDER STRUCTURE ALREADY EXISTS, THE COMMANDS FOR DIRECTORIES CREATION ARE NOT EXECUTED AND A MESSAGE WILL APPEAR IN THE COMMAND WINDOW STATING THAT THE FOLDERS ALREADY EXIST

4.1 Creating Folder Structure on the NMIII Camera-PC and on the DLR OPS-PC for Images Storage

4.1.1 On the Camera-PC (NM-III) and on the DLR OPS-PC **Launch** the **edeniss_remote_mkdir.bat** batch file in a *Windows CMD command line*

enter [CAM]

4.1.2 **Verify** the following folders have been created:

- *D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\CropImages\HDTOPVIEW\<camera position1>*

Where *<camera position1>* is:

- L1-2C, L1-4C
- L2-1C, L2-2C, L2-3C, L2-4C
- L3-1C, L3-2C, L3-3C, L3-4C
- L4-1L, L4-2L, L4-3L
- L4-1R, L4-2R, L4-3R, L4-4C
- R1-2C, R1-4C
- R2-2C, R2-4C
- R3-4C
- R4-2C, R4-4C

- *D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\CropImages\HDSIDEVIEW\<camera position2>*

Where *<camera position2>* is:

- L12-1S, L12-3S, L34-1S, L34-3S

2.510 EDEN ISS Datalog and Images Automatic Transfer to MCC (EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

- R12-1S, R12-3S, R34-1S, R34-3S

- *D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\CropImages\UFIMAGERS\<ufimager camera position>*

Where *<ufimager camera position>* is:

- UFIImager1, UFIImager2, UFIImager3, UFIImager4

- *D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\CropImages\ISPR\<ispr camera position>*

Where *<ispr camera position>* is:

- GCScam, GCSUFIcam, GCTcam

4.2 Creating Folder Structure on the NMIII Argus-PC and on the DLR OPS-PC for Data Log Storage

4.2.1 On the Argus-PC (NM-III) and on the DLR OPS-PC **Launch** the *edeniss_remote_mkdir.bat* batch file in a *Windows CMD command line*
enter *[DATA]*

4.2.2 **Verify** the following folders have been created, for Argus and ISPR data files:

- *D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\DataFiles\Argus*
- *D:\FTP_EDEN-ISS\DataFiles\ISPR\<ispr datafile dir>*

Where *<ispr datafile dir>* is:

- LOG, VALUES, ERROR

5 HD IMAGES AUTOMATIC ACQUISITION SCHEDULING

NOTE

EVEN IF THE HD CAMERA'S INSTALLED IN THE MTF FOR BOTH AMBIENT AND PLANT MONITORING CAN BE MANAGED BY THE SW FACTORY, IT IS PREFERRED TO USE AN AD-HOC DEVELOPED SW APPLICATION FOR THE AUTOMATIC ACQUISITION OF PLANT IMAGES. THIS APPLICATION ACQUIRES ONE PICTURE PER CAMERA PER DAY.

2.510 EDEN ISS Datalog and Images Automatic Transfer to MCC (EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)


```
C:\windows\system32\cmd.exe
EDEN ISS batch file, edeniss_scheduler.bat, to schedule tasks for images acquisition or for images forwarding
[Al]cquisition allows you to schedule images acquisition at hour:minute (hh:mm) every day.
The scheduled task name is "snapshot_taskname"

[Fl]orwarding allows you to schedule images forwarding at hour:minute (hh:mm) every day.
The scheduled task name is "ftp_taskname"

Do yo want to schedule images [Al]cquisition or images [Fl]orwarding [A,F]?
```

Fig. 1: Cmd Prompt


```
C:\windows\system32\cmd.exe
EDEN ISS batch file, edeniss_scheduler.bat, to schedule tasks for images acquisition or for images forwarding
[Al]cquisition allows you to schedule images acquisition at hour:minute (hh:mm) every day.
The scheduled task name is "snapshot_taskname"

[Fl]orwarding allows you to schedule images forwarding at hour:minute (hh:mm) every day.
The scheduled task name is "ftp_taskname"

Do yo want to schedule images [Al]cquisition or images [Fl]orwarding [A,F]?A
Input the Images Acquisition Time
Enter hour [0-23]: 12
hour = 12
Enter minute [0-59]: 25
hour = 25
Image Automatic Acquisition Task ("snapshot_taskname") has been created. The images will be acquire
SCHTASKS /create /SC DAILY /ST 12:25 /TN snapshot_taskname /TR ""C:\Program Files (x86)\Python35-32
ISS\IPZ_SW\camera_snapshot_robot.py"
OPERAZIONE RIUSCITA: l'attività pianificata "snapshot_taskname" è stata creata.
Do yo really want to quit [S,N]?
```

Fig. 2: Confirmation Message

5.1 On **Camera-PC (MTF)**, In a *Windows CMD command line*,

Launch edeniss_camera_scheduler_DLR.bat batch file

Verify the Cmd prompt appears on the screen as per Fig. 1

To schedule the image acquisition **Input** in sequence:

- A
- Hour (in the format 0-23)
- Minutes (in the format 0-59)

Verify that the snapshot_taskname has been created (a confirmation message will appear)

Verify the images have been acquired and saved on the MTF camera PC

6 HD AND MULTIWAVE FEG PLANT IMAGES AUTOMATIC TRANSFER

NOTE

2.510 EDEN ISS Datalog and Images Automatic Transfer to MCC (EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

1. THIS STEP REFERS TO THE AUTOMATIC TRANSFER FROM THE MTF TO NMIII AND TO THE MCC OF ALL THE PLANTS IMAGES GENERATED WITHIN THE FEG:
 - HD IMAGES
 - MULTIWAVE IMAGES
2. TRANSFER SHALL OCCUR AFTER THE IMAGE ACQUISITION HAS BEEN COMPLETED

6.1 Automatic Transfer of the Plant Images to the MCC (DLR OPS –PC)

6.1.1 On the **Camera-PC (MTF)**, In a *Windows CMD command line*,

If the cmd prompt is still active **enter** N, otherwise **launch** edeniss_camera_scheduler_DLR.bat

6.1.2 **Verify** the Cmd prompt appears on the screen as per Fig. 1

6.1.3 **Input** in sequence:

- B
- Hour (in the format 0-23)
- Minutes (in the format 0-59)

6.1.4 **Verify** that the ftp_taskname has been created.

A confirmation message will appear saying that the *ftp_taskname_camera_DLR has been created*

6.1.5 **@DLR**, Verify that the images have been transferred on the DLR OPS PC (path as per step 4.1.2)

6.2 Automatic Transfer of the Plant Images to NMIII Camera PC

On the **Camera-PC (MTF)**, In a *Windows CMD command line*,

launch edeniss_camera_scheduler_NMIII.bat batch file

Input in sequence

- Hour (in the format 0-23)
- Minutes (in the format 0-59)

Verify that the ftp_taskname has been created.

A confirmation message will appear saying that the *ftp_taskname_camera_NMIII has been created*

@NMIII, Verify that the images have been transferred on the NMIII Camera PC (path as per step 4.1.2)

2.510 EDEN ISS Datalog and Images Automatic Transfer to MCC (EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

7 SCHEDULING ARGUS DATA TRANSFER FROM MTF TO NMIII AND TO DLR

NOTE

ARGUS GENERATES DATA LOG WITH A PREDEFINED TIMING. THESE DATA HAVE TO BE DAILY AND AUTOMATICALLY TRANSFERRED TO THE NMIII AND THE MCC.

7.1 Scheduling Argus Datalog Transfer to DLR

7.1.1 On **Argus-PC (MTF)**, IN THE *Windows CMD command line*

Launch edeniss_data_scheduler_DLR.bat batch file

7.1.2 **Input** in sequence:

- Hour (in the format 0-23)
- Minutes (in the format 0-59)

7.1.3 **Verify** that the ftp_taskname has been created.

A confirmation message will appear saying that the *ftp_taskname_data_DLR has been created*

7.1.4 **@DLR**, Verify that the data have been transferred on the DLR OPS PC
Path as per step 4.2.2

7.2 Scheduling Argus Datalog Transfer to NMIII

On **Argus-PC (MTF)**, in the *Windows CMD command line*

Launch edeniss_data_scheduler_NMIII.bat batch file

Input in sequence:

- Hour (in the format 0-23)
- Minutes (in the format 0-59)

Verify that the ftp_taskname has been created.

A confirmation message will appear saying that the *ftp_taskname_data_DLR has been created*

@NMIII, Verify that the data have been transferred on the NMIII Argus PC
Path as per step 4.2.2

8 Scheduling the ISPR Datalogs and Images Automatic Transfer

NOTE

THE ISPR GENERATES DATALOGS AND IMAGES WITH A PREDEFINED TIMING. THESE DATA HAVE TO BE DAILY AND AUTOMATICALLY TRANSFERRED TO NMIII AND THE MCC.

2.510 EDEN ISS Datalog and Images Automatic Transfer to MCC (EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

8.1 Scheduling ISPR Datalog Transfer to DLR

8.1.1 On the **ISPR PC (MTF)**, in a *Windows CMD command line*,

launch edeniss_isprdata_scheduler_DLR.bat batch file

8.1.2 **Input** in sequence:

- Hour (in the format 0-23)
- Minutes (in the format 0-59)

8.1.3 **Verify** that the ftp_taskname has been created.

A confirmation message will appear saying that the *ftp_taskname_isprdata_DLR has been created*

8.1.4 **@DLR**, Verify that the data have been transferred on the DLR OPS PC
Path as per step 4.2.2

8.2 Scheduling ISPR Datalog Transfer to NMIII

8.2.1 On the **ISPR PC (MTF)**, in a *Windows CMD command line*,

launch edeniss_isprdata_scheduler_NMIII.bat batch file

8.2.2 **Input** in sequence:

- Hour (in the format 0-23)
- Minutes (in the format 0-59)

8.2.3 **Verify** that the ftp_taskname has been created.

A confirmation message will appear saying that the *ftp_taskname_isprdata_NMIII has been created*

8.2.4 **@NMIII**, Verify that the data have been transferred on the NMIII Argus PC
Path as per step 4.2.2

8.3 Scheduling ISPR Images Transfer to DLR

On the **ISPR PC (MTF)**, in a *Windows CMD command line*,

launch edeniss_isprcamera_scheduler_DLR.bat batch file

Input in sequence:

- Hour (in the format 0-23)
- Minutes (in the format 0-59)

2.510 EDEN ISS Datalog and Images Automatic Transfer to MCC

(EDEN ISS/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE)

Verify that the ftp_taskname has been created.

A confirmation message will appear saying that the *ftp_taskname_isprcamera_DLR* has been created

@DLR, Verify that the images have been transferred on the DLR OPS PC (path as per step 4.1.2)

8.4 Scheduling ISPR Images Transfer to NMIII

On the **ISPR PC (MTF)**, in a *Windows CMD command line*,

launch edeniss_isprcamera_scheduler_NMIII.bat batch file

Input in sequence:

- Hour (in the format 0-23)
- Minutes (in the format 0-59)

Verify that the ftp_taskname has been created.

A confirmation message will appear saying that the *ftp_taskname_isprcamera_NMIII* has been created

@NMIII, Verify that the images have been transferred on the NMIII Camera PC (path as per step 4.1.2)

3.210 Growth Media Preparation for Safety Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Preparation of media for the growth, isolation and detection of microorganisms potentially present in fruit and vegetables cultivated in the FEG

DURATION

30 minutes + (time needed for solution solidification)

TOOLS

Pipets
Pipetter
Adjustable Volume Pipetter
Pipetter Tips
Microbial Plates
Scale
Pressure Cooker
Heating stirring plate
Bunsen Burner

ITEMS

Glass Jar with cover lid
Autoclave tape
Deionized and Sterile Water (TBD volume)
Growth Media Powder

NOTE

1. THE SAFETY ANALYSIS AIMS AT THE VERIFICATION OF THE ABSENCE OF DANGEROUS MICROORGANISMS (AS LISTED BELOW) ON THE PLANTS CULTIVATED TO BE EATEN BY THE NMIII CREW:
 - COMMON PATHOGENS
 - TOTAL MICROBIAL COUNT
 - YEASTS AND MOULDS
 - TOTAL COLIFORM
 - *ESCHERICHIA COLI*
 - *SALMONELLE SPP.*
 - *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS*
 - *BACILLUS CEREUS*
 - *EMERGING PATHOGENS*
 - *ENTEROBACTER SAKAZAKII*
 - *LISTERIA INNOCUA*
 - *CLOSTRIDIUM SPP*THOSE ANALYSES REQUIRES, AMONG THE OTHERS, THE AVAILABILITY OF MEDIA FOR THE GROWTH, ISOLATION AND DETECTION OF MICROORGANISMS POTENTIALLY PRESENT IN FRUIT AND VEGETABLES CULTIVATED IN THE FEG. THESE MEDIA CAN BE PROVIDED READY TO USE, OR ALTERNATIVELY CAN BE PREPARED STARTING FROM DRIED POWDER. THIS PROCEDURE DESCRIBE THIS LAST CASE.
2. THE GROWTH MEDIA PREPARATION REQUIRES SEVERAL HOURS TO HAVE THE PLATES READY TO USE. FOR THAT REASON IT CAN BE DONE THE DAY BEFORE THE PREPARATION OF THE SAMPLES

3.210 Growth Media Preparation for Safety Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

NMIII 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

NOTE

1. CREW SHALL BE INSTRUCTED ON THE MEDIA TO BE PREPARED BY MCC. IN ANY CASE THEY WILL BE SELECTED BETWEEN THOSE LISTED BELOW:
 - HI CHROME EC0157: H7 SELECTIVE AGAR BASE
 - HI CHROME COLIFORM AGAR
 - HI CHROME RAJHANS MEDIUM, MODIFIED
 - VIOLET RED BILE AGAR
 - NUTRIENT BROTH N.2
 - HI CHROME BACILLUS AGAR
 - LISTERIA SELECTIVE AGAR
 - BACTERIOLOGICAL AGAR
 - TRYPTONE YEAST EXTRACT AGAR
 - YEAST EXTRACT
 - SLANETZ BARTLEY MEDIUM
 - LAB LEMCO AGAR
2. TO NOT CONTAMINATE THE SAMPLES, CREW IS REQUESTED TO CAREFULLY WASH THE HANDS BEFORE STARTING THE OPERATIONS AND WEAR LATEX GLOVES

- 1.1 Prepare and/or collect the required tools and items
- 1.2 Call **MCC** to be instructed on the media to be prepared
- 1.3 Carefully wash the hands
- 1.4 Wear the gloves

2 CULTURE MEDIA PREPARATION

Figure 1: Powder preparation

3.210 Growth Media Preparation for Safety Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2.1 Take the selected growth media (the weight is depending on the number of sample to be prepared) and put it in a transparent glass jar. Add Agar in proportion 1.2 – 1.6%. Then add distilled water as necessary (Fig. 1)

Figure 2: Heating/Stirring Plate

- 2.2 Put the jar on the heating/stirring plate and activate the stirrer for TBD minutes (Alternatively a spoon can be used) (Fig. 2)

Figure 3: Labelling with autoclave tape

- 2.3 Close the Jar with its lid cover and put on the lid the autoclave tape. Write on the Autoclave tape the type of culture media under preparation. (Fig. 3)

3.210 Growth Media Preparation for Safety Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 4: Pressure Cooker

- 2.4 Put the jar in the pressure cooker and close the cooker lid. Be sure that some water is in the cooker. Put the cooker on the heating/stirring plate and activate the heater at 270 degC for 30 minutes

Figure 5: Solution Ready to use

- 2.5 The solution is ready for use. Remove the autoclave tape from the cover to the jar side or to add a new label.
- 2.6 Repeat for the other growth media as required

3 PLATES PREPARATION

NOTE

1. THREE PLATES HAVE TO BE PREPARED FOR EACH MICROORGANISM CULTURE, TO ENSURE THE RELIABILITY OF THE MEASUREMENT
2. THE PLATES PREPARATION HAS TO BE DONE CLOSE TO THE BUNSEN BURNER FLAME TO PREVENT CONTAMINATION (THE PICTURES IN THE FOLLOWING SHOW THE PLATES DONE UNDER A LAMINAR FLOW HOOD THAT IS NOT AVAILABLE IN THE NMIII LAB)

3.210 Growth Media Preparation for Safety Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure6: Plates labelling

- 3.1 Label the plates. Do that on the on the bottom of the plates and not on the cover to avoid mistakes when the covers are removed (could be reinstalled on the wrong plate)

Figure7: Preparation of the pipetter

- 3.2 Open the pipette package and engage the pipette with the pipetter. Pay attention to not touch the pipette with your hand.

Figure 8: Sucking the culture media

3.210 Growth Media Preparation for Safety Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 3.3 Suck 20 ml of solution from the jar

Figure 9: Injection of the solution in the plate

- 3.4 Inject the solution in the plate (fig. 9)
- 3.5 Repeat for the other two plates
- 3.6 Repeat for the other growth media if any

Figure 10: Solution Solidification

- 3.7 Leaving the cover open, wait TBD time until the solution solidifies
- 3.8 Close the plates. They are ready to be used (Perform procedure 3.211 Sample Preparation for Safety Analysis, All steps).

3.211 Sample Preparation for Safety Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Preparation of samples for the growth, isolation and detection of microorganisms potentially present in fruit and vegetables cultivated in the FEG

DURATION

TOOLS

Pipets
Pipetter
Adjustable Volume Pipetter
Pipetter Tips
Microbial Plates (ready to use)
Scale
Bunsen Burner
Microbiological Incubator

ITEMS

Spatulas
Falcon Conical Tubes (50 ml)
Falcon Conical Tubes (15 ml)
Filter Bags
Deionized and Sterile Water (TBD volume)

NOTE

THE SAFETY ANALYSIS AIMS AT THE VERIFICATION OF THE ABSENCE OF DANGEROUS MICROORGANISMS (AS LISTED BELOW) ON THE PLANTS CULTIVATED TO BE EATEN BY THE NMIII CREW:

- COMMON PATHOGENS
- TOTAL MICROBIAL COUNT
- YEASTS AND MOULDS
- TOTAL COLIFORM
- *ESCHERICHIA COLI*
- *SALMONELLE SPP.*
- *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS*
- *BACILLUS CEREUS*
- *EMERGING PATHOGENS*
- *ENTEROBACTER SAKAZAKII*
- *LISTERIA INNOCUA*
- *CLOSTRIDIUM SPP*

THOSE ANALYSES REQUIRES, AMONG THE OTHERS, THE AVAILABILITY OF MEDIA FOR THE GROWTH, ISOLATION AND DETECTION OF MICROORGANISMS POTENTIALLY PRESENT IN FRUIT AND VEGETABLES CULTIVATED IN THE FEG. AT THIS STAGE THESE MEDIA ARE PROVIDED READY TO USE.

3.211 Sample Preparation for Safety Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

NMIII 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

- 1.1 Call **MCC** to be instructed on the samples to be prepared (growth media to be used and plants to be tested)
- 1.2 Prepare and/or collect the required tools and items
- 1.3 Carefully wash the hands
- 1.4 Don the gloves

2 SAMPLE PREPARATION

NOTE

THE SEQUENCE IS SHOWN FOR LEAFY GREENS. NEVERTHELESS THE SAME SEQUENCE APPLIES TO THE FRUIT AND RADISH PLANTS.

Figure 1: Weigh the sample

- 2.1 Prepare, weigh the selected vegetable (from 10 to 50 g, depending on the vegetable) and wash it with abundant fresh water

Figure2: solution of water and hypochlorite (2%)

3.211 Sample Preparation for Safety Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2.2 Immerse the vegetable in a solution of water and hypochlorite (2%) for 15 minutes. Then wash with fresh water until the hypochlorite is completely removed
- 2.3 Immerse the vegetable in a solution of water and sodium bicarbonate (50g/l) for 15 minutes. Then wash with fresh water

Figure 3: Mortar

- 2.4 Put the vegetable in a mortar and crush it by means of the pestle until it is reduced in a fine paste. Then add distilled water or physiological solution and stir the solution

Figure 4: Filter Bags

- 2.5 Put the solution in a filter bag

3.211 Sample Preparation for Safety Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 5: Preparing the Falcon Tubes

- 2.6 Prepare and label an Eppendorf Conical Tube (50 ml)

Figure 6: Pipetter Preparation

- 2.7 Prepare the pipetter. Open the pipette package and with the pipetter engage the pipette.

Figure 7: Solution transfer to the Eppendorf Tube

3.211 Sample Preparation for Safety Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2.8 Using the pipetter, transfer the liquid part form the filter bag to the Eppendorf conical tube

Figure 8: Engaging a pipetter tips

- 2.9 Engage the Pipetter Tips with the Adjustable Volume Pipetter and the Pipetter Tips

Figure 9: Plate preparation

- 2.10 Using the adjustable volume pipetter, take 100 microliters of the solution from the Eppendorf conical tube and inject it in the plate. Repeat for other two plates.

3.211 Sample Preparation for Safety Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 10: Solution distribution on the growth media

- 2.11 Using the spatulas, distribute gently the solution in the plates. Proceed until all the liquid part has been absorbed by the culture media. Repeat for the other two plates.

Figure 11: Incubator

- 2.12 Put the plates in the incubator for 24 hours (Fig. 11)
- 2.13 Repeat step 2 for other plants and/or growth media as necessary.

3 CLOSEOUT

- 3.1 Take off the gloves
- 3.2 Waste the consumable items
- 3.3 Stow the tools and the unused items
- 3.4 Log the activity in the log Journal

3.212 Safety Analysis Using the Micro Biological Survey Method

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE/HC)

OBJECTIVE

Perform the Safety analysis using the rapid Micro Biological Survey (MBS) Method

DURATION

Sample preparation (30 minutes)

Results (sample dependent 3 to 67 hours))

TOOLS

Sterile tweezers

ITEMS

MBS Kit (containing the reaction vial and a vial of distilled water)

Protective Glass

Nitrile Gloves

Protective Respirator Mask

NOTE

1. THE MICRO BIOLOGICAL SURVEY (MBS) METHOD IS AN INNOVATIVE RAPID COLORIMETRIC SYSTEM TO PERFORM MICROBIOLOGICAL TESTS ON FOOD, WATER AND SURFACES. THE METHOD OF ANALYSIS IS BASED ON THE OBSERVATION OF THE CHANGE OF COLOR IN THE SUSPENSION FORMED IN THE ANALYSIS VIAL USED WHEN THE TEST SAMPLE IS ADDED: THE SUSPENSION CHANGES COLOR IF THERE ARE MICROORGANISMS, THE GREATER THE AMOUNT OF MICROORGANISMS, THE MORE RAPID THE CHANGE OF COLOR

2. SELECTED REAGENTS FOR THE SELECTIVE SEARCH OF THE FOLLOWING MICROORGANISMS ARE:

- CBT-A01 (TOTAL VIABLE COUNT)
- CO-A02 (COLIFORMS)
- EC –A22 (ESCHERICHIA COLI)
- SL-A06 (SALMONELLA SPP.)
- LY-A07 (LISTERIA SPP.)

OTHER REAGENTS ARE AVAILABLE, BUT THEY ARE NOT APPLICABLE TO VEGETABLES

1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

WARNING

THE OPERATIONS WITH THE IDENTIFIED REAGENTS ARE CORRELATED WITH SEVERAL HAZARDS AS DESCRIBED IN THE REAGENTS SAFETY DATA SHEETS. THE MITIGATION OF SUCH HAZARDS REQUIRES THE ADOPTION OF SEVERAL PRECAUTIONS AS LISTED BELOW:

- REAGENTS SHALL BE USED/STORED AWAY FROM HEAT, HOT SURFACES, SPARKS, OPEN FLAMES AND OTHER IGNITION SOURCES
- SMOKING IS FORBIDDEN DURING THE HANDLING OF REAGENTS
- CREW SHALL WEAR WEAR PROTECTIVE GLOVES/ PROTECTIVE CLOTHING/ EYE PROTECTION/ FACE PROTECTION DURING THE OPERATIONS

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- REAGENT SHALL NOT BE RELEASED TO THE ENVIRONMENT.

NOTE

BEFORE HANDLING THE VIALS AND PROCEEDING WITH THE ANALYSIS A THOROUGH HAND WASHING IS RECOMMENDED.

- 1.1 Retrieve the MBS kit from storage with the selected reagent
- 1.2 Carefully wash your hand
- 1.3 Don Gloves
- 1.4 Don Protective Glass
- 1.5 Don Protective Mask

Figure 1: Reagent Vial Opening

- 1.6 Open the vial, taking care to flip the cap so that the inner surface does not come into contact with the surface to avoid contamination.

Figure 2: Reagent preparation

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(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE/HC)

1.7 Open the vial of water supplied with the reaction vial, and insert the entire contents of the vial itself. Mix by shake the vial until the reagent is completely dissolved and no solid powder is present (20 seconds using a vortex)

1.8 Wait 10 minutes. After that the reagent is ready for use.

2 ANALYSIS EXECUTION

NOTE

1. THE SIZE OR THE EXACT WEIGHT OF THE SAMPLE TO BE EXAMINED IS NOT SO IMPORTANT. HOWEVER, THE SAMPLE MUST BE REDUCED TO A VERY SMALL PARTS (MAXIMUM SIZE 2-3 MM)
2. FOR INSERTING THE SAMPLE INTO THE VIAL, WE RECOMMEND USING A TOOL USED DURING THE PROCESSING OF THE FOOD ITSELF, SINCE BY SO DOING, YOU WILL BE ABLE TO DETECT ANY CONTAMINATION OF THE FOOD DUE TO EXTRINSIC CAUSES.

Figure 3: Inserting the sample in the vial

2.1 Take a small part of the vegetable (about the volume of a grain of corn, approximately corresponding to 1 g) with a tool used during the processing of the food itself and insert it into the vial (alternatively you can use sterile tweezers)

2.2 Accurately mix the sample with the solution contained into the vial by inverting the vial several times.

NOTE

THE INCUBATOR TEMPERATURE AND THE INCUBATION DURATION ARE DEFINED AS FOLLOW:

REAGENT	U.M	Limit of Acceptability	TEMP. (degC)	TIME OF OBSERVATION (hh.min)
TOTAL VIABLE COUNT	CFG/g	10^7	30	03:00
COLIFORMS	CFU/g	10^3	37	16:35
ESCHERICHIA COLI	CFU/g	10^3	44	26:00
SALMONELLA SPP	CFU/g	0	37	67:00

3.212 Safety Analysis Using the Micro Biological Survey Method

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE/HC)

LISTERIA SPP	CFU/25g	0	37	36:00
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ANY CHANGE IN THE COLOUR OF THE SOLUTION BEFORE THIS TIME REPRESENT A LEVEL OF CONTAMINATION HIGHER THAN THE ACCEPTABLE LIMITS. SHORTER IS THE TIME, HIGHER IS THE LEVEL OF CONTAMINATION.

- 2.3 Place the vial in the incubator thermostat and setup the temperature as per reagent requirement
- 2.4 Log the activity in the log journal
- 2.5 Wait the needed time as defined per reagent

3 RESULTS EVALUATION

NOTE	
1.	FOR LONG TIME OF OBSERVATION IT IS RECOMMENDED TO HAVE INTERMEDIATE CHECK'S.
2.	THE ANALYSIS RESULT IS POSITIVE IF, AND ONLY IF, OCCURS A COMPLETE COLOR CHANGE OF THE VIAL CONTENT
3.	THE COLOR PALETTE, AS WELL OTHER RELEVANT INFORMATIONS ARE PROVIDED AS ANNEX TO THIS PROCEDURE.

- 3.1 Check periodically for color status. Log on the log journal the time and the results of the observation. Report to MCC at the end.

4 POST-ANALYSIS STERILIZATION

NOTE	
1.	STERILIZATION OF THE VIALS IS REQUIRED BEFORE THE DISPOSAL
2.	THE ADDITION OF THE STERILIZING AGENT CAN CAUSE A FURTHER COLOR CHANGE

Figure 4: Sterilization

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(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE/HC)

- 4.1 After analysis, without opening the vial, firmly press the top of the cap and shake for about 10 seconds. After 5-10 minutes the contents of the vial is completely sterilized
- 4.2 Waste the vials according to the NMIII disposal procedures

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ANNEX 1: CBT-A01 - TOTAL VIABLE COUNT CONTROL SHEET

MBS MICRO BIOLOGICAL SURVEY		TOTAL VIABLE COUNT CONTROL SHEET										CBT-A01		
ANALYTICAL METHOD		Detection of aerobic or microaerophilic mesophilic microorganisms which are able to grow on complete media.										SCQ CBT-A01 (30) 16.01		
MBS - MICRO BIOLOGICAL SURVEY		COLOR OF ANALYSIS AT START				COLOR OF ANALYSIS AT END			POSITIVE			NEGATIVE		
INCUBATION TEMPERATURE	30 °C													
CONTAMINATION [CFU/g] [CFU/ml] [CFU/100cm ²]		10 ⁶	10 ⁷	10 ⁶	10 ⁵	10 ⁴	10 ³	10 ²	10	1	0			
TIME OF COLOR CHANGE [hour, minutes]	Water	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Meat	< 2.30	2.30	7.00	11.20	16.00	20.50	25.00	30.00	34.00	36.00			
	Fish	< 2.00	5.00	8.30	12.15	16.00	19.30	23.20	27.00	31.00	36.00			
	Dairy product	< 2.30	2.30	6.00	9.40	13.15	16.45	20.20	24.00	27.30	36.00			
	Vegetables	< 3.00	3.00	6.30	10.00	13.30	17.00	20.20	23.50	27.15	36.00			
	Other	< 3.00	6.50	10.00	14.00	17.20	20.50	24.30	28.00	32.00	36.00			
	Surfaces	< 3.00	6.50	10.00	14.00	17.20	20.50	24.30	28.00	32.00	36.00			
QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS														
According to main standards and EU Regulations.														
TYPE OF SAMPLE						U.M.	LIMIT OF ACCEPTABILITY	TIME OF OBSERVATION [hours, minutes]						
FOOD														
Raw meat and preparations of meat						CFU/g	10 ⁶	7.00						
Milk and dairy products						CFU/ml	10 ⁶	6.00						
Fresh vegetables; precut vegetables (ready to eat)						CFU/g	10 ⁷	3.00						
Egg products						CFU/g	10 ⁵	14.00						
Ice-cream; bakery products						CFU/g	10 ⁵	14.00						
Cooked and stewed products						CFU/g	10 ⁴	17.20						
First and second courses cooked, served hot and cold						CFU/g	10 ⁶	10.00						
Frozen fishery products						CFU/g	10 ⁶	8.30						
Frozen meat and preparations of meat						CFU/g	10 ⁶	7.00						
Pre-cooked frozen dishes						CFU/g	10 ⁵	14.00						
Frozen vegetables						CFU/g	10 ⁶	6.30						
SURFACES														
Worktops; tools						CFU/cm ²	10 ²	17.20						
Hands						CFU/cm ²	10 ³	14.00						
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3.212 Safety Analysis Using the Micro Biological Survey Method (EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE/HC)

ANNEX 2: CO-A02 - COLIFORMS CONTROL SHEET

MBS MICRO BIOLOGICAL SURVEY		COLIFORMS CONTROL SHEET								CO-A02	
ANALYTICAL METHOD		Rod-shaped aerobic, Gram-negative, non spore-forming, cytochrome oxidase negative microorganism; fermenting lactose with production of acids in the presence of bile salts or other surfactants.									
MBS - MICRO BIOLOGICAL SURVEY		SCQ CO-A02 (37) 17.01									
INCUBATION TEMPERATURE	COLOR OF ANALYSIS AT START			COLOR OF ANALYSIS AT END		POSITIVE			NEGATIVE		
37 °C											
CONTAMINATION [CFU/g] [CFU/ml] [CFU/100cm ²]		10 ⁹	10 ⁷	10 ⁶	10 ⁵	10 ⁴	10 ³	10 ²	10	1	0
TIME OF COLOR CHANGE [hours.minutes]	Water	< 3.00	< 3.00	< 3.00	< 3.00	3.10	9.25	15.35	21.50	28.15	36.00
	Meat	< 4.00	< 4.00	4.10	8.20	12.30	16.35	20.50	25.00	29.10	36.00
	Fish	< 4.00	< 4.00	4.10	8.20	12.30	16.35	20.50	25.00	29.10	36.00
	Dairy product	< 4.00	< 4.00	4.10	8.20	12.30	16.35	20.50	25.00	29.10	36.00
	Vegetables	< 4.00	< 4.00	4.10	8.20	12.30	16.35	20.50	25.00	29.10	36.00
	Other	< 4.00	< 4.00	4.10	8.20	12.30	16.35	20.50	25.00	29.10	36.00
	Surfaces	< 4.00	< 4.00	4.10	8.20	12.30	16.35	20.50	25.00	29.10	36.00
QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS											
According to main standards and EU Regulations											
TYPE OF SAMPLE		U.M.	LIMIT OF ACCEPTABILITY	TIME OF OBSERVATION [hours.minutes]							
FOOD											
Raw meat		CFU/g	10 ³	9.25							
Raw milk and products made from raw milk		CFU/ml	10 ⁵	8.20							
Milk and products made from milk		CFU/ml	10 ³	16.35							
Egg products		CFU/g	10 ³	16.35							
Fresh vegetables		CFU/g	10 ³	16.35							
Preparations of mixed ingredients (ready to eat)		CFU/g	10 ²	20.50							
First and second courses cooked, served hot and cold		CFU/g	10	25.00							
Frozen precooked dishes		CFU/g	10 ⁵	8.20							
SURFACES											
Worktops; tools		CFU/cm ²	10	16.35							
Hands		CFU/cm ²	10 ²	12.30							
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ANNEX 3: EC-A22 – ESCHERECHIA COLI CONTROL SHEET

MBS MICRO BIOLOGICAL SURVEY		Escherichia coli CONTROL SHEET										EC-A22			
ANALYTICAL METHOD		Rod-shaped aerobic, Gram-negative, non spore-forming, cytochrome oxidase negative microorganism; fermenting lactose with production of acids in the presence of bile salts or other surfactants; at a temperature of 44 °C produce indole from tryptophan.										SCQ EC-A22 (44) 17.01			
MBS - MICRO BIOLOGICAL SURVEY		COLOR OF ANALYSIS AT START				COLOR OF ANALYSIS AT END				POSITIVE			NEGATIVE		
INCUBATION TEMPERATURE	44 °C														
CONTAMINATION [CFU/g] [CFU/ml] [CFU/100cm ²]		10 ⁰	10 ⁷	10 ⁶	10 ⁵	10 ⁴	10 ³	10 ²	10	1	0				
TIME OF COLOR CHANGE [hours.minutes]	Water	< 3.00	< 3.00	< 3.00	3.10	9.40	15.40	21.50	28.10	34.20	40.00				
	Meat	< 3.00	< 3.00	7.15	13.30	19.45	26.00	35.15	38.30	44.50	48.00				
	Fish	< 3.00	< 3.00	7.15	13.30	19.45	26.00	35.15	38.30	44.50	48.00				
	Dairy product	< 3.00	< 3.00	7.15	13.30	19.45	26.00	35.15	38.30	44.50	48.00				
	Vegetables	< 3.00	< 3.00	7.15	13.30	19.45	26.00	35.15	38.30	44.50	48.00				
	Other	< 3.00	< 3.00	7.15	13.30	19.45	26.00	35.15	38.30	44.50	48.00				
	Surfaces	< 3.00	< 3.00	7.15	13.30	19.45	26.00	35.15	38.30	44.50	48.00				
QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS															
According to main standards and EU Regulations															
TYPE OF SAMPLE							U.M.	LIMIT OF ACCEPTABILITY	TIME OF OBSERVATION [hours.minutes]						
FOOD															
Fresh pastry and bakery products							CFU/g	10	38.30						
Raw meat; minced meat; preparations of meat							CFU/g	10 ²	35.15						
Fishery products, seafood, shellfish							CFU/g	10	38.30						
Egg products							CFU/g	10 ²	35.15						
Milk and products made from milk							CFU/g	10 ²	35.15						
Pre-cut vegetables (ready to eat); fruit juice							CFU/g	10 ²	26.00						
Preparations of mixed ingredients cooked (ready to eat)							CFU/g	10	38.30						
Preparations of mixed ingredients not cooked (ready to eat)							CFU/g	10 ²	35.15						
SURFACES															
Worktops; tools							CFU/cm ²	10	26.00						
Hands							CFU/cm ²	10	26.00						
WATER															
Water for human consumption							CFU/100ml	0	40.00						
Water for human consumption placed in bottles or containers							CFU/250ml	0	40.00						
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3.212 Safety Analysis Using the Micro Biological Survey Method (EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE/HC)

ANNEX 4: SL-A06 – SALMONELLA SLL CONTROL SHEET

MBS MICRO BIOLOGICAL SURVEY		Salmonella spp. CONTROL SHEET										SL-A06
ANALYTICAL METHOD		Gram-negative, aerobic-anaerobic facultative enterobacteria, able to ferment mannitol. Catalase positive, produce hydrogen sulfide, reduce nitrate to nitrite.										
MBS - MICRO BIOLOGICAL SURVEY		SCQ SL-A06 (37) 16.01										
INCUBATION TEMPERATURE	COLOR OF ANALYSIS AT START			COLOR OF ANALYSIS AT END			POSITIVE			NEGATIVE		
	37 °C											
CONTAMINATION [CFU/g] [CFU/ml] [CFU/100cm ²]		10 ⁰	10 ¹	10 ²	10 ³	10 ⁴	10 ⁵	10 ⁶	10 ⁷	10 ⁸	10 ⁹	
TIME OF COLOR CHANGE [hours.minutes]	Water	< 10.00	< 10.00	< 10.00	11.00	22.10	33.15	44.20	55.30	66.30	67.00	
	Meat	< 10.00	< 10.00	< 10.00	11.00	22.10	33.15	44.20	55.30	66.30	67.00	
	Fish	< 10.00	< 10.00	< 10.00	11.00	22.10	33.15	44.20	55.30	66.30	67.00	
	Dairy product	< 10.00	< 10.00	< 10.00	11.00	22.10	33.15	44.20	55.30	66.30	67.00	
	Vegetables	< 10.00	< 10.00	< 10.00	11.00	22.10	33.15	44.20	55.30	66.30	67.00	
	Other	< 10.00	< 10.00	< 10.00	11.00	22.10	33.15	44.20	55.30	66.30	67.00	
	Surfaces	< 10.00	< 10.00	< 10.00	11.00	22.10	33.15	44.20	55.30	66.30	67.00	
QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS												
According to main standards and EU Regulations												
TYPE OF SAMPLE				U.M.	LIMIT OF ACCEPTABILITY	TIME OF OBSERVATION [hours.minutes]						
FOOD												
Raw meat; minced meat and preparations of meat				CFU/25g	0	67.00						
Yogurt; pasteurized milk; cheses				CFU/25g	0	67.00						
Washed fresh vegetables; precut vegetables (ready to eat)				CFU/25g	0	67.00						
Fresh whole eggs (shell) and egg products				CFU/25g	0	67.00						
Milk powder and whey powder				CFU/25g	0	67.00						
Shelled crustaceans products and cooked molluscs				CFU/25g	0	67.00						
Live bivalve molluscs, echinoderms, tunicates and gastropods				CFU/25g	0	67.00						
Powdered infant products and dried dietary for special medical purposes products				CFU/25g	0	67.00						
Frozen fishery products				CFU/25g	0	67.00						
Frozen pre-cooked dishes				CFU/25g	0	67.00						
SURFACES												
Worktops; tools				CFU/cm ²	0	67.00						
Hands				CFU/cm ²	0	67.00						
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3.212 Safety Analysis Using the Micro Biological Survey Method (EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE/HC)

ANNEX 5: LY-A07 – LISTERIA CONTROL SHEET

MBS MICRO BIOLOGICAL SURVEY		Listeria spp. CONTROL SHEET										LY-A07
ANALYTICAL METHOD		Gram-positive, non spore-forming, facultative anaerobic microorganisms, resistant to many antibiotics. Grow at pH between 5 and 9 and in the presence of NaCl to 10%. Catalase positive, oxidase negative, do not hydrolyze urea, gelatin and casein. Do not reduce nitrates and do not produce indole nor hydrogen sulfide.										
MBS - MICRO BIOLOGICAL SURVEY		SCQ LY-A07 (37) 16.01										
INCUBATION TEMPERATURE	COLOR OF ANALYSIS AT START			COLOR OF ANALYSIS AT END			POSITIVE			NEGATIVE		
37 °C												
CONTAMINATION [CFU/g] [CFU/ml] [CFU/100cm ²]		10 ⁸	10 ⁷	10 ⁶	10 ⁵	10 ⁴	10 ³	10 ²	10	1	0	
TIME OF COLOR CHANGE [hours:minutes]	Water	< 4.00	4.00	8.00	12.00	16.00	20.00	24.00	28.00	23.00	36.00	
	Meat	< 4.00	4.00	8.00	12.00	16.00	20.00	24.00	28.00	23.00	36.00	
	Fish	< 4.00	4.00	8.00	12.00	16.00	20.00	24.00	28.00	23.00	36.00	
	Dairy product	< 4.00	4.00	8.00	12.00	16.00	20.00	24.00	28.00	23.00	36.00	
	Vegetables	< 4.00	4.00	8.00	12.00	16.00	20.00	24.00	28.00	23.00	36.00	
	Other	< 4.00	4.00	8.00	12.00	16.00	20.00	24.00	28.00	23.00	36.00	
	Surfaces	< 4.00	4.00	8.00	12.00	16.00	20.00	24.00	28.00	23.00	36.00	
QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS												
According to main standards and EU Regulations												
TYPE OF SAMPLE		U.M.	LIMIT OF ACCEPTABILITY		TIME OF OBSERVATION [hours:minutes]							
FOOD												
Foods for infants and for special medical purposes (according to Reg.to CE 2073/05)		CFU/25g	0		36.00							
Other foods than those intended for infants and for special medical purposes who are able to support growth of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>		CFU/25g	0		36.00							
Meat and preparations of meat		CFU/25g	0		36.00							
Washed vegetables; precut vegetables (ready to eat)		CFU/25g	0		36.00							
Preparations of mixed ingredients (ready to eat)		CFU/25g	0		36.00							
Pasteurized milk		CFU/25g	0		36.00							
Soft cheeses (made from heat-treated milk); cheeses made from raw milk		CFU/25g	0		36.00							
First, second courses and vegetables cooked		CFU/25g	0		36.00							
Frozen fishery products		CFU/g	10 ²		24.00							
Frozen vegetables and fruits		CFU/g	10 ²		24.00							
SURFACES												
Worktops; tools		CFU/cm ²	0		36.00							
Hands		CFU/cm ²	0		36.00							
MBS SRL - Via Giacomo Peroni 386 - 00131 Roma (IT) - CF e PI 09423051003 Tel. +39.06.40040358 - Fax +39.06.40040364 - www.emmeblesse.net - info@emmeblesse.net												

3.220 Sample Collection and Storage for Quality Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Collection and storage of samples for the quality analysis to be performed at the CNR and LIT laboratory

DURATION

TBD

TOOLS (per sampling event)

FreeZone® 6 Liter Benchtop Freeze Dry System

Vacuum Pump

Weight scale

1 Scalpel

1 Scissor

1 Kitchen knife

1 Pruning Shears

ITEMS (per sampling event)

1 pair of gloves

1 plastic bowl

12 sealable aluminum foil bags

1 laboratory book

1 permanent black marker

absorbent paper

NOTE

1. FOR THE ANALYSIS TO BE PERFORMED AT CNR AND LIT LABORATORIES, A CRUCIAL ACTIVITY TO BE PERFORMED BY THE ANTARCTICA OPERATOR IS THE SAMPLE PREPARATION AND STORAGE. DEPENDING ON THE ANALYSIS TO BE DONE TWO KIND OF TREATMENTS ARE FORESEEN, A SIMPLE FREEZING AT -20°C OR THE SAMPLE LIOPHYLIZATION. IN PREPARATION OF THIS LAST A PRELIMINARY FREEZING AT -80°C HAS TO BE DONE.
2. AS A PRELIMINARY ESTIMATE, IT IS ASSUMED THAT 100 G OF FRESH MATERIAL SHOULD BE SUFFICIENT TO PERFORM ALL ANALYSIS, TAKING INTO CONSIDERATION THAT THE DRY MATTER CONTENT OF THE TISSUES IS NORMALLY CLOSE TO 5%. COLLECTING 100G OF FRESH MATERIAL SHOULD PROVIDE APPROXIMATELY 5G OF DRY MATTER.

SS 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

- 1.1 Prepare and/or collect the required tools and items
- 1.2 Carefully wash the hands
- 1.3 Wear the gloves

3.220 Sample Collection and Storage for Quality Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 1: Bag labelling

Figure 2: Taking the weight of the bag and of the plastic bowl

- 1.4 Using the permanent black marker, labels each bag with the following information:
DATE, SPECIES, LOCATION, SUB1 or SUB2, REP. #
- 1.5 Weigh the bag and log the weight on the log journal to have the tare value for each bag
- 1.6 Weigh the plastic bowl and log the weight on a log journal to have the tare

2 PLANT SAMPLING

FEG 2.1 SAMPLING OF EDIBLE FRUITS

NOTE

1. TWELVE (12) SAMPLES PER SPECIES HAVE TO BE COLLECTED BY CREW AS PER THE FOLLOWING SCHEMA:
 - THREE (3) PLANTS IN THREE DIFFERENT LOCATIONS
 - FOUR (4) FRUITS PER PLANTTHE FRUITS SHALL BE UNIFORM WITH RESPECT TO THEIR POSITION ON THE PLANT, THE RIPENING STATE AND THE DIMENSION
2. THE SAMPLING ACTIVITY SHALL BE QUICKLY COMPLETED IN ORDER TO PRESERVE THE DIFFERENT QUALITATIVE METHABOLITES

3.220 Sample Collection and Storage for Quality Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 3: Cucumber sampling

3.220 Sample Collection and Storage for Quality Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 4: Pepper sampling

Figure 5: Tomatoes sampling

2.1.1 Collect the required fruits for sampling

3.220 Sample Collection and Storage for Quality Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

2.1.2 Using the kitchen knife, cut the fruit in small pieces as per the sequence shown in Fig. 3,4 and 5. Remove the non-edible parts.

2.1.3 Go to step 2.4

2.2 SAMPLING OF EDIBLE LEAVES

NOTE

1. TWELVE (12) SAMPLES PER SPECIES HAVE TO BE COLLECTED BY CREW AS PER THE FOLLOWING SCHEMA:

- THREE (3) PLANTS IN THREE DIFFERENT LOCATIONS
- FOUR (4) SAMPLING PER PLANT

LEAFY VEGETABLE SAMPLED MUST BE UNIFORM IN RELATION TO THE NUMBER OF LEAVES, HEIGHT, LIGHT EXPOSITION, AND ALL TYPES OF TISSUES MUST BE PRESENT IN THE SAMPLE (FOR EXAMPLE LEAF LAMINA AND PETIOLES)

2. THE SAMPLING ACTIVITY SHALL BE QUICKLY COMPLETED IN ORDER TO PRESERVE THE DIFFERENT QUALITATIVE METHABOLITES

Figure 6: Lettuce Sampling

2.2.1 Collect the required leafy vegetables for sampling

2.2.2 If the leafy vegetable is a Lettuce, using the kitchen knife, cut the fruit in small pieces as per the sequence shown in Fig. 6.

3.220 Sample Collection and Storage for Quality Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 7: Swiss Chard, Rockets and Red Mustard Samples

2.2.3 If the leafy vegetables are Swiss Chard, Rockets or Red Mustard cut the plant at the base by means of a pruning shears

2.2.4 GOTO step 2.4

2.3 SAMPLING OF EDIBLE TAP ROOTS

NOTE

1. TWELVE (12) SAMPLES PER SPECIES HAVE TO BE COLLECTED BY CREW AS PER THE FOLLOWING SCHEMA:
 - THREE (3) PLANTS IN THREE DIFFERENT LOCATIONS
 - FOUR (4) SAMPLING PER PLANTTHE TAP ROOTS SHOULD BE ROUND (THE DIAMETER USUALLY IS ABOUT 8-15MM) AND WITH A RED COLOR
2. THE SAMPLING ACTIVITY SHALL BE QUICKLY COMPLETED IN ORDER TO PRESERVE THE DIFFERENT QUALITATIVE METHABOLITES

2.3.1 Collect the required fruits for sampling

2.3.2 Using the kitchen knife, cut the taproot in four small part (as for tomatoes , see Fig 5)

2.4 SAMPLE PREPARATION

2.4.1 Collect 100 g of material

2.4.2 Put 20 g of material in the bag labelled SUB1 and 80 g in the bag labelled SUB2. Close them

2.4.3 Store the SUB1 bags in the freezer at -20degC

2.4.4 Store the SUB2 bags in the freezer at -80degC

NMIII 5 SUB2 SAMPLES LYOPHILISATION

NOTE

1. LYOPHILISATION (OR FREEZE DRYING) IS A PROCESS WHEREBY WATER, OR ANOTHER SOLVENT, IS REMOVED FROM FROZEN MATERIAL BY CONVERTING THE FROZEN WATER DIRECTLY INTO VAPOUR WITHOUT THE INTERMEDIATE FORMATION OF LIQUID WATER. IT IS AN IMPORTANT PROCESS IN SAMPLE PREPARATION AND FOR THE PRESERVATION AND STORAGE OF BIOLOGICALS, PHARMACEUTICALS AND FOODS

3.220 Sample Collection and Storage for Quality Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2. LYOPHILISATION IS REQUIRED FOR THE ONLY SAMPLES MARKED AS SUB2
- 3. **TBD** TIME AT -80°C IS NECESSARY TO HAVE THE SAMPLE READY FOR LIOPHYLIZATION

Figure 8: Sample insertion sequence

Figure 9: Freeze drier Control Panel

5.1 When the sample is ready start the liophylisation process.

5.2 INSTRUMENT INIZALITION

5.2.1 Ensure the dryer manifold and collector are dry. Remove any moisture before continuing with operation

5.2.2 Turn ON the **Main Power Switch** – located on the left side of the cabinet

3.220 Sample Collection and Storage for Quality Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

5.2.3 Place the drying manifold on top of the collector, ensuring the rubber seals are aligned

5.2.4 Press the **Manual Refrigeration Switch**. The freezer dryer will begin cooling to -50C

5.3 SAMPLE ADDITION AND DRYING

5.3.1 Once the **Collector Temperature Graph Display** indicates that the temperature has adequately reduced, retrieve the bags labelled SUB2 from the freezer, and place them, upright where possible, into the drying manifold. Ensure that the bags are only partially sealed

5.3.2 Place the lid onto the drying manifold, ensuring it is secure, close the valve

5.3.3 Press the **Auto Mode Switch**. This will switch off the manual function

5.3.4 Press the **Auto Mode Switch** a second time to initiate the vacuum

5.3.5 Monitor the **Vacuum Graph Display** until the lower green LED light is steadily illuminated

5.3.6 Once the **Collector Temperature Graph Display** and **Vacuum Graph Display** both have the lower green LED lights steadily illuminating, the sample have begun lyophilising

5.4 SAMPLE REMOVAL

CAUTION

Return from vacuum to ambient pressure has to be done with caution. Opening the valve too quickly or completely at first will cause the vacuum to be released too soon resulting the samples being destroyed or ejected from the sample bags

5.4.1 Once the samples have been adequately dried for between 24 and 36 hours, depending on the tissue quantity, press the **Auto Mode Switch** to turn off the vacuum

5.4.2 Relieve the vacuum by opening the drying manifold valve slightly and very gently.

5.4.3 Once the vacuum has completely dissipated, as indicated by the **Vacuum Graph Display**, the drying manifold can be carefully taken off the drying chamber using an upwards motion.

5.4.4 Remove the samples and shut the bags in order to have them fully sealed

5.4.5 Store the bags at 4°C

5.5 Instrument Shut-off

3.220 Sample Collection and Storage for Quality Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 5.5.1 Defrost the ice build-up inside the drying chamber by either exposing the chamber to ambient temperatures and allow to melt naturally, or by adding warm water to aid the process.
 - 5.5.2 Open the hose on the right of the chamber to drain the waste water
 - 5.5.3 Once drained reseal the hose and dry the inside of the chamber with some paper towels or a cloth.
 - 5.5.4 Switch the **Main Power Switch** to the OFF position
- 6 **CLOSEOUT**
- 6.1 Take Off the gloves and wash your hand
 - 6.2 Clean the tools and stow them
 - 6.3 Waste the not used plants part.

3.230 Quality Measurement: Refractometer Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Measurement of refractive index to determine the % Brix of sugar in aqueous solutions

DURATION

5 minutes per measurement

TOOLS

HANNA HI 96801 Refractometer

ITEMS

Plastic pipette

Garlic Squeezer

Deionized or distilled water (100 ml)

Soft tissue

NOTE

THE REFRACTOMETER IS A TOOL THAT MEASURE THE PERCENT SOLIDS (TSS) IN A GIVEN WEIGHT OF PLANT JUICE (ALSO CALLED BRIX). THE BRIX IS ACTUALLY A SUMMATION OF THE POUNDS OF SUCROSE, FRUCTOSE, VITAMINS, MINERALS, AMINO ACIDS, PROTEINS, HORMONES, AND OTHER SOLIDS IN ONE HUNDRED POUNDS OF ANY PARTICULAR PLANT JUICE. BRIX VARIES DIRECTLY WITH PLANT **QUALITY**, FOR THIS REASON THE REFRACTOMETER WILL BE USED IN THE EDEN ISS OPERATIONS.

Figure 1: HANNA HI 96801 Refractometer

3.230 Quality Measurement: Refractometer Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

1. **Battery** (blinks when low battery condition detected)
2. **Primary Display** (displays measurement and error messages)
3. **Measurement in Progress Tag**
4. **SETUP:** Factory Calibration Tag
5. **CAL:** Calibration Tag
6. **Measurement Unit**
7. **Automatic Temperature Compensation** (blinks when temperature exceeds 10-40 °C range)
8. **Temperature Units**
9. **Secondary Display** (displays temperature measurements; when blinking, temperature has exceeded operation range: 0-80 °C)

Figure 2: Displays Elements

1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

- 1.1 Collect all the required items and tools
- 1.2 Carefully wash your hands

2 INSTRUMENT CALIBRATION

NOTE

CALIBRATION HAS TO BE DONE EVERY DAY BEFORE STARTING WITH THE MEASUREMENTS, OR AFTER A LONG SERIES OF MEASUREMENTS.

Figure 3: Calibration

3.230 Quality Measurement: Refractometer Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2.1 Using a plastic pipette, fill the sample well with distilled or deionized water. Make sure the prism is completely covered
- 2.2 Cover the sample well with your hand or other shading plate during the calibration
- 2.3 Press the zero key. If no error messages appears, the unit is calibrated. The zero will be set on the display and will remain until the unit is deactivated
- 2.4 Using a soft tissue, remove the water and dry the surface

3 TAKING MEASUREMENT

Figure 4: Taking measurements

Produce	Avg %Brix
Rocket	4.57
Lettuce	1.47
Pepper (Green) (3gFW)	4.63
Pepper (Red) (3gFW)	4.83
Salad Tomato	4
Small Cherry	7.6
large Cherry	5.8

Fig. 5: Expected values for plant species

- 3.1 Place approximately 2g of sample (could be fruit or leaf) in garlic press and squeeze juice out in the sample well (this operations can also be done by hand). Make sure the prism is completely covered.

NOTE

3.230 Quality Measurement: Refractometer Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

1. IF THE TEMPERATURE OF THE SAMPLE DIFFERS SIGNIFICANTLY FROM THE TEMPERATURE OF THE INSTRUMENT, WAIT APPROXIMATELY 1 MINUTE TO ALLOW THERMAL EQUILIBRATION.
2. THE LAST MEASUREMENT VALUE WILL BE DISPLAYED UNTIL THE NEXT SAMPLE IS MEASURED OR THE INSTRUMENT IS TURNED OFF. TEMPERATURE WILL BE CONTINUOUSLY UPDATED.
3. THE ATC TAG BLINKS AND AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE COMPENSATION IS DISABLED IF THE TEMPERATURE EXCEEDS THE 10-40 °C RANGE.

3.2 Press the **READ** key

3.3 Take the reading and log it in the log journal

4 **SAMPLE WELL CLEANING**

Figure 6: Sample well cleaning

4.1 Remove sample from the sample well by absorbing with a soft tissue. Use care not to scratch the prism surface. Dry the surface completely

4.2 Using a plastic pipette, rinse prism and sample well with distilled or deionized water. Wipe dry.

5 **CLOSEOUT**

5.1 If a new measurement is required GOTO step 3

5.2 Shutdown the instrument and stow it

5.3 Carefully wash the garlic squeezer and stow it

3.231 Quality Measurement: Penetrometer Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Indicative measurement of fruit firmness for ripening.

DURATION

5 minutes per measurement

TOOLS

PCE Instruments Force Gauge PCE-FM 200

ITEMS

Soft Tissue

NOTE

1. THE PENETROMETER IS A HAND-HELD DEVICE USED TO MEASURE THE FIRMNESS OF RELATIVELY HOMOGENOUS FRUIT AND/OR VEGETABLES. IN THE EDEN ISS OPERATIONS IT WILL BE USED FOR THE QUALITY ANALYSIS OF THE CUCUMBERS, TOMATOES AND PEPPERS
2. SEVERAL SENSING HEADS CAN BE MOUNTED ON THE INSTRUMENT (THE PICTURE SHOWS THE HOOK HEAD MOUNTED ON THE INSTRUMENT FOR TENSION MEASUREMENT). FOR THE EDEN ISS THE ONLY CONIC HEAD HAS TO BE CONSIDERED
3. NO SAMPLE PREPARATION IS NECESSARY AS THE INSTRUMENT CAN BE USED DIRECTLY ON THE FRUIT *IN SITU*.

Figure 1: PCE Instruments Force Gauge PCE-FM 200

SS 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

- 1.1 Retrieve the Penetrometer from the stowage
- 1.2 Slide the **Power Off/On/Peak Hold button** to the "On" position.
- 1.3 Select the measurement by pressing the **g/oz/N Unit Switch**

3.231 Quality Measurement: Penetrometer Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 1.4 Carefully wash your hands
- 1.5 Attach the cone adapter provided for measurement of tomato, bell pepper cucumber, and strawberry
- 1.6 Zero the instrument by pressing the **Zero Button**.

FEG 2 SAMPLE MEASUREMENT

NOTE

1. THE COMPRESSION MEASURING FUNCTION IS EXECUTED AUTOMATICALLY
2. THE OBJECT BEING MEASURED SHOULD BE DIRECTLY IN LINE WITH THE SENSING HEAD

Figure 2: Taking measurement

3.231 Quality Measurement: Penetrometer Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Produce	Avg g/oz/N	Std Dev	95% CI
Baby Vine Tomatoes, N=12 x 2 reps	0.74	0.12	0.002
Baby Vine Plum Tomatoes, N=14 x 2 reps	0.89	0.07	0.001
Large Vine Tomatoes, N=5 x 3 reps	1.15	0.12	0.003
Salad Tomatoes, N=4 x 3 reps	1.82	0.05	0.001
Green Bell Pepper, N=3 x 4 reps	2.18	0.25	0.009
Yellow Bell Pepper, N=3 x 4 reps	2.02	0.05	0.002
Red Bell Pepper, N=3 x 4 reps	1.56	0.10	0.004
Cucumber, N=3 x 6 reps	2.17	0.08	0.003
Strawberries, N=18 x 2 reps	0.24	0.05	0.001

Figure 3: Example of expected values

- 2.1 Start the measurement by applying force (pushing the sensing adapter to the sample). Ensure that the motion used is constant and that the action is terminated once the end of the cone portion of the probe has been inserted into the sample. The LCD display will display the average value
- 2.2 Take the reading and log it in the log journal
- 2.3 Repeat for the other sample as required

FEG 3 CLOSEOUT

- 3.1 Shutdown the instrument
- 3.2 Dismount the Conic Head and clean it with a soft tissue and with water
- 3.3 Stow the tool

3.232 Quality Measurement: Colourimeter Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Measurement the colour co-ordinates of food samples

DURATION

5 minutes per measurement

TOOLS

PCE Instruments Colourimeter PCE-CSM 1

ITEMS

White Calibration Plate (if calibration is required)

NOTE

1. THE HAND-HELD COLORIMETER IS A TOOL FOR THE MEASUREMENT OF THE COLOUR COORDINATES OF FOOD SAMPLES AS AN INDICATION OF THE BIOACTIVE CONTENT. IN THE EDEN ISS PROGRAM THIS INSTRUMENT WILL ONLY BE USED ON LARGER FRUITS AND VEGETABLES SUCH AS TOMATOES (INCLUDING BABY TOMATOES), BELL PEPPER, CUCUMBERS. THE INSTRUMENTS READS THREE PARAMETERS, THE SO CALLED CIE SYSTEM COORDINATES (L^* , A^* , B^*):
 - A^* TAKES POSITIVE VALUES FOR REDDISH COLOURS AND NEGATIVE VALUES FOR THE GREENISH ONES
 - B^* TAKES POSITIVE VALUES FOR YELLOWISH COLOURS AND NEGATIVE VALUES FOR THE BLUISH ONES
 - L^* IS AN APPROXIMATE MEASUREMENT OF LUMINOSITY.
2. NO SAMPLE PREPARATION IS NECESSARY AS THE INSTRUMENT CAN BE USED DIRECTLY ON THE COLOURED FRUIT / VEGETABLE *IN SITU*.

Figure 1: PCE Instruments Colourimeter PCE-CSM 1

3.232 Quality Measurement: Colourimeter Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 2: Instrument Overview

- SS 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION**
- 1.1 Retrieve the Colourimeter from stowage
 - 1.2 Make sure the battery is installed or the device is connected to an external power source.
 - 1.3 Remove the dust protective black cover

3.232 Quality Measurement: Colourimeter Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 1.4 Turn on the device by switching the On/Off button to “1”. After a few seconds, you are automatically directed to the “Standard Measurement” screen. The default setting for this measuring mode is L*a*b*C*H.
- 1.5 If calibration is not required GOTO step 3
- 1.6 If standard measurement is not necessary GOTO step 5

2 INSTRUMENT CALIBRATION

NOTE

A CALIBRATION IS ONLY REASONABLE IN THE FOLLOWING CASES: WHEN FIRST USING THE DEVICE, AFTER STRONG CHANGES IN THE ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS, WHEN THE DEVICE HAS NOT BEEN USED FOR A SIGNIFICANT PERIOD OF TIME OR WHEN THE MEASUREMENT RESULTS ARE INACCURATE.

- 2.1 Press the Menu button, select “Calibrate “and press Enter
- 2.2 Use the arrow keys to select **white calibration** or **black calibration** and press Enter to confirm. A confirmation display with instructions will appear

2.3 Perform White Calibration

NOTE

WHITE CALIBRATION IS USED TO CONFIRM LUMINOSITY INTENSITY. IT IS RECOMMENDED FOR ALL FRUIT AND VEGETABLE ANALYSIS

- 2.3.1 Use the arrow keys to select **white calibration** and press Enter to confirm. A confirmation display with instructions will appear
- 2.3.2 Retrieve the calibration plate
- 2.3.3 Turn the device upside down and place the white calibration plate on the measuring aperture
- 2.3.4 Press the Testing button to start the calibration
- 2.3.5 Wait until the following message appears on the screen: White Calibration Success

2.4 Perform Black Calibration

NOTE

BLACK CALIBRATION IS USED TO DEEP COLOUR INTENSITY

- 2.4.1 Using the arrows keys, select **black calibration** and press enter to confirm. A confirmation display with instructions will appear

3.232 Quality Measurement: Colourimeter Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2.4.2 Point the instrument towards the air. Keep the device away at least 1 meter from reflecting objects like walls, tables or other objects
- 2.4.3 Press the Testing button to start the calibration
- 2.4.4 Wait until the following message appears on the screen: Black Calibration Success

FEG 3 TAKING A STANDARD MEASUREMENT

NOTE

1. THE STANDARD MEASUREMENT ALLOWS FOR CLEAR IDENTIFICATION OF STRONG RED, YELLOW AND GREEN COLOURS.
2. THE STANDARD MEASUREMENT IS RECORDED AND SAVED ON THE INTERNAL MEMORY OF THE COLOURIMETER. IT CAN THEN BE USED AS REFERENCE TO DETERMINE COLOUR CHANGE IN FRUITS AND VEGETABLES AS THEY GROW.

- 3.1 Prepare the RED colour reference items
- 3.2 Press and hold the testing button – located on the back panel of the device. Four (4) light cones appear to aid with selecting the measuring point.
- 3.3 Move the device as close to the measuring point as possible.
- 3.4 Release the testing button. The colorimeter now takes a measurement (Fig. 3)
- 3.5 Log the reading in the log journal (including date and time)

Figure 3: Standard Measurement Result

3.232 Quality Measurement: Colourimeter Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

3.5 Repeat step from 3.1. to 3.5 for YELLOW and GREEN colour standard measurements

4 SAMPLE MEASUREMENT

Fig. 4: Standard Record Display

4.1 Press the **Menu** button , select "Record" and press **Enter** to confirm. The standard record displays (fig.4) is displayed

4.2 Using the **key arrows** select the Standard Measurement to be used as reference for sample measurement (RED, YELLOW or GREEN)

Figure 4: Taking measurement of sample

4.3 Press **Enter** to get to the sample measurement display

3.232 Quality Measurement: Colourimeter Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 4.4 Press and hold the testing button – located on the back panel of the device. Four (4) light cones appear to aid with selecting the measuring point.
- 4.5 Move the device as close to the measuring point as possible (fig. 4)
- 4.6 Release the testing button. The colourimeter now takes a measurement

Figure 5: Sample Measurement Results

- 4.7 Read the deviations of the sample in the display (Fig. 5) and log them in the log journal
- 4.8 If another measurement is required with the same color reference press the **Back** button. The sample measurement display is displayed back. Repeat steps from 4.3 to 4.7
- 4.9 If other measurements for different colours have to be taken, press the **Back** button. Repeat step from 4.1 to 4.7 selecting the relevant Sample Measurement Displays.

SS 4 CLOSEOUT

- 3.1 Shutdown the instrument and stow it

3.232 Quality Measurement: Chlorophyll Meter Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Measurement of chlorophyll content in plant leaves

DURATION

5 minutes per measurement

TOOLS

MINOLTA Chlorophyll Meter SPAD-502

ITEMS

None

NOTE

1. THE AMOUNT OF CHLOROPHYLL PRESENT IN PLANT LEAVES CAN SERVE AS AN INDICATOR OF THE OVERALL CONDITION OF PLANT HEALTH. IN GENERAL, HEALTHIER PLANTS CONTAIN MORE CHLOROPHYLL THAN LESS HEALTHY PLANTS.
2. THE SPAD VALUE DETERMINED BY THE SPAD-502 PROVIDES AN INDICATION OF THE RELATIVE AMOUNT OF CHLOROPHYLL PRESENT IN PLANT LEAVES. THIS SPAD VALUE CAN BE USED TO DETERMINE WHEN AND IF ADDITIONAL NUTRIENTS ARE REQUIRED.
3. NO PREPARATION IS NECESSARY AS THE CHLOROPHYLL METER SPAD-502 CAN BE USED ON PLANT LEAVES DIRECTLY *IN SITU*

Figure 1: MINOLTA Chlorophyll Meter SPAD-502

3.232 Quality Measurement: Chlorophyll Meter Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- SS 1 **ACTIVITY PREPARATION****
- 1.1 Retrieve the Chlorophyll Meter from stowage

- 2 **INSTRUMENT CALIBRATION****

NOTE

CALIBRATION IS NECESSARY WHENEVER THE METER IS SWITCHED ON AFTER HAVING BEEN SWITCHED OFF

- 2.1 Turn the power switch to ON
- 2.2 When the word “Calibration” appears on the screen press close and hold the measuring head until a beep sounds and the following screen appears

Calibration is now complete

- 2.3 If a series of beeps sound and “Error” appears in the display, calibration was not preformed correctly. Repeat Step 2.1 and 2.2
- 2.4 If a series of beeps sound and “Error” and “E-U” appear in the display, then the measuring head may be dirty. Clean the windows and repeat steps 1 and 2.

- FEG 3 **CHLOROPHYLL CONTENT MEASUREMENTS****

Figure 2: taking measurements

3.232 Quality Measurement: Chlorophyll Meter Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Produce	Avg Reading	Std Dev	95% CI
Red Lettuce (Outrageous) Inner Green Leaf N=12	5.98	1.99	0.04
Red Lettuce (Outrageous) Outer Red Leaf N=12	29.33	7.25	0.13
Butterleaf Lettuce (Red Variety) Inner Green Leaf, N=10	3.79	2.50	0.05
Butterleaf Lettuce (Red Variety) Outer Red Leaf, N=10	36.08	10.52	0.21
Chives (leaf Bottom), N=6	34.13	8.77	0.22
Chives (leaf Middle), N=6	39.48	9.86	0.25
Chives (leaf Top), N=6	31.18	8.55	0.11
Parsley (Leaf), N=7	29.80	19.22	0.46
Parsley (Top of Stalk), N=7	15.43	7.79	0.18
Parsley (Bottom of Stalk), N=7	11.36	4.86	0.05

Figure 3: Expected Values

- 3.1 Insert the plant sample to be measured into the sample slot of the measuring head. Ensure the sample completely covers the receiving window.
- 3.2 Press and close the measuring head. Hold until a beep sounds. The measurement will appear on the display and will automatically be stored in the memory.
- 3.3 Log the measurement in the log journal
- 3.4 If a series of beeps sound and error is displayed on the screen measuring was not performed correctly. This may be due to the sample being too thick, the measuring head not being closed tightly enough or opened too soon. Repeat steps 3.1 and 3.2
- 3.5 If a series of beeps sounds and the word Calibration appears on the screen, then the temperature has changed by more than 10°C since calibration and needs recalibrating. Stored data will be deleted. GOTO step 2

SS 4 CLOSEOUT

- 3.1 Shutdown the instrument and stow it

3.234 Quality Measurement: Nitrate Ion Meter Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Measurement of the nitrate ion level of fruit and vegetables

DURATION

5 minutes per measurement + 30 minutes for sample preparation

TOOLS

Horiba Nitrate Ion Meter B-741
Pipetter
High Concentration Standard Solution
Low concentration Standard solution

ITEMS

Beaker
Laboratory Spatula
Deionised Water
Dry Wipes

NOTE

1. LEAFY VEGETABLES OCCUPY A VERY IMPORTANT PLACE IN THE HUMAN DIET, BUT UNFORTUNATELY CONSTITUTE A GROUP OF FOODS WHICH CONTRIBUTES MAXIMALLY TO NITRATE CONSUMPTION BY LIVING BEINGS. UNDER EXCESSIVE APPLICATION OF NITROGEN FERTILIZER, THESE VEGETABLES CAN ACCUMULATE HIGHLEVELS OF NITRATE AND, UPON BEING CONSUMED BY LIVING BEINGS, POSE SERIOUS HEALTH HAZARDS. THEREFORE, EFFORTS ARE WARRANTED TO CHECK IF THE NITRATE CONCENTRATION IN HARVESTED VEGETABLES ARE WITHIN THE ALLOWED RANGE FOR INGESTION BY HUMAN BEINGS.
2. SAMPLE PREPARATION IS REQUIRED BEFORE USING THE IN METER, AND THIS OPERATIONS IS VERY SIMILAR TO THE ONE DESCRIBED FOR THE ON-SITE SAFETY ANALYSIS. THEREFORE THE MEASUREMENT WITH THE NITRATE ION METER COULD BE COMBINED WITH THE SAFETY MEASUREMENT

Figure 1: Horiba Nitrate Ion Meter B-741

3.234 Quality Measurement: Nitrate Ion Meter Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

SS 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

- 1.1 Retrieve the Nitrate Ion Meter and the other tools and items from stowage

2 SAMPLE PREPARATION

NOTE

1. ONE SMALL PIECE (1 GRAMS) OF VEGETABLES ARE SUFFICIENT FOR THE ANALYSIS
2. THIS STEP CAN BE SKIPPED IF SAMPLES HAVE ALREADY BEEN PREPARED FOR SAFETY ANALYSIS (REF. 3.211 SAMPLE PREPARATION FOR SAFETY ANALYSIS)

- 2.1 Collect the vegetable (leaves and/or fruit) to be analyzed, and cut them in small pieces
- 2.2 Put one or more piece in a beaker and reduce them in even smaller pieces by means of a laboratory spatula
- 2.3 Add 5 ml of deionised water in the beaker. Wait not less then 10 minutes before using the sample for measurements
- 2.4 Repeat for other species to be analyzed

3 INSTRUMENT CALIBRATION

NOTE

1. CALIBRATION IS NECESSARY WHENEVER THE METER IS SWITCHED ON AFTER HAVING BEEN SWITCHED OFF
2. WASHING THE SENSOR WITH THE STANDARD SOLUTION BEFOREHAND MAY PROVIDE MORE ACCURATE CALIBRATION

- 3.1 Wash the sensor with water

- 3.2 Turn On the Instrument. Press the ON/OFF button over 2 seconds to turn on the instrument

3.234 Quality Measurement: Nitrate Ion Meter Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 3.2 Press and hold the MEAS switch for over 3 seconds in the measurement mode to enter the special setting mode. All items appear on the LCD, and then the display changes as shown below.

- 3.3 Press the **CAL** switch until the **CAL** symbol appears.
- 3.4 Press the MEAS switch for 0.5 seconds. This will display the current calibration setting
- 3.5 Press the **CAL** switch for 0.5 seconds to change the calibration setting. Change the setting to Two Point Calibration, this will be indicated by the number 2 as displayed below

- 3.6 Press the **MEAS** switch to apply the setting. The measurement mode is returned
- 3.7 Open the light shield cover and put some drops of the low-concentration standard solution on the flat sensor to cover the entire flat sensor

- 3.8 Close the light shield cover and press the **CAL** switch over 2 seconds
- 3.9 The **CAL** and ☺ symbols will blink and the calibration value will be displayed
- 3.10 Once calibration is complete the **CAL** and ☺ symbols stop blinking and remain steady

3.234 Quality Measurement: Nitrate Ion Meter Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 3.11 After the calibration for low concentration is completed, open the light shield cover to remove the low-concentration standard solution and wipe off moisture on the sensor
- 3.12 Wash the sensor with tap water. Dry with dry wipes
- 3.13 Put some drops of the high-concentration standard solution on the flat sensor to cover the entire flat sensor
- 3.14 Close the light shield cover and press the **CAL** switch for over 2 seconds
- 3.15 The **CAL** and ☺ symbols will blink and the calibration value will be displayed
- 3.16 Once calibration is complete the **CAL** and ☺ symbols stop blinking and remain steady.
- 3.17 Clean the sensor with tap water. Dry with dry wipes
- 3.18 Press the **MEAS** switch for 0.5 seconds to enter the measurement mode and prepare for measurement

4 TAKING MEASUREMENT

Figure 2: Taking Measurement

- 4.1 Verify the instrument is in measurement mode
- 4.2 Open the light shield cover and, by means of the pipetter, put some drops of sample on the flat sensor until it is completely covered
- 4.3 Close the light shield cover

3.234 Quality Measurement: Nitrate Ion Meter Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 4.4 When the ☺ symbol lights up the measurement is completed
- 4.5 To lock the measured value, press the **MEAS** switch for 0.5 seconds
- 4.6 When the **MEAS** and ☺ symbols stop blinking and remain steady the measurement is locked
- 4.7 Clean the sensor with tap water. Dry with dry wipes
- 4.8 If other measurements are required repeat step 4 using other species samples

SS 5 CLOSEOUT

- 5.1 Shutdown the instrument
- 5.2 Clean the beakers, the pipetter and the spatula with tap water
- 5.3 Stow all the items and tools
- 5.4 Waste the unused vegetables samples.

3.300 E-Nose Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Measurement of microbial contamination using the E-Nose

DURATION

TBD

TOOLS

E-Nose

1 Plant Sampler

1 Air Sampler 2 Evolution (modular part of the plant sampler)

1 Transfer Line

1 Stowage Container

6 Filter F1 (Particle Filter)

12 Filter F2 (Humidifier)

Power supply

USB-Cable

WinMuster S/W

ITEMS

Nitrile Gloves

NOTE

1. THE E-NOSE OFFERS TWO DIFFERENT OPERATING OPTIONS (AND THEREFORE TWO DIFFERENT CONFIGURATIONS):
 - THE FIRST OPTION FORESEES THE MEASUREMENT OF CONTAMINANTS ON DIFFERENT SURFACES INSIDE THE FEG.
 - THE SECOND OPTION FORESEES THE MEASUREMENTS OF CONTAMINANTS ON THE PLANTS LEAVES. IN THIS CASE THE AIRSAMPLER HAS TO BE MOUNTED ON THE PLANT SAMPLER
2. E-NOSE OPERATIONS IS COMPOSED OF THREE STEPS
 - DATA ACQUISITION ON THE E-NOSE DEVICE
 - DATA DOWNLOAD VIA USB TO THE CREW LAPTOP (THE **WINMUSTER** S/W SHALL BE PREVIOUSLY INSTALLED ON THE LAPTOP)
 - DATA TRANSFER TO MCC

3.300 E-Nose Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 1: E-NOSE configured for surface measurement

Figure 2: E-NOSE configured for measurement on plant leaves

- MTF 1 SYSTEM SETUP
- 1.1 Retrieve all the items and tools from stowage
- 1.2 Withdraw the "E-NOSE" Device from the Container

3.300 E-Nose Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 1.3 Withdraw Power Cable from the Container and connect it to the 230V power socket on the E-NOSE Device

Figure 3: Transfer Line Connection to E-NOSE Device

- 1.4 Withdraw the Transfer Line from the Container and connect it to the E-Nose

Figure 4: Filter F1 (Particle Filter – Left) and Filter F2 (Humidifier – Right)

- 1.5 Withdraw the filter kit from the container and take one bag with filters from it
- 1.6 Remove both cover caps of the Filter- F2

Figure 5: Filter F2 Connected to the E-NOSE Device

- 1.7 Connect Filter F2 to connector Zero Gas 1 at the rear side of the “E-NOSE” Device

3.300 E-Nose Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 1.8 Connect Filter F1 with Transfer line

If measurements on plants are required

Figure 6: Configuration of the Air Sampler for Measurement on Plants

- 1.9 Mount the Air Sampler on the handle of the Plant Sampler as per Fig. 6

Figure 7: Air Sampler Connected to the Filter 1

- 1.10 Connect the Air Sampler with Filter F1

3.300 E-Nose Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 8: Air Sampler Connected to the Filter 2 (for surface measurement on the left and for leaves measurement on the right)

- 1.11 Connect Filter F2 to the Air Sampler

2 TAKING MEASUREMENTS

NOTE

E-NOSE MEASUREMENT IS DONE OF THREE PHASES :

- SYSTEM INITIALIZATION: AFTER THE ACTIVATION THE E-NOSE IS MANTAINED IN STAND BY FOR 40 MINUTES. DURING THIS TIME THE SYSTEM IS FLUSHED UNTIL IT REACHES A STEADY STATE STATUS
- ENVIRONMENTAL AIR MEASUREMENT. THE AIR SAMPLER IS NOT CONNECTED TO THE SURFACE/PLANT TO BE ANALYSED
- SAMPLE MEASUREMENT. THE AIR SAMPLER IS CONNECTED TO THE SURFACE/PLANT TO BE ANALYSED. DURING THE SAMPLE MEASURMENT A SHORT CONNECTIVITY TEST IS DONE TO VERIFY IF THE FILTER F2 IS CORRECTLY INSTALLED ON THE AIR SAMPLER. IN PARTICULAR AT THE BEGINNING OF THE MEASUREMENT THE INLET OF THE FILTER F2 IS CLOSED WITH A FINGER FOR 2/3 SECONDS. A CHANGE IN THE SIGNAL IS THE PROOF OF A CORRECT CONNECTION. TO AVOID CONTAMINATION GLOVES SHALL BE USED.

- 2.1 Don Nitrile gloves

2.2 System Initialization

- 2.2.1 Activate the E-NOSE Device (On the rear part of the device push the switch "POWER" to ON)
- 2.2.2 Wait until the inialization is completed (the system goes to Standby)

3.300 E-Nose Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Fig. 9: System in STANDBY

2.2.3 On the LCD screen of the E-Nose Device, verify the system is in STANDBY

2.2.4 Wait for 40 minutes

2.3 Environmental Air Measurement

2.3.1 Without connecting the Air Sampler to the surface to be analysed push the button "MEASUREMENT"

Figure 10: Measurement Sequence as shown on the Display

2.3.2 On the E-NOSE Device verify that the sequence Shown in Figure 10 is executed:

- CLEANING SENSORS
- BASELINE TRIM
- CONNECTING VIAL COUNTDOWN
- MEASUREMENT PLOTS APPEARANCE
-

2.3.3 After measurement starts (from plot appearance), wait for TBD time

2.3.4 Verify the E-Nose come back to Stand-By

2.4 Sample Measurement

3.300 E-Nose Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2.4.1 Push the button “MEASUREMENT” and wait for the appearance of the message “CLEANING SENSOR” on the E-NOSE Device Display

Figure 10: Sample Measurement (Surface on the left, plant on the right)

- 2.4.2 Place the Air Sampler on the dedicated surface or plant
- 2.4.3 Verify the sequence of fig.10 is executed. When the “MEASUREMENT” plots appears, wait TBD time, close for 2-3 seconds the Filter 2 on the Air Sampler with a finger, verify that the measurement changes and then remove the finger.
- 2.4.4 Wait TBD time
- 2.4.5 Verify the E-Nose come back to Stand-By

3 MEASUREMENT DATA DOWNLOAD

- 3.1 Connect the USB cable to the E-Nose connector and to the Crew-Notebook
- 3.2 Turn on the Crew-Notebook and start the WinMuster S/W.

(Double Click on)

3.300 E-Nose Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 11: WinMuster SW Main Display

3.3 After the S/W has been started, check the following windows appears

Figure 12: Options popup menu – Search Device Option

3.4 Press "Options" and "Search Devices"

Figure 13: Select Device Display

3.300 E-Nose Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

3.5 Select the device "PEN3" and confirm with "OK". A dialog Window appears

Figure 16: PEN3 Data Window

3.6 Press "Yes"

Figure 15: Options popup menu – PEN 3 option

3.7 Press "Options", "PEN3" and Logdata

Figure 16: PEN3 Data Window

3.8 Find the measurement data in the list

3.9 Choose a folder where the data has to be stored and indicate the measurement files to be downloaded. Press "Load"

3.300 E-Nose Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 17: Dialog Window

3.10 Confirm the Start of the Download by pressing "Yes"

Figure 18: Confirmation Window

3.11 Verify the download is finished

Figure 19: Navigation path

3.12 Press "File", "Measurement" and "Load" to open the downloaded files

3.300 E-Nose Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 20: Record Selection

3.13 Choose one measurement file and press "Open"

Figure 21: Data Analysis Plot

3.14 Check the appearance of the measurement plot (Fig. 21)

3.300 E-Nose Operations

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

3.15 Repeat from step 3.7 for other measurements

4 CLOSEOUT

4.1 Power off the E-NOSE Device (On the rear part of the device push the switch "POWER" to OFF)

4.2 Disconnect the Fliter F2 from the Air Sampler and install the cover caps (2) on it

4.3 Disconnect the Fliter F1 from the Air Sampler

If the E-NOSE has been used for PLANT Measurement

4.4 Dismount the Air Sampler from the Plant Sampler Handle

4.5 Disconnect the Filter F1 from the Transfer Line

4.6 Disconnect the Filter F2 from the E-NOSE Device and install the cover caps(2) on it

4.7 Disconnect the Transfer Line from the E-NOSE Device

4.8 Disconnect the Power Cable from the E-NOSE Device

4.9 Waste the Filters 1and the Filters 2

4.10 Stow the E-Nose device, the power cable and the transfer line

3.310 Sampling for Microbial Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Collection of samples and storage for off-line microbial analysis.

DURATION

TBD

TOOLS

N/A

ITEMS

42 Eppendorf Tubes (2ml)
42 Centrifuge tubes (15ml)
42 Nylon flocked swab with containers
Markers
3 Sterile Nitrile Gloves
Sterile Water (TBD ml)

NOTE

SEVERAL SAMPLES HAVE TO BE COLLECTED BY CREW AS PER THE FOLLOWING SCHEMA:

- 10 LOCATION WITHIN THE FEG
- 6 LOCATION WITHIN THE SERVICE MODULE
- 4 LOCATIONS OF THE ISPR RACK

TWO SAMPLES HAVE TO BE COLLECTED FOR EACH LOCATION.

IN ADDITION TWO OTHER FIELD NEGATIVE CONTROL SAMPLES HAVE TO BE COLLECTED FOR EACH SAMPLING EVENT

Figure 1: Items to be used

3.310 Sampling for Microbial Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

1.1 Collect all the required items and tools

1.2 Carefully wash your hands

1.2 Wear Nitrile Gloves

2 SURFACE SAMPLING

Figure 2: swab preparation

2.1 Remove a sterile swab from its container (Fig.2)

Fig. 3: Swab moisten

3.310 Sampling for Microbial Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

NOTE

A NEW STERILE EPPENDORF TUBE SHALL BE USED FOR A NEW SAMPLING

- 2.2 Moisten the head of the swab using the sterile water in the sterile Eppendorf tube (2 ml) (Fig. 3)

Figure 4: Water Excess removal

- 2.3 Express excess moisture from the swab against the interior wall of the tube (fig. 4)

Figure 5: First swab position

3.310 Sampling for Microbial Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2.4 Hold the swab so that the handle makes about a 30° angle with the surface to be sampled (fig. 5)

Figure 6: Swabbing – step 1

- 2.5 While moving the swab in one direction, rotate the head of the swab slowly and thoroughly over a measured 25 cm² surface area (Fig. 6)

Figure 7: Swabbing – Step 2

3.310 Sampling for Microbial Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2.6 Change the linear direction of the swabbing motion 90° and again swab the surface thoroughly

Figure 8: Swabbing – Step 3

- 2.7 Complete a third coverage of the surface by again changing the direction of the swabbing motion by 135°

Figure 9: Swab preparation for storage

- 2.8 Put the swab in a sterile centrifuge tube (15 ml) containing 2,5 ml sterile water, and break the swab shaft at the breakpoint (Fig. 9)

3.310 Sampling for Microbial Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2.9 Close the tube for storage and label the tube (location/date/time/microbial)
- 2.10 Repeat step 2 for the same location, and then twice for all the locations of the FEG, Service Module and the ISPR Rack

3 FIELD NEGATIVE CONTROL SAMPLE COLLECTION

NOTE

1. TWO FIELD NEGATIVE CONTROL SAMPLES HAVE TO BE COLLECTED FOR COMPARISON PURPOSE, ONE IN THE FEG AND THE OTHER ONE IN THE SERVICE SECTION.
2. THE ACTIVITY IS VERY SIMILAR TO WHAT DONE FOR THE MICROBIAL SAMPLING AS DESCRIBED IN STEP 2, WITH THE ONLY DIFFERENCE THAT THE SWAB WILL BE MOVED THROUGH THE AIR RATHER THAN ON A SOLID SURFACE

- 3.1 Perform step 2.1, 2.1 and 2.3

Figure 10: Swabbing through the air

- 3.2 Wave the moistened swab through the air for 2 to 4 seconds
 - 3.3 Perform steps 2.8, 2.9, 2.10 and 2.11
 - 3.4 Repeat the step 3 until the six sample (two for FEG, two for the Service Module and two for the ISPR Rack have been acquired)
- 4 **CLOSEOUT**
- 4.1 Take off the gloves

3.310 Sampling for Microbial Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 4.1 Store the tube at -18degC)
- 4.2 Document the activity in the log journal
- 4.3 Waste the gloves and the swab sticks

3.311 Sampling for Molecular Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- SS **1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION**
- 1.1 Collect all the required items and tools
- 1.2 Carefully wash your hands
- 1.3 Don Nitrile Gloves
- FEG **2 SURFACE SAMPLING**

Figure 2: swab preparation

- 2.1 Remove a sterile swab from its container (Fig.2)

Fig. 3: Swab moisten

3.311 Sampling for Molecular Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

NOTE

A NEW STERILE EPPENDORF TUBE SHALL BE USED FOR A NEW SAMPLING

- 2.2 Moisten the head of the swab using the sterile water in the sterile Eppendorf tube (2 ml) (Fig. 3)

Figure 4: Water Excess removal

- 2.3 Express excess moisture from the swab against the interior wall of the tube (fig. 4)

Figure 5: First swab position

3.311 Sampling for Molecular Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2.4 Hold the swab so that the handle makes about a 30° angle with the surface to be sampled (fig. 5)

Figure 6: Swabbing – step 1

- 2.5 While moving the swab in one direction, rotate the head of the swab slowly and thoroughly over a measured 25 cm² surface area (Fig. 6)

Figure 7: Swabbing – Step2

3.311 Sampling for Molecular Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2.6 Change the linear direction of the swabbing motion 90° and again swab the surface thoroughly

Figure 8: Swabbing – Step 3

- 2.7 Complete a third coverage of the surface by again changing the direction of the swabbing motion by 135°

Figure 9: Swab preparation for storage

- 2.8 Put the swab back in its container

3.311 Sampling for Molecular Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2.9 Close the tube for storage and label the tube (location/date/time/microbial)
- 2.10 Repeat step 2 for all the locations of the FEG and then and then twice for all the locations of the Service Module and the ISPR Rack

FEG 3 FIELD NEGATIVE CONTROL SAMPLE COLLECTION

NOTE

1. TWO FIELD NEGATIVE CONTROL SAMPLES HAVE TO BE COLLECTED for COMPARISON PURPOSE, ONE IN THE FEG AND THE OTHER IN THE SERVICE SECTION.
2. THE SAMPLING IS VERY SIMILAR TO THE MICROBIAL SAMPLING AS DESCRIBED IN STEP 2, WITH THE ONLY DIFFERENCE THAT THE SWAB WILL BE MOVED THROUGH THE AIR RATHER THAN ON A SOLID SURFACE

- 3.1 Perform step 2.1, 2.1 and 2.3

Figure 10: Swabbing through the air

- 3.2 Wave the moistened swab through the air for 2 to 4 seconds
- 3.3 Perform steps 2.8, 2.9 and 2.10
- 3.4 Repeat the step 3 in the Service Module
- 4 **CLOSEOUT**
- 4.1 Doff and waste the gloves
- 4.1 Document the activity in the log journal

3.311 Sampling for Molecular Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

4.2 Store the tube at -18degC

3.312 Plant Sampling For Microbial and Molecular Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Collection of plant samples and storage for off-line microbial and molecular analysis.

DURATION

TBD

TOOLS

N/A

ITEMS

40 Centrifuge Tubes (50ml) for sample

4 Centrifuge Tubes (50ml) for control (with tissue)

44 Tweezers

44 Scalpel

Markers

3 Sterile Nitrile Gloves

NOTE

1. FOUR SAMPLES PER PLANT (10 PLANTS IN TOTAL) HAVE TO BE COLLECTED BY CREW. TWO SAMPLES WILL BE USED FOR MICROBIAL AND 2 SAMPLES FOR MOLECULAR ANALYSIS.
2. FOR EACH SAMPLING EVENT 4 OTHER FIELD NEGATIVE CONTROL SAMPLES HAVE TO BE COLLECTED
3. EACH SAMPLING REQUIRES THE USE OF A NEW TWEEZER AND A NEW SCALPEL

Figure 1: Items to be used

3.312 Plant Sampling For Microbial and Molecular Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- SS 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION**
- 1.1 Collect all the required items and tools
 - 1.2 Carefully wash your hands
 - 1.3 Wear Nitrile Gloves
- FEG 2 PLANT SAMPLING**
- 2.1 Remove a sterile scalpel from its pouch
 - 2.2 Remove sterile tweezers from its pouch

Fig.2: Plant Sample Cutting

Figure 3: Plant Sample Insertion in the Tube

3.312 Plant Sampling For Microbial and Molecular Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2.3 Grab a leaf (or another plant part) with tweezers (Fig. 2)
- 2.4 Cut the plant part with the scalpel (Fig. 2)
- 2.5 Put the plant part into a centrifuge tubes (50 ml) (Fig. 3)
- 2.6 Close the tube for storage
- 2.7 Label the tube unambiguously
- 2.8 Repeat step 2 for another sample (same plant)
- 2.9 Repeat step 2 for another plant until all the plants samples have been collected.

3 FIELD NEGATIVE CONTROL SAMPLE COLLECTION

- 3.1 Remove a sterile scalpel from its pouch
- 3.2 Remove sterile tweezers from its pouch

Figure 4: Tissue removal from its tube

3.312 Plant Sampling For Microbial and Molecular Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 5: Piece of tissue cutting

- 3.3 Remove the piece of tissue with tweezers from its tube (50 ml) (fig. 4)
 - 3.4 Cut the piece of tissue with the scalpel (fig. 5)
 - 3.5 Put the piece of tissue back to its tube
 - 3.6 Close the tube for storage
 - 3.7 Label the tube unambiguously
 - 3.8 Repeat step 3 other three times (four samples to be collected in total)
- 4 CLOSEOUT**
- 4.1 Take off the gloves and waste them
 - 4.1 Document the activity in the log journal (date location sample number, etc.)
 - 4.2 Store the tube at -18degC

3.313 Liquid Sampling For Microbial and Molecular Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Collection of nutrient solution samples and storage for off-line microbial and molecular analysis

DURATION

TBD

TOOLS

N/A

ITEMS

4 Centrifuge Tubes (50ml)

Sterile Nitrile Gloves

NOTE

TWO SAMPLES PER THANK (2 THANKS) HAVE TO BE COLLECTED BY CREW. TWO SAMPLES WILL BE USED FOR MICROBIAL AND 2 SAMPLES FOR MOLECULAR ANALYSIS.

Figure 1: Items to be used

SS 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

NOTE

TO PREVENT CONTAMINATION THE HANDS HAVE TO BE CLEAN AND STERILE GLOVES SHALL BE WEARED BEFORE THE START OF THE OPERATIONS

- 1.1 Collect all the required items and tools
- 1.2 Carefully wash your hands
- 1.3 Don Nitrile Gloves

3 LIQUID SAMPLING

3.313 Liquid Sampling For Microbial and Molecular Analysis (EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 2: Bulk Solution Tank Cover

- 3.1 Remove the Bulk Solution Tank Panel.
Remark. It is not necessary to unscrew the bolts. They are just used to align the Tank Panel.

Figure 2: Liquid Sampling

- 3.2 Fill the centrifuge tubes (50 ml) with 30 - 40 ml of the nutrient solution
- 3.2 Close the tube for storage and label it with the following information:
- Tank Number (1 or 2)
 - Type of analysis (microbial or molecular)
 - Date (yyyy.mm.dd)

3.313 Liquid Sampling For Microbial and Molecular Analysis

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

3.3 Document date, location, sample number etc. in the journal

3.4 Store the tube at -18degC

4 CLOSEOUT

4.1 Reinstall the Bulk Solution Tank Panel.

4.2 Restow the tools and the items

3.312 TransMADD Decontamination

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE/HC)

OBJECTIVE

Decontaminate the FEG and/or the entire MTF in case microbial contaminations is detected

DURATION

120 minutes

TOOLS

Diop Generator

Nozzle

ITEMS

Bottle holder

Bottle for the agent

Tube adapter (2)

Tube (3 meter)

Power cable

Decontamination Agent

NOTE

THE TRANSMADD OFFERS TWO DIFFERENT OPERATING OPTIONS (AND THEREFORE TWO DIFFERENT CONFIGURATIONS):

- THE FIRST OPTION IS STORING THE DECONTAMINATION AGENT INSIDE THE GENERATOR, AND THE NOZZLE IS MOUNTED ON THE DIOP GENERATOR AND THE DECONTAMINATION AGENT IS DIRECTLY VAPORIZED BY THE NOZZLE. IN THIS CASE THE ENTIRE SYSTEM IS PLACED IN THE ROOM TO BE DECONTAMINATED,
- THE SECOND OPTION IS STORING THE DISINFECTION AGENT IN A SMALLER BOTTLE FIXED IN A FLASK HOLDER. THE DECONTAMINATION AGENT IS CONDUCTED BY A TUBE TO THE NOZZLE. IN THIS SECOND CASE THE ONLY BOTTLE AND THE NOZZLE ARE PLACED IN THE ROOM TO BE DECONTAMINATED.

3.312 TransMADD Decontamination

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE/HC)

Figure 1: Decontamination Items: two configurations

1 SYSTEM SETUP – CONFIGURATION 1

NOTE

THE BOTTLE HOLDER AND THE BOTTLE FOR THE AGENT ARE NOT REQUIRED FOR THIS CONFIGURATION

Figure 2: Configuration 1: System placed inside the FEG

1.1 Destow the tools and items from their stowage location

3.312 TransMADD Decontamination

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE/HC)

- 1.2 Install the nozzle on the Diop generator
- 1.3 Fill the Diop generator tank with the selected decontaminant agent
- 1.4 Place the system in the middle of the FEG in an elevated position (could be on a chair or on the trolley)
- 1.5 Attach the power cable to the Diop Generator
- 1.6 GOTO step 3

2 SYSTEM SETUP – CONFIGURATION 2

NOTE

ALL THE ITEMS AND TOOLS ARE REQUIRED FOR THIS CONFIGURATION

Figure 3: Configuration 2 – Nozzle in the FEG and Diop in the SS

- 2.1 Destow the tools and items from their stowage location

3.312 TransMADD Decontamination

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE/HC)

Figure 4: Suction Valve Installed on the bottle

- 2.2 Fill the bottle with the selected decontaminant agent
- 2.3 Install the bottle into the bottle holder and install the suction valve (Fig.4)

Fig. 5: Nozzle connected to the suction valve

- 2.4 Connect the suction valve to the nozzle and place the nozzle in the bottle holder

Fig. 6: Tube connected

- 2.5 Install the tube adapter on the nozzle and on the Diop generator

3.312 TransMADD Decontamination

(EDEN ISS/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE/HC)

- 2.6 Install the tube
- 2.7 Place the system nozzle/bottle in the middle of the FEG in an elevated position (could be on a chair or on the trolley). The Diop has to be left in the SS
- 2.8 Exit from the FEG and close the door

3 DECONTAMINATION EXECUTION

WARNING
NO PERSONS SHALL STAY INSIDE THE ROOM TO BE DECONTAMINATED DURING THE TRANSMADD OPERATIONS.

- 3.1 Check that no persons are inside the FEG
- 3.2 Adjust the Diosol Generator to the appropriate volume (for the FEG 70 m³ tbc)
- 3.3 Turn off the Air Management System and the Air Circulation Fan inside the FEG
- 3.4 Activate the Diop. Push the power switch to position "I". (If you are in the FEG, leave it within 30 sec. and close the door)
- 3.5 Put on the door a security sign with the following words: "DO NOT OPEN, DECONTAMINATION IN PROGRESS"
- 3.6 Wait 90 minutes until the end of the decontamination operations. Deactivate the Diop (Push the power switch to position "O").
- 3.7 Turn On the Air Management System and the Air Circulation Fan inside the FEG
- 3.8 Open the door and assure air circulation for the following 30 minutes. Do not enter in the FEG during this time.
- 3.9 When the 30 minutes have expired, enter in the FEG and retriev the system nozzle/bottle.

4 CLOSEOUT

- 4.1 Deconfigure the system as required
- 4.2 Stow all the items and tools

4200 Nutrient Distribution System Bulk Solution Tank Refill

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

OBJECTIVE

Changing the Hydroponic Nutrient Solution in Tank X (where tank X implies NDS bulk solution rack tank 1 or 2)

DURATION

120 min (TBC)

TOOLS

N/A

ITEMS

Fresh Water Canisters (20 litre tank)

Waste Water Canisters (20 litre tank)

Stock Solution A (4 litre bottle)

Stock Solution B (4 litre bottle)

Acid Solution (4 litre bottle)

Base Solution (4 litre bottle)

Bleach

Clean Beaker

Protective Glasses

Protective Mask

Protective Gloves

Lab Coat/Coveralls

Blue Tissue

Mikrozyd Tissue

Karcher Suction Pump with its drain tube

Plastic Tank for waste water

NOTE

THIS PROCEDURE APPLIES TO BOTH THE BULK SOLUTION TANK #1 AND THE BULK SOLUTION TANK #2. IN FACT, EVEN IF THEY COULD BE FILLED WITH TWO DIFFERENT NUTRIENT SOLUTIONS, THE OPERATION TO DO THAT IS THE SAME FOR THE TWO TANKS.

- SS 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION**
1.1 Retrieve the items and tools

WARNING

1. POTENTIAL ELECTRICAL SHOCK HAZARD: THE ACTIVITIES HAVE TO BE DONE WITH THE NDS COMPONENT OFF
2. POTENTIAL CHEMICAL HAZARD: THE OPERATOR MUST WEAR INDIVIDUAL PROTECTIVE ITEMS (LAB COAT/COVERALLS, GLOVES, GLASSES AND MASK) DURING THE OPERATIONS

4200 Nutrient Distribution System Bulk Solution Tank Refill (EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

Figure 1: LED Lighting System Display – Main Page

1.2 On the LED Lighting System Display (Fig. 1)

Cmd the LED Panel Units (All) to Manual Off

Figure 2: Nutrient Delivery System Display – Irrigation Equipment Control

1.3 In the Irrigation Equipment Control Display

Turn **OFF** all high pressure aeroponic pumps fed from Tank 1(2) (Fig. 2):

4200 Nutrient Distribution System Bulk Solution Tank Refill

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

- Cmd HP1 Pump to Manual Off**
- Cmd HP2 Pump to Manual Off**
- Cmd HP3 Pump to Manual Off**
- Cmd HP4 Pump to Manual Off**
- Cmd HP5 Pump to Manual Off**
- Cmd HP6 Pump to Manual Off**
- Cmd HP7 Pump to Manual Off**
- Cmd HP8 Pump to Manual Off**

TANK 1 EQUIPMENT CONTROL

	BULK NS TANK 1 CONTROLS	Dosing Status	0.00 %
EC Setpoint	2.20 mS	A Dosing Pump Manual Off	Off 0 %
pH Setpoint	5.90 pH	B Dosing Pump Manual Off	Off 0 %
		Filling Status	100.00 %
	SOLENOID FW TANK 1	Manual Off	Off 0 %
	REC PUMP TANK 1	Manual Off	Off 0 %

SHARED TANK EQUIPMENT CONTROL

	ACID DOSING PUMP	Manual Off	Off 0 %
	ACID SOLENOID	Manual Off	Off 0 %
	BASE DOSING PUMP	Manual Off	Off 0 %
	BASE SOLENOID	Manual Off	Off 0 %
	PUMP FW	Manual Off	Off 0 %
	OZONE GENERATOR	Manual Off	Off 0 %

Figure 3: Nutrient Delivery System Display – Tanks Equipment Control

1.4 Turn OFF the Tanks Actuators (fig. 3):

In Tank 1(2) Equipment Control Display

- Cmd A Dosing Pump to Manual Off**
- Cmd B Dosing Pump to Manual Off**
- Cmd Solenoid FW Tank 1(2) to Manual Off**
- Cmd Rec Pump Tank 1(2) to Manual Off**

In Shared Tank Equipment Control box

- Cmd Acid Dosing Pump to Manual Off**
- Cmd Acid Solenoid to Manual Off**
- Cmd Base Dosing Pump to Manual Off**
- Cmd Base Solenoid to Manual Off**
- Cmd Pump FW to Manual Off**
- Cmd Ozone Generator to Manual Off**

4200 Nutrient Distribution System Bulk Solution Tank Refill

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

Figure 4: Power Rack Interface – NDS Service Section Line

- 1.5 On the Power Rack Interface – NDS Service Section Line (Fig. 4)

Switch OFF the Air Pump 1
Switch OFF the Air Pump 2
Switch OFF the Circ Pump 1
Switch OFF the Circ Pump 2

2 OLD BULK SOLUTION REMOVAL

Figure 5: NDS Rack – Bulk Solution Tank 2

- 2.1 Remove the Lid Panel from the Bulk Solution Tank 1(2) (Fig. 5)
- 2.2 Pull out the EC and pH sensors from the Bulk Solution Tank and lay them on the top of the Bulk Solution Tank with the Lid Panel.
Remark: There is no need to feed the sensor and sensor cables out from the Lid Panel

4200 Nutrient Distribution System Bulk Solution Tank Refill

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

- 2.3 Wash the sensors with fresh water and then place them in clean beaker with water to clean and prevent drying of sensors

Remark: The bolts are used to align the cover - no need to unscrew them

Figure 6: Drain Pipeline (Left) and Karcher Pump (Right)

Figure 7: Drain Valve position

- 2.4 Collect sufficient 20 L waste water bottles near the NDS drain pipeline subfloor access location
- 2.5 Lift the left floor panel in front of the ISPR Rack to access the Drain Pipeline (Fig. 6 – Left)
- 2.6 Wear appropriate Personal Protective Equipment (Gloves, Mask and Glasses)
- 2.7 Connect the drain tube to the outlet port of the Karcher Pump
- 2.8 Connect the Drain Pipeline to the inlet port of the Karcher Pump (Fig. 6 – Right)
- 2.9 Insert the free end of the drain tube in the first waste water canister.

4200 Nutrient Distribution System Bulk Solution Tank Refill

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

- 2.10 Open Tank 1(2) Drain Valve (Fig. 7)
- 2.12 Turn On the Karcher Pump
- 2.13 Wait until the 20 L waste water canister is almost filled.
- 2.14 Turn off the Karcher Pump.
- 2.15 Remove the free end of the drain tube from the waste water canister and close the canister lid.
- 2.16 Repeat the process filling subsequent waste water canisters (i.e. from step AA until step BB) until the respective NDS tank is empty.

3 BULK SOLUTION TANK 1(2) CLEANING

- 3.1 Clean all inside surfaces (including recirculation pump, thermal coil, and pipes) by hand with blue tissue first.
- 3.2 Repeat cleaning, this time with Mikrozyd tissues and blue tissues
- 3.3 Rinse inside with fresh water using hose (to remove any particles left on the surfaces)

Figure 8: Mesh Filters Valve (located below the NDS Tank)

- 3.4 **Close** Tank 1(2) outlet valve at Filter
- 3.5 **Turn On** the Karcher Pump again
- 3.6 Wait until the all the water in the tank is drained (Push with tissue if needed to remove as much as possible) then **Turn Off** the Karcher Pump.
- 3.7 Fill Tank 1(2) with water until level reaches above cooling coil
- 3.8 Add bleach – approximately 100 ml – does not have to be measured exactly
- 3.9 On the Power Rack Interface – NDS Service Section Line (Fig. 4)

4200 Nutrient Distribution System Bulk Solution Tank Refill

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

Switch ON the Circ Pump 1

Switch ON the Circ Pump 2

3.10 In Tank 1(2) Equipment Control box

Cmd Rec Pump Tank 1(2) to Manual On

3.11 Wait 1 minute (TBC) to have the bleach mixed with water (the recirculation pump will be also cleaned inside) then

Cmd Rec Pump Tank 1(2) to Manual Off

3.12 **Turn On** the Karcher Pump again

3.13 Wait until the all the bleached water in the tank is drained (Push with tissue if needed to remove as much as possible) then **Turn Off** the Karcher Pump.

3.14 Fill again the tank 1(2) with water until level reaches above cooling coil.

3.15 **Turn On** the Karcher Pump again

3.16 Wait until the all the bleached water in the tank is drained, then **Turn Off** the Karcher Pump.

4 FEED LINES CLEANING

4.1 Carefully remove Mesh Filter (Fig. 8), using a beaker or bowl to capture leaked water

4.2 Wash it and reinstall in its position

4.3 Fill Tank 1(2) with a little bit of Water

4.4 **Open** Outlet valve of Tank 1(2) at Filter

4.5 In the Irrigation Equipment Control Display

Turn **OFF** all high pressure aeroponic pumps fed from Tank 1(2) (Fig. 2):

Cmd HP1 Pump to Manual On

Cmd HP2 Pump to Manual On

Cmd HP3 Pump to Manual On

Cmd HP4 Pump to Manual On

Cmd HP5 Pump to Manual On

Cmd HP6 Pump to Manual On

Cmd HP7 Pump to Manual On

Cmd HP8 Pump to Manual On

4.6 Wait for 1 spray from Return Line to clean feed and return lines.

if Return pump not sprays for a while

4200 Nutrient Distribution System Bulk Solution Tank Refill

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

add more water to return lines to active Return Pump

4.7 In the Irrigation Equipment Control Display

Turn **OFF** all high pressure aeroponic pumps fed from Tank 1(2) (Fig. 2)

Cmd HP1 Pump to **Manual Off**

Cmd HP2 Pump to **Manual Off**

Cmd HP3 Pump to **Manual Off**

Cmd HP4 Pump to **Manual Off**

Cmd HP5 Pump to **Manual Off**

Cmd HP6 Pump to **Manual Off**

Cmd HP7 Pump to **Manual Off**

Cmd HP8 Pump to **Manual Off**

5 FINAL CLEANING OF THE BULK SOLUTION TANK 1(2) AND ADDITIONAL CHECKS

5.1 Fill Tank 1(2) with a little fresh water once again

5.2 **Turn On** the Karcher Pump again

5.3 Wait until the all the water in the tank is drained then **Turn Off** the Karcher Pump.

5.4 Repeat step 5 twice to clear tank 1(2) of any leftover particulate

5.5 Close the Tank 1(2) Drain Valve (Fig. 7)

5.6 Verify the fresh water tank is filled

If the tank is empty than fill it. **PERFORM** Procedure “4.300 Fresh Water Tank Filling”

5.7 Verify the waste water is empty

If the tank is filled than empty it. **PERFORM** Procedure “4.310 Waste Water Tank Emptying”

4200 Nutrient Distribution System Bulk Solution Tank Refill

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

Figure 9: NDS Rack – Stock, Acid and Base Solution Tank 2

- 5.8 Check the level of the Stock, Acid and Base Solution in the related tanks (Fig. 9). If necessary refill them.

6 NUTRIENT SOLUTION REFILL

- 6.1 Fill Bulk Solution Tank 1(2) to about half way up with fresh water
- 6.2 Slowly dump into the Bulk Solution Tank 1(2) the pre-made 4 L Stock solution A (B)

NOTE

- ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY SETUP.** EC TARGET VALID PARAMETERS ARE:
 - Leafy Crops: 2.3 +/- 0.2 mS/cm²
 - Fruit Crops: 3.5 +/- 0.2 mS/cm²
- pH Setup.** pH TARGET VALID PARAMETERS ARE FROM 5.2 TO 6.5

Fig. 10: pH and EC transmitters

4200 Nutrient Distribution System Bulk Solution Tank Refill

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

- 6.3 While watching the EC values (Fig. 10) acquired by means of the removed EC sensor, slowly add fresh water into the NDS tank (1/2) until the EC value is close to the required range
- 6.4 Reinstall the lid panel on the Bulk Solution Tank 1(2)
- 6.5 Reinstall the EC sensor in the Bulk Solution Tank 1(2) lid panel
- 6.6 Take off the protective gloves, mask and glasses
- 6.7 On the Power Rack Interface – NDS Service Section Line (Fig. 3)

Switch ON the Air Pump 1
Swicth ON the Air Pump 2

Figure 11: Nutrient Delivery System Display – Tanks Equipment Control. NDS Configuration

- 6.9 Turn ON the Tanks Actuators and input the EC and pH Setpoints (Fig. 11):

In Tank 1(2) Equipment Control Control box

Input EC Setpoint = as required
Input pH Setpoint = as required

Cmd A Dosing Pump to **Automatic**
Cmd B Dosing Pump to **Automatic**
Cmd Solenoid FW Tank 1(2) to **Automatic**
Cmd Rec Pump Tank 1(2) to **Automatic**

4200 Nutrient Distribution System Bulk Solution Tank Refill

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

In Shared Tank Equipment Control box

Cmd Acid Dosing Pump to **Automatic**

Cmd Acid Solenoid to **Automatic**

Cmd Base Dosing Pump to **Automatic**

Cmd Base Solenoid to **Automatic**

Cmd Pump FW to **Automatic**

Cmd Ozone Generator to **Automatic**

- 6.10 After 30 minutes, verify on the pH and EC transmitters that the pH and the EC have been adjusted to the defined target

If the EC and/or the pH are out of range

PERFORM procedure 5.600 NDS pH and EC Setting Failure

NOTE

1. EACH OF THE EIGHT NDS RACKS CAN BE SET TO RECEIVE NUTRIENT SOLUTION FROM EITHER TANK 1 OR TANK 2. TO CHANGE THE SOURCE SOLUTION, BOTH THE FEED VALVE AND THE RETURN VALVE MUST BE SWITCHED TO THE APPROPRIATE TANK. TO CHANGE THE FEED VALVE FOR ANY RACK, REFER TO THE DIAGRAM OF VALVE POSITION (FIG. 9)

Figure 12: NDS feed tank valve positions

THE CORRESPONDING WASTE VALVE MUST ALSO BE CHANGED. REFER TO THE VALVE DIAGRAM BELOW FOR THE CORRECT POSITIONING OF THE VALVE HANDLE.

4200 Nutrient Distribution System Bulk Solution Tank Refill

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

Figure 13: NDS waste valve position

2. CREW WILL BE INSTRUCTED BY **MCC** ON THE VALVE CONFIGURATION BEFORE THE ACTIVITY STARTS
3. THE VALVES ARE UNDER THE FEG FLOOR. THE FEG FLOOR HAS TO BE REMOVED TO ACCESS THEM

6.11 Configure the NDS feed tank valve position as required (example in fig. 12)

6.12 Configure the Waste valve position as required (example in fig. 13)

Figure 14: Nutrient Delivery System Display – Irrigation Equipment Control Configuration

6.13 Turn **ON** all high pressure aeroponic pumps fed from Tank 1(2) (Fig. 14):

In the Irrigation Equipment Control box

- Cmd L1 HP Pump to **Automatic**
- Cmd L2 HP Pump to **Automatic**
- Cmd L3 HP Pump to **Automatic**
- Cmd L4 HP Pump to **Automatic**
- Cmd R1 HP Pump to **Automatic**

4200 Nutrient Distribution System Bulk Solution Tank Refill

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

Cmd R2 HP Pump to **Automatic**
 Cmd R3 HP Pump to **Automatic**
 Cmd R4 HP Pump to **Automatic**

7 CLOSEOUT

- 7.1 Disconnect the Drain Pipeline to the inlet port of the Karcher Pump (Fig. 6 – Right)
- 7.2 Disconnect the drain tube to the outlet port of the Karcher Pump
- 7.3 Remove the the free end of the drain tube from the Waste Plastic Tank

Fig. 15: LED Lighting System Display – Main Page

- 7.4 On the LED Lighting System Display
 Cmd LED Panel Unit (All) to Automatic (Fig. 15)
- 7.5 Stow items and tools

4.220 NDS Sensors Calibration

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Calibrate the pH and the EC probes.

DURATION

120 min (TBC)

TOOLS

N/A

ITEMS

250 ml beakers (5)

Large rinse bucket

Deionised Water

pH 4.0 solution

pH 7.0 solution

pH 10.0 solution

1,413 μ s solution

12,880 μ s solution

Dry wipe

NOTE

1. TWO PH SENSORS AND TWO EC SENSORS ARE INSTALLED FOR EACH BULK SOLUTION TANK, FOR A TOTAL OF 4 pH SENSORS AND 4 EC SENSORS TO BE CALIBRATED
2. THE SENSORS ARE DIRECTLY CONNECTED TO THEIR TRANSMITTERS BOARD WHOSE SETUP IN THE NDS SYSTEM, I.E. CONNECTION TO ARGUS AND TO SENSORS, HAS BEEN DONE AS PART OF SYSTEM INTEGRATION
3. SENSORS CALIBRATION IS DONE VIA TRANSMITTER BOARD INTERFACES.

4.220 NDS Sensors Calibration

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 1: pH and EC sensors in the Bulk Solution Tank 2 (Right)

- SS 1 **ACTIVITY PREPARATION**
- 1.1 Retrieve the items and tools
- 1.2 Deactivate the pH and EC Control

In Tank 1(2) Equipment Control box

Cmd A Dosing Pump to Manual Off
Cmd B Dosing Pump to Manual Off
Cmd Solenoid FW Tank 1(2) to Manual Off
Cmd Rec Pump Tank 1(2) to Manual Off

In Shared Tank Equipment Control box

Cmd Acid Dosing Pump to Manual Off
Cmd Acid Solenoid to Manual Off
Cmd Base Dosing Pump to Manual Off
Cmd Base Solenoid to Manual Off
Cmd Pump FW to Manual Off
Cmd Ozone Generator to Manual Off

4.220 NDS Sensors Calibration

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

SS 2 pH PROBES CALIBRATION

NOTE

1. The pH SENSOR USES A THREE POINT CALIBRATION. THREE STANDARDS ARE REQUIRED FOR PROPER CALIBRATION OF THE pH UNITS AND CONSIST OF pH 4.0, 7.0 AND 10.0 SOLUTIONS
2. THE PROCEDURE IS WRITTEN FOR A GENERIC TANK X, BUT OF COURSE IS APPLICABLE TO BOTH THE TANKS

- 2.1 Remove the probe to be calibrated from the Bulk Solution Tank X and rinse with deionized (or equivalent)
- 2.2 Place the probe in pH 7.0 calibration solution and ensure the end of the probe is completely submerged

Figure 2: pH Calibration Buttons on the pH Transmitter Boards

- 2.3 On the pH Transmitter Board
 1. Press and hold the button marked "7.0" for 1.5 seconds. The display will flash: CAL 7.0
- 2.4 Wait until the display will flash: done
- 2.5 Remove the probe from the calibration solution and rinse with deionized water (or equivalent)
- 2.6 If required
 - repeat step 2.3 to 2.5 for pH 4.0 and pH 10.0
- 2.7 Reinstall the pH Sensors in the Bulk Solution Tank X
- 2.8 If required
 - repeat step 2.1 to 2.6 for the other Bulk Solution Tank

3 EC PROBE CALIBRATION

NOTE

1. THE CONDUCTIVITY SENSOR USES A 3 POINT CALIBRATION: DRY, LOW AND HIGH. THE FIRST CALIBRATION POINT IS "DRY" AND THIS IS ONLY PERFORMED WHEN A NEW PROBE

4.220 NDS Sensors Calibration

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- IS CONNECTED TO THE TRANSMITTER FOR THE FIRST TIME. THE OTHER TWO CALIBRATION POINTS ARE PRESET TO SPECIFIC INDUSTRY STANDARD CALIBRATION VALUES. TO ACCOUNT FOR POSSIBLY HIGHER EC LEVELS, THE PROBES USED IN THE EDEN SYSTEM ARE MIDRANGE WITH A CALIBRATION CONSTANT OF $K=1$.
2. THE STANDARDS REQUIRED FOR CALIBRATION ARE $1,413\mu\text{S}$ AND $12,880\mu\text{S}$.

3.1 Dry Calibration

NOTE

DRY PROBE CALIBRATION IS ANALOGOUS TO THE TARE FUNCTION ON A SCALE. AFTER DRY CALIBRATION THE DISPLAYED CONDUCTIVITY SHOULD BE 0.

- 3.1.1 Remove the probe from the nutrient tank, rinse with deionized water (or equivalent) and then dry it off

Figure 3: EC Calibration Buttons on the EC Transmitter Boards

- 3.1.2 On the EC Transmitter Board

Press and hold the dry calibration button for 1.5 seconds. The screen will display “dry” during the calibration

- 3.1.3 Wait until the screen will display "DONE"

3.2 Low and High Calibration

- 3.2.1 If not already done

Remove the probe from the nutrient tank and rinse with deionized water (or equivalent)

- 3.2.2 Place the probe in the $1,413\mu\text{S}$ solution. Ensure that the bottom of the probe is completely submersed)

- 3.2.3 Wait until the conductivity readings stabilize

- 3.2.4 Press and hold the low calibration button for 1.5 seconds. The screen will display “Low” during calibration

4.220 NDS Sensors Calibration

(EDEN ISS/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 3.2.5 Wait until the screen will display "DONE"

- 3.2.6 Remove the probe from the calibration solution and rinse with deionized water (or equivalent)

- 3.2.7 If required
repeat from step 3.2.2 to step 3.2.5 for the 12,880 µs solution

- 3.2.8 Reinstall the EC Sensors in the Bulk Solution Tank X

- 3.2.9 If required
repeat step 3.1 and then from step 3.2.2 to step 3.2.5 for the other Bulk Solution Tank

4 CLOSEOUT

4.1 Re-activate the pH and EC Control

In Tank 1(2) Equipment Control box

Cmd A Dosing Pump to Automatic

Cmd B Dosing Pump to Automatic

Cmd Solenoid FW Tank 1(2) to Automatic

Cmd Rec Pump Tank 1(2) to Automatic

In Shared Tank Equipment Control box

Cmd Acid Dosing Pump to Automatic

Cmd Acid Solenoid to Automatic

Cmd Base Dosing Pump to Automatic

Cmd Base Solenoid to Automatic

Cmd Pump FW to Automatic

Cmd Ozone Generator to Automatic

4.2 Stow the tools and items

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

OBJECTIVE

Perform the proper mechanical configuration of the Rack during the commissioning phase (HW setup, drawer mechanical blocks removal, cabling installation etc.)

DURATION

90 minutes (TBC)

TOOLS

M 2,5 Allen Key
10 mm wrench
Philips head Screw driver

ITEMS

Protective Nitrile Gloves

Dry wipes

Ziplock Bag

Permanent marker

Kapton Tape

"Cooling Inlet Purge" ON / OFF valve

"Cooling Outlet Purge" ON / OFF valve

Pressure Sensor Gauges (4)

CO₂ Bottles

Concentrated nutrient tanks (3)

Fresh Water Tank

Flexible Hoses for the GCS Connection/Air Management System to the Cooling System (4)

- "GCS THC-SX Inlet Cooling Water" (1)
- "GCS THC-DX Inlet Cooling Water" (1)
- "GCS THC SX and DX Outlet Cooling Water" (1)
- "GCS CO₂ inlet" (1x)

Flexible Hoses for the GCT Connection/Air Management System to the Cooling System (4)

- "GCT THC-SX Inlet Cooling Water" (1)
- "GCT THC-DX Inlet Cooling Water" (1)
- "GCT THC SX and DX Outlet Cooling Water" (1)
- "GCT CO₂ inlet" (1)

Flexible Hoses for the Illumination Drawers Connection to the Cooling System (4)

- "COOL ILL IN" (1)
- "COOL ILL OUT" (1)
- "COOL ILR IN" (1)
- "COOL ILR OUT" (1)

Flexible Hoses for the GCS Connection to the NDS (2)

- GCS to NDS Condensate line (1)
- NDS to GCS Nutrient Solution Line (1)

Flexible Hoses for the GCT Connection to the NDS (2)

- GCT to NDS Condensate line (1)
- NDS to GCT Nutrient Solution Line (1)

Data Cables for the connection of the PCDH to the Illumination Drawers (2)

Data Cables for the connection of the PCDH to the GCT and GCS (4 cables with 1 connector on one side and two connectors on the other side)

Data cable for the connection of the PCDH to the NDS (1)

Data cable for the connection of the PCDH to the MUM Right Panel (4, including 1 USB cable)

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

SS 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

NOTE
ALL THE REQUIRED ITEMS AND TOOLS, AND THE SPARE PARTS ARE AVAILABLE AT NMIII
IN ANTARCTICA AND ARE CORRECTLY LABELLED AND STOWED

1.1 Retrieve the tools and the items from stowage

Figure 1: EDEN ISS Rack fluidic/electrical interfaces located on ILL, ILR and upper side of GCS/GCT

Figure 2 Drawers Mechanical fixation tool

1.2 Remove Kapton Tape from the fluidic / electrical interface of EDEN ISS Rack. See Figure 1 and Figure 2

1.3 Remove Mechanical fixation tool placed on EDEN ISS Rack to avoid accidental drawer opening during shipment to NMIII in Antarctica. See Figure 2

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

2 ISPR CONNECTION TO THE MTF SERVICES

NOTE

THE MTF PROVIDES SEVERAL SERVICES TO THE ISPR RACK:

- POWER
- COOLING
- DATA

TO ACCESS THESE SERVICE THE RACK HAS TO BE CONNECTED TO THE DEDICATED MTF INTERFACES PLACED BENEATH THE MTF FLOOR CLOSE TO THE ISPR RACK. THESE INTERFACES ARE AVAILABLE AS CABLES AND HOSES ALREADY INSTALLED ON THE MTF CONNECTORS AND PROPERLY LABELLED

Figure 3 Main Utility Module (MUM) locations

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

Figure 4 MUM Lower panel configuration

Figure 5: PCDH Panel – VGA Connector

- 2.1 Retrieve the empty ziplock bag. Label it “CAPS REMOVED FROM THE ISPR MUM”
- 2.2 Remove the floor panels in front of the ISPR Rack to access the MTF power and water lines
- 2.3 On the Main Utility Module (MUM) – Lower Panel , Remove the cap from “Hot H₂O to MTF” QD fitting (see Figure 4) and put it in the Ziplock Bag
- 2.4 Connect “Hot H₂O to MTF” to the proper MTF fluidic line (stainless steel flex line)
- 2.5 Remove the cap from “Cold H₂O from MTF” QD fitting (see Figure 4) and put it in the Ziplock Bag

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

2.6 Connect “Cold H₂O from MTF” to the proper MTF fluidic line (stainless steel flex line)

NOTE

1. TWO POWER INTERFACES ARE AVAILABLE AT MUM LEVEL – LOWER PANEL:
 - RACK MAIN POWER SUPPLY
 - AUXILIARY POWER SUPPLY

FOR THE ANTARCTICA OPERATIONS THE ONLY RACK MAIN POWER SUPPLY INTERFACE IS REQUIRED. THE OTHER ONE IS A SERVICE POWER SUPPLY TO BE USED DURING STAND ALONE TEST OR IN CASE OF FAILURE OF THE MAIN POWER INTERFACE

2. ONE VGA INTERFACE IS AVAILABLE ON THE PCDH FRONT PANEL
 - VGA CONNECTOR
3. NO POWER/VIDEO CONNECTIONS HAVE TO BE DONE ON THE MUM UPPER RIGHT PANEL

2.5 Connect EDEN ISS power cable to the Rack “Main Power Supply”

2.6 Connect the VGA cable to the VGA Connector on the PCDH Front Panel (Fig. 5)

2.6 Connect “Cooling Inlet Purge” valve as per Figure 4

2.7 Connect “Cooling Outlet Purge valve as per Figure 4

Figure 6: Cooling lines pressure sensors – before sensors installation

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

Figure 7: Cooling lines pressure sensors – after sensors installation

- 2.11 In GCS and GCT cooling lines frame (detailed in Figure 6), connect Pressure Gauges 1 to 4 as per Figure 4
- 2.12 Reinstall the floor panels removed in Step 2.2
- 3 **MUM_CO₂ BOTTLE INSTALLATION**

Figure 8: Lower left side of the Main Utility Module: Front Panel

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

Figure 9: MUM Internal components - CO₂ Bottles and Manometers

Figure 10: CO₂ Bottles – Outlet Valves and Fittings configuration

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

- 3.1 Remove the front panel of the Main Utility Module by means of M 2,5 allen key (see Figure 8)
 - 3.2 Remove the bottles fixations (M2,5 Allen Key)
 - 3.3 Install the CO₂ bottles (2). Install the bottles fixations (M 2,5 allen key)
 - 3.4 Connect the CO₂ outlet fittings
 - 3.5 Slowly open the CO₂ Outlet Pressure Regulation Valves. On the pressure sensors verify that the pressure is increasing
 - 3.6 Regulate the CO₂ Outlet Pressure Regulation Valves in order to have the pressure = 1,5 **bar**.
- 4 NDS_CONCENTRATED NUTRIENT TANKS INSTALLATION**

NOTE

THE NDS DRAWER HAS BEEN SHIPPED TO NMIII IN ANTARCTICA AS SEPARATE ITEM. IT HAS TO BE CONFIGURED AND INSTALLED INSIDE THE ISPR RACK AS PART OF THE RACK MECHANICAL CONFIGURATION

WARNING

THE DRAWER INSTALLATION OPERATION HAS TO BE DONE BY TWO OPERATORS. ONE SINGLE OPERATOR CANNOT SUSTAIN THE DRAWER AND IN PARALLEL REMOVE THE FIXATION BOLTS, WITH A POSSIBLE RISK OF DRAWER FALL, AND THEREFORE OPERATOR INJURY OR DRAWER DAMAGE.

1.120 ISPR Configuration (ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

Figure 11 Configuration of NDS Inside Transport Container

- 4.1 Retrieve the NDS transport container from stowage and put it close to EDEN ISS Rack
- 4.2 Open NDS Transport container by unscrewing the screw (Philip Head Screwdriver)
- 4.3 In the NDS Volume remove the fixation kapton of the drawers metal runners
- 4.4 Extract the drawers metal runners and install the drawer on them. Tightens the six M2,5 bolts (3 screws for each side) with a M2,5 allen key.

Remark: Do not close the drawer at the end of the installation

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

Figure 12: NDS Drawer upper panel fixed by kapton tape

- 4.5 Remove kapton tape that holds NDS Drawer cover in position. See Figure 12
- 4.6 Remove the NDS upper panel (lift it up – no bolts to be removed) and temp stow it.

NOTE

1. THREE SOFT BAGS HAVE TO BE INSTALLED IN THE NDS DRAWER ACTING AS CONCENTRATED NUTRIENT TANK_A, TANK_B AND TANK_C AS SHOWN IN THE BELOW FIGURE 13

Figure 13: Concentrated Nutrient Tanks A, B and C

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

- 4.7 Wear the Nitrile Gloves
- 4.8 Remove the “Support Plate_1”
- 4.9 Remove the “Support Plate_2”
- 4.10 Install the “Nutrient Tank_A”. Connect it to the QD
- 4.11 Re-mount the “Support Plate_2”
- 4.12 Install the “Nutrient Tank_B” . Connect it to the QD
- 4.13 Re-Install “Support Plate_1”
- 4.14 Install the “Nutrient Tank_C”. Connect it to the QD
- 4.15 Remount “NDS Drawer Upper Panel”

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

- 4.16 Put Kapton tape to secure the NDS upper panel to the NDS drawer as per Figure 14
- 4.17 Push the NDS drawer inside the Rack until the stop.
- 4.18 Take off Nitrile Gloves

5 UTILITIES CONNECTIONS

5.1 Data Cables Installation

NOTE

THE POWER COMMAND AND DATA HANDLING DRAWER (PCDH) IS THE ISPR S/S FOR THE POWER DISTRIBUTION AND DATA MANAGEMENT. THE CONNECTIONS OF THIS SUBSYSTEM WITH THE OTHER ISPR SUBSYSTEMS IS DONE VIA EXTERNAL CABLES TO BE CONNECTED ON DEDICATED CONNECTORS ON THE PCDH FRONT PANEL AND ON THE OTHER ISPR SUBSYSTEMS CONNECTORS

Figure 15: Data connectors on the PCDH Front Panel

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

Figure 16: Data Connectors on the GCS, on the NDS and on the Illumination Drawer Left (ILL)

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

Figure 17: Data Connectors on the GCT (Green connectors) and on the Illumination Drawer Right (ILR)

- 5.1.1 Connect ILR-A (on the PCDH) to the ILR-A (on the ILL)
- 5.1.2 Connect the ILL-A (on the PCDH) to the ILL-A (on the ILR)
- 5.1.3 Connect the MUM-D (on the PCDH) to the MUM-D (on the MUM Panel Upper Right)
- 5.1.4 Connect the MUM-G (on the PCDH) to the Monitor (on the MUM Panel Upper Right)
- 5.1.5 Connect the GCS-G1/GCS-G2 (on the PCDH) to the I-G (on the GCS)

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

- 5.1.6 Connect the GCS-H1/CGS-H2 (on the PCDH) to the I-H (on the GCS)
- 5.1.7 Connect the GCT-G1/GCT-G2 (on the PCDH) to the I-G (on the GCT)
- 5.1.8 Connect the GCT-H1/CGT-H2 (on the PCDH) to the I-H (on the GCT)
- 5.1.9 Connect the NDS-B (on the PCDH) to the NDS-B (on the NDS)
- 5.1.10 Connect the MUM H1 (on the PCDH) to the MUM H1 (on the MUM Panel Upper Right)
- 5.1.11 Connect the MUM H2 (on the PCDH) to the MUM H2 (on the MUM Panel Upper Right)

5.2 Fluidic Lines Connections

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

Figure 18: Water Cooling Lines and CO2 Lines Connections

THE CONNECTIONS ARE DONE BY MEANS OF FLEXIBLE HOSES PROPERLY AND UNIVOCALLY LABELED

2. THE COLLING WATER PATH IS AS FOLLOW:

- a. COOL WATER IS GOING VIA THE MUM INTERFACES FROM THE MTF HEAT EXCHANGER TO THE GCT/GCS THC SX/DX WERE COLLECTS THE HEAT DISSIPATED BY THE PELTIER
- b. THEN THE WATER IS GOING TO THE ILL/ILR WERE COLLECTS THE WATER GENERATED BY THE LED LAMP UNITS
- c. FINALLY THE WATER IS COMING BACK TO THE MTF HEAT EXCHANGER VIA THE MUM INTERFACES

- 5.2.1 Connect the GCS CO2 MUM I/F (on the MUM Left Panel) to the GCS CO2 Inlet (on the GCS).
- 5.2.2 Connect the GCT CO2 MUM I/F (on the MUM Left Panel) to the GCT CO2 Inlet (on the GCT)
- 5.2.3 Connect the Cool ILL MUM I/F (on the MUM Left Panel) to the Cool ILL IN (On the ILL). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.
- 5.2.4 Connect the GCS THC-SX MUM I/F (on the MUM Left Panel) to the GCS THC-SX IN (on the GCS). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.
- 5.2.5 Connect the GCS THC-DX MUM I/F (on the MUM Left Panel) to the GCS THC-DX IN (on the GCS). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.
- 5.2.6 Connect the Cool ILL In to the GCS SX Out and to the GCS DX Out (on the GCS). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.
- 5.2.7 Connect the Cool ILR MUM I/F (on the MUM Right Panel) to the Cool ILR IN (on the ILR). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.
- 5.2.8 Connect the GCT THC-SX MUM I/F (on the MUM Right Panel) to the GCT THC-SX IN (on the GCT). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.
- 5.2.9 Connect the GCT THC-DX MUM I/F (on the MUM Right Panel) to the GCT THC-DX IN (on the GCT). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.
- 5.2.10 Connect the Cool ILR In to the GCT SX Out and to the GCT DX Out (on the GCT). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

5.3 NDS Connections

NOTE

THE NDS SYSTEM PROVIDES THE NUTRIENT SOLUTION TO THE GCT AND THE GCS AND MANAGES THE CONDENSATE WATER PRODUCED BY THE COOLING SYSTEM. THE

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

CONNECTION OF THE NDS WITH THE OTHER SYSTEM IS DONE VIA INTERFACES ON THE FRONT PANEL OF THE RACK AS SHOWN IN FIGURE 19 BELOW. THE CONNECTIONS ARE DONE USING BLACK RUBBER TUBES

Figure 19: NDS Fluidic Interfaces

- 4.2.1 Connect “GCS to NDS Condensate line” (on the NDS) to the GCS Condensate Out (on the GCS) see Fig. 19. Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.
- 4.2.2 Connect “GCT to NDS Condensate line” (on the NDS) to the GCT Condensate Out (on the GCS) see Fig. 19. Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.
- 4.2.3 Connect NDS to GCS Nutrient Solution Line (on the NDS) to GCS Nutrient Solution Inlet NDS (on the GCS) see Fig 19. Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

1.120 ISPR Configuration

(ISPR RACK/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE/HC)

- 4.2.4 Connect NDS to GCT Nutrient Solution Line (on the NDS) to GCT Nutrient Solution Inlet NDS (on the GCT) see Fig 19. Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

5 CLOSEOUT

- 5.1 Stow the items and tools

1.140 ISPR Activation and Checkout

(ISPR Rack/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Activation of the ISPR Rack and Self-Test.

DURATION

30 minutes

TOOLS

N/A

ITEMS

N/A

SS 1 ISPR RACK ACTIVATION

Figure 1: Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel – ISPR Power Switch

1.140 ISPR Activation and Checkout

(ISPR Rack/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE)

Figure 2: ISPR Rack Main Switch

- 1.1 On the S/S Power Panel Switch ON the ISPR Rack switches (Fig. 1)
- 1.2 On the electrical panel on the Rack top left side, switch ON the ISPR power switch (Fig. 2)

2 RUCOLA SW INITIALIZATION AND AUTOMATIC TEST

NOTE

1) AT THE END OF THE SW LOAD, THE SYSTEM STARTS AN AUTOMATIC TEST (SELF TEST) WITH THE OBJECTIVE TO VERIFY THAT:

- ALL ACTUATORS / SENSORS ARE PROPERLY CONNECTED TO THE SYSTEM
- ALL ACTUATORS / SENSORS ARE ACTUALLY WORKING

THE SELF TEST IS DONE IN 11 STEPS AS DESCRIBED IN THE FOLLOWING TABLE

1.140 ISPR Activation and Checkout

(ISPR Rack/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE)

RUCOLA SW - System Self Test			
Test Name	Tested Components	Execution Note	outcome
NDS	Nutrient Solution Tank Level Indicator	The SW verifies the Level of the liquid in the tank	The reading outcome could be : 1) OK (light green) if tank level is properly read by SW. And pumps are working properly 2) Failed (dark green) if tank level can't be read or tank is empty or pumps are not working properly
	D.I. Water Tank Level Indicator		
	Water to GC pump	Pumps are operated for 1 sec to check if they are working properly	
	Water to NUT pump		
ILL	LED Panel Check	The SW switches ON LED Lamps	The reading outcome could be : 1) OK (light green) LED LAMP and Cameras are properly actuated by SW. 2) Failed (dark green) LED LAMP can't be actuated or Cameras are not properly actuated by SW.
	Cameras Ckeck	The SW switches ON Cameras	
ILR	see ILL	see ILL	see ILL
GCS 1	Temp of recirculating water (placed inside GCS lateral panel)	SW reads the following parameters: 1) Temp of recirculating water 1) T inside GCS 2) RH 3) O ₂	The reading outcome could be : 1) OK (light green) all sensors are working properly. 2) Failed (dark green) sensors are not working properly
	T inside GCS		
	RH		
	O ₂		
GCS 2	Moisture Sensors (8x)	The SW acquires the Moisture sensors values. <i>These sensors are connected to +5VDC. They works properly if they provide a signal between 0V and 5V</i>	The reading outcome could be : 1) OK (light green) if moisture sensors signal is between 0 to +5 VDC. 2) Failed (dark green) if moisture sensors signal is not between 0 to +5 VDC.
GCS 3	Solenoid valves	Solenoid valves (8) are activated by the SW, the operator is asked to report if the valves have been operated as expected. <i>Remark: The SW is not providing any feedback on the correct functioning of the valve, but rather the test operator has to verify if the valves are correctly working. That can be done by simply verifying if an audible noise can be heard for each valve open/close cycle during the execution of the test. The following sequence applies:</i> 1. The SW activate the solenoid valves, operating them one by one separately with a delay of 1 second between two consecutive actuation. 2) A dialog windows appears, asking the test operator to confirm or not if the valves are correctly working. 3) The Operators clicks to "YES" or "NO" depending on the results of the test.	The reading outcome could be : 1) OK (light green) if the pump is correctly powered 2) Failed (dark green) Otherwise
GCS THC	Heaters (inside THC)	Rucola SW acts as follows: 1) SW reads cooler temp and Heater temp. 2) SW switches ON either the heater and the cooler for 30 sec. SW reads again cooler temp and Heater temp.	The reading outcome could be : 1) OK (light green) if cooler temp is lowered and heater temp is increased. 2) Failed (dark green) -> Otherwise
	Cooler (Inside THC)		
GCT 1	see GCS 1	see GCS 1	see GCS 1
GCT 2	see GCS 2	see GCS 2	see GCS 2
GCT 3	see GCS 3	see GCS 3	see GCS 3
GCT THC	see GCS THC	see GCS THC	see GCS THC

2) AT THE END OF EACH STEP, THE RESULT COULD BE:

- SUCCESSFUL -> THE SYSTEM SELF CHECK PROGRAM MOVES AUTOMATICALLY TO THE NEXT TEST CHECK STEP.

1.140 ISPR Activation and Checkout

(ISPR Rack/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE)

- NOT SUCCESSFUL. IN THIS CASE 3 ACTIONS ARE ALLOWED:
 - a. "RUN AGAIN" -> IN THIS MODE, THE SYSTEM RUNS AGAIN THE TEST CHECK NOT ALREADY PASSED
 - b. "ABORT"-> THE SOFTWARE IS SHUT OFF, SO THAT IT COULD BE RESTARTED AND SYSTEM SELF CHECK PROGRAM COULD BE PERFORMED AGAIN
 - c. "CONTINUE ANYWAY" THE SYSTEM CONTINUES WITH THE BOOT OF THE RUCOLA SYSTEM REGARDLESS OF THE OUTCOME OF THE SPECIFIC TEST CHECK.

Figure 3: RUCOLA SW Main Page

1.140 ISPR Activation and Checkout

(ISPR Rack/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE)

Figure 4: RUCOLA SW - Self Test Window

- 2.1 Switch ON RUCOLA SW by double clicking on the .exe file. The loading window will appear (Fig. 3), followed by the System Self Test Window (Fig. 4).
- 2.2 While monitoring the execution of the test (verification of the evolution of the LED's in the Self-Test Window), before the test GCS3 and GCT3 pay attention to the noise coming from the rack. A "click" is expected for each tested valve for a total of 8 "clicks" per test.
- 2.3 Check that the test is successful (fig. 4):
 - NDS LED** = Green (Successful with no error)
 - ILL LED** = Green (Successful with no error)
 - ILR LED** = Green (Successful with no error)
 - GCS1 LED** = Green (Successful with no error)
 - GCS2 LED** = Green (Successful with no error)
 - GCS2 LED** = Green (Successful with no error)
 - GCS THCs LED** = Green (Successful with no error)
 - GCT1 LED** = Green (Successful with no error)
 - GCT2 LED** = Green (Successful with no error)
 - GCT3 LED** = Green (Successful with no error)
 - GCT THCs LED** = Green (Successful with no error)
- 2.4 If one or more test failed with the following message: "Failed with no error",

Repeat the test Click on **Run again** in the Test Failed message window. If necessary repeat the test up to 5 times

1.140 ISPR Activation and Checkout

(ISPR Rack/CREW/COMMISSIONING/PRE)

If the test cannot be completed without errors

Stop the operations and Call MCC. Wait for instructions

2.5 If one or more tests failed with an error message

Stop the operations, record the message and Call MCC. Wait for instructions

2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth

(ISPR Rack/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

OBJECTIVE

Configure the rack in preparation of plant growth cycle. Pillow preparation and installation in the growth chambers, fluidics and cables connections, rack activation and setup of the experiment parameters (Temperature, Relative Humidity, Light Intensity, etc.).

DURATION

TBD

TOOLS

2,5 mm allen key
Phillips-head screwdriver
Scissors
Laboratory spatula

ITEMS

Dry Wipes
Paper strips
Agar-Agar Powder
Distilled Water

NOTE

- 1) FOUR DIFFERENT CROPS WILL BE CULTIVATED INSIDE THE RACK GROWTH CHAMBERS (GCT AND GCS) AS FOLLOW:

- TOMATO CHERRIE LADIES (GCT)
- LETTUCE CHEROKEE (GCS)
- TOKIO BEKANA (GCS)
- RUCOLA (GCS)

- 2) THE AMOUNT OF TIME NEEDED FROM SEEDING TO HARVESTING IS DESCRIBED IN THE FOLLOWING TABLE.

	Amount of time required for seeds growth [months]	Foreseen Growth Ratio
Tomato Cherrie Kisses	3	33% until the end of Month #1 66% until the end of Month #2 100% until the end of Month #3
Rucola	1	Started and accomplished During Month #1
Lettuce Cherokee	1	Started and accomplished During Month #2
Tokio Bekana	1	Started and accomplished During Month #3

- 3) CONSIDERING 1 YEAR OF OPERATIONS AND THAT IT IS POSSIBLE TO CULTIVATE ONE SPECIES PER GROWTH CHAMBER AT TIME, THE FOLLOWING SCHEMA IS ENVISAGED:
- THREE CROP CYCLE ARE "NOMINALLY" POSSIBLE, EACH ONE LASTING THREE MONTHS

2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth

(ISPR Rack/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

- FOR EACH MONTH ONE SPECIES WILL BE CULTIVATED PER GROWTH CHAMBER AS PER THE FOLLOWING SCHEMA

- 4) 1 PILLOWS INSTALLATION EVENT FOR THE GCT AND 3 PILLOWS INSTALLATION EVENTS FOR THE GCS ARE FORESEEN IN A CYCLE. IN THIS WAY 8 PILLOWS PER MONTH ARE OPERATED IN PARALLEL, CONSIDERING GCT + GCS, RESULTING IN A TOTAL OF 16 PILLOWS OPERATED EVERY CROP CYCLE (3 MONTHS) AS PER THE FOLLOWING PICTURE

2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth

(ISPR Rack/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

5) THE SECOND AND THE THIRD CYCLE ARE A REPETITION OF THE FIRST CYCLE

REMARK: WHAT DESCRIBED STRONGLY DEPENDS ON THE SUCCESS OF THE PLANT GROWTH. OF COURSE SEVERAL FACTORS COULD LEAD TO DEVIATION OF THE NOMINAL PLAN. THAT WILL BE MANAGED CASE BY CASE.

SS 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

WARNING

THE ISPR CONFIGURATION HAS TO BE DONE WITH THE RACK POWERED OFF. IN FACT AN ELECTRICAL SHOCK HAZARD HAS TO BE CONSIDERED FOR OPERATIONS DONE WITH THE RACK ACTIVE

1.2 If the Rack is active and there are operations running

stop the operations and deactivate the rack as per the following steps.

Figure 1: RUCOLA SW Main Page – Stop the operations

1.2.1 Click on the “STOP” button in RUCOLA SW main dialog window so that configuration parameters are saved and Rucola Software is switched off (Fig. 1)

2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth

(ISPR Rack/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

Figure 2: ISPR Rack Main Switch

1.2.2 On the upper left panel of the ISPR Rack, switch Off the “Rack Power Switch” (Fig. 2)

Figure 3: Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel – ISPR Power Switch

1.2.3 On the EDEN ISS Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel, Switch OFF the ISPR Rack switches (Fig. 3)

2 SEEDING

NOTE

2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth

(ISPR Rack/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

- 1) SEEDING IS DONE BY MEANS OF THE PREPARATION OF SEEDS STRIPS AND THEN INSERTION OF THESE LAST INSIDE THE SUBSTRATE PILLOWS.
- 2) THE DIMENSIONS OF THE SEED STRIPS AND THE NUMBER OF SEEDS PER STRIPS ARE AS FOLLOW:

- 60 X20 MM FOR TOMATO, LETTUCE AND TOKIO BEKANA (1 SEED PER STRIP)
- 200 X 20 FOR RUCOLA (20 SEEDS PER STRIP)

- 3) IN ONE CYCLE THE FOLLOWING STRIPS HAVE TO BE PREPARED:
 - MONTH #1: 8 STRIPS FOR RUCOLA AND 8 STRIPS FOR TOMATO
 - MONTH #2: 16 STRIPS FOR LETTUCE CHEROKEE
 - MONTH #3: 16 STRIPS FOR TOKIO BEKANA
- 4) EACH SEED(S) STRIP IS DONE OF TWO PAPERS STRIPS WITH ONE OR MORE SEEDS IN THE MIDDLE

- 2.1 Prepare as many papers strips as the crop (or the cycle phase) requires (see NOTE)
- 2.2 Prepare jelly-like substance adding 5g of Agar-Agar powder to 250 ml of D.I water
- 2.3 Using a laboratory spatula distribute some part of the Agar Agar solution on one paper strip
- 2.4 Put the seeds on the paper strip as required
- 2.5 Cover the seeds with the second paper strips. Press the strip
- 2.6 Repeat for the other seeds/strips

2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth

(ISPR Rack/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

Figure 4: Substrate Pillow

- 2.7 Insert the paper strip(s) in the pillow.
Lift the fabric flap A, B and C, D (Fig. 4) and place the paper strips between porous fabric and the waterproof one as per the following schema (see NOTE):

Month #1

- Rucola: one strip for each cut in the waterproof cloth
- Cherry tomato: one strip for each cut in the waterproof cloth

Month#2

- Lettuce Cherokee: two strips for each cut in the waterproof cloth

Month#3

- Tokio Bekana: two strips for each cut in the waterproof cloth

3 PILLOW INSTALLATION IN THE GROWTH CHAMBERS

3.1 Drawer Extraction and Opening

NOTE

1. THE FOLLOWING STEPS APPLIES TO BOTH THE TALL GROWTH CHAMBERS (GCT) AND THE SHORT GROWTH CHAMBERS (GCS)
2. ALL THE FLUIDIC LINES ARE EQUIPPED WITH SELF LOCKING QUICK DISCONNECT COUPLING DEVICES, THEREFORE ONLY MANUAL ACTION IS REQUIRED FOR CONNECTION/DISCONNECTION

2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth

(ISPR Rack/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

ILLUMINATION DRAWER LEFT/GCS

ILLUMINATION DRAWER RIGHT/GCT

Figure 5: Cooling lines to be disconnected from the illumination drawers

- 3.1.1 On the Illumination Drawer, disconnect the COOL ILL/ILR IN and the COOL ILL/ILR OUT hoses (Fig. 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth

(ISPR Rack/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

Figure 6: Lines to be disconnected from the GCT and the GCS

- 3.1.2 Disconnect CO₂ inlet line (Fig. 6)
- 3.1.3 Disconnect Nutrient solution inlet line (Fig. 6). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops
- 3.1.4 Disconnect moisture recovery lines from THC (Fig. 6). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops
- 3.1.5 Disconnect the electrical connections and Peltier cooling line from the THC of both GCT / GCS (Fig. 6) (remark: one of the THC of the GCT is missing in the picture)
- 3.1.6 Pull the GCT / GCS drawer out of EDEN ISS Rack until the stop

NOTE

TO ACCESS THE INTERIOR OF THE GROWTH CHAMBERS (BOTH THE GCS AND THE GCT) A LATERAL PANEL HAS TO BE REMOVED. TO DO THAT 10 BOLTS HAVE TO BE UNSCREWED FOR THE GCS AND 12 BOLTS HAVE TO BE UNSCREWED FOR THE GCT AS PER THE FOLLOWING FIGURES

2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth

(ISPR Rack/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

Figure 7: GCS, later panel fixations bolts position

Figure 8: GCS, later panel fixations bolts position

2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth

(ISPR Rack/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

3.1.7 Unscrew the bolts with 2,5 allen key that secure AI panel to the drawer lateral structure of GCS/GCT

3.1.8 Remove the lateral AI panel from GCS/GCT

3.2 Root Module Preparation

Figure 9: Root Module

Figure 10: Root Module Panel Removal

3.2.1 If a plant growth cycle experiment has already been completed cut all the plants stems close to the Root module panels. Waste them.

2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth

(ISPR Rack/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

Figure 11: Moisture sensor

- 3.2.2 Remove the Moisture Sensors (Fig. 11)
 - 3.2.3 Disconnect the inlet water line QDs (Blue boxes in Figure 9)
 - 3.2.4 Disconnect the outlet water line QDs (yellow box in Figure 9)
 - 3.2.5 Unscrew the top panels bolts (16) by means of a Phillips-head screwdriver (Red Circles in Fig. 9)
 - 3.2.6 Remove the panels (4) (Fig. 10) and temporary stow them
 - 3.2.7 If there are pillows (4) inside the root module
remove and temporary stow them
 - 3.2.8 Install the new pillows (4) inside the root module
 - 3.2.9 Install the panels (4). Install and tighten the screws by means of the Phillip-head screwdriver
 - 3.2.10 Connect the inlet water lines
 - 3.2.11 Connect the outlet water line
 - 3.2.12 Insert the Humidity Sensors in their location (Fig. 4 and 11)
- 3.3 Growth Chamber Closure**
- 3.3.1 Install the lateral AI panel on GCS/GCT. Screw the M2,5 bolts using the Allen Key and tighten them.

2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth

(ISPR Rack/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

NOTE

THE POWER AND DATA ISPR/GROWTH CHAMBERS INTERFACES ARE LOCATED ON THE REAR PART OF THE GROWTH CHAMBERS AND ON THE REAR PANEL OF THE RACK ENCLOSURE. TO ENSURE A PROPER CONNECTIONS THE DRAWER HAS TO BE COMPLETELY INSERTED IN ITS ENCLOSURE

Figure 12: Power and Data Connectors on the Rear Panel of the Rack Enclosure

- 3.3.2 Push the GCT / GCS drawer in the EDEN ISS Rack until the stop
- 3.3.3 Connect the electrical connections and Peltier cooling line from the THC of both GCT / GCS (Fig. 6) (remark: one of the THC of the GCT is missing in the picture)
- 3.3.4 Connect moisture recovery lines to the THC (Fig. 6). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops
- 3.3.5 Connect Nutrient solution inlet line (Fig. 6). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops (Fig. 6)
- 3.3.6 Connect CO₂ inlet line (Fig. 6)

SS 4 ISPR RACK ACTIVATION

- 4.1 Perform 1.140 ISPR Activation and Checkout, all steps

5 SETUP OF THE EXPERIMENT PARAMETERS AND OPERATIONS START

NOTE

1. THE OPERATIONS OF THE ISPR RACK ARE NOMINALLY CONDUCTED BY MEANS OF CONFIGURATION FILES THAT ARE PREPARED IN ADVANCE AND DEFINES THE CONFIGURATION PARAMETERS (TEMPERATURE, LIGHT INTENSITY, CO₂ LEVEL, ETC) FOR THE SELECTED CROP.
2. THE CONFIGURATION FILE NAME IS DEFINED AS FOLLOW:
 - configuration parameter file_AAAAMMDD_001
 - configuration parameter file_AAAAMMDD_002
 -

2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth

(ISPR Rack/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

- configuration parameter file_AAAAMMDD_999
3. THE PREPARATION OF THE CONFIGURATION FILE IS UNDER TAS-I RESPONSIBILITY. IN CASE THE OPERATIONS HAVE TO BE DONE BY THE ON SITE OPERATOR, TAS-I WILL PROVIDE INSTRUCTIONS ON WHAT TO DO

Figure 15: RUCOLA SW - Initial Configuration Display

- 5.1 RUCOLA Main Page: Initial Configuration
Click on **Load From File** (Fig. 15). A window with the list of files will appear, select the desired one and click on **Load** button.
- 5.2 RUCOLA Main Page: Initial Configuration: Current Values
- Verify **Level Flex Bags** Parameters = as defined in the configuration file
Verify **Nut. Solution properties** = as defined in the configuration file
Verify **Flux Canalizer Status** = as defined in the configuration file
Verify **Parameters GCS Phase 1** = as defined in the configuration file
Verify **Parameters GCS Phase 2** = as defined in the configuration file
Verify **Parameters GCS Phase 3** = as defined in the configuration file
Verify **Parameters GCT Phase 1** = as defined in the configuration file
Verify **Parameters GCT Phase 2** = as defined in the configuration file
Verify **Parameters GCT Phase 3** = as defined in the configuration file
Verify **Day After Planting** = as defined in the configuration file
- 5.3 If all the parameters are as expected, click on **OK** Button. The operations will start.
GOTO step 5

2.300 ISPR Configuration for Plant Growth

(ISPR Rack/CREW/NOMINAL/PRE/HC)

Figure 16: Initial Configuration Display – Save to File Command Button

5.4 If the parameters are not as expected

Input manually the correct parameters as per configuration file provided by MCC/TAS-I

Save the parameters on a new file. In the Initial Configuration Display, click on **Save to File**

Repeat steps from 5.1 to 5.3

If the problem persists

input again the desired data

Click on the OK button. The operations will start.

6 CLOSEOUT

6.1 Stow the tools and items

6.2 Waste the removed pillow (if any)

3410 ISPR Nutrient Solution Sample Collection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Collection of Nutrient Solution Sample for off line analysis of its composition

DURATION

20 minutes

TOOLS

N/A

ITEMS (PROVIDED WITH THE RACK)

1/4 Hose Barb Valved In-Line Coupling Body (Female)

1/4 teflon pipe line (length = 25 cm)

Sampling Bottle / Falcon™ 50mL Conical tube

Labels

Red marker

Dry wipe

SS 1 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

1.1 Collect the needed items

1/4 Hose Barb Valved In-Line Coupling Body (Female)

Teflon Pipe

Sampling Bottle / Falcon™ 50mL Conical tube

3410 ISPR Nutrient Solution Sample Collection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 1: Nutrient Delivery System Drawer – Sampling Setup

- 1.2 Connect the rear side of 1/4 Hose Barb Valved In-Line Coupling Body (Female) to the Teflon pipe line (fig. 1)
- 1.3 Connect the front side of the 1/4 Hose Barb Valved In-Line Coupling Body (Female) to the sampling port (male) (Fig. 1)
- 1.4 Insert / Connect the pipeline to the sampling bottle.

2 SAMPLING

NOTE

1. WHEN THE NUTRIENT SAMPLING IS SELECTED, THE RUCOLA SOFTWARE AUTOMATICALLY DISABLES RACK MANAGEMENT PROCESSES, BUT SAVING THE CONFIGURATION PARAMETERS, AND ENABLES THE ONLY DEVICES NECESSARY FOR SAMPLING
2. RUCOLA SOFTWARE AUTOMATICALLY DELIVERS THE REQUIRED AMOUNT OF SOLUTION BY MEANS OF NDS INTERNAL PUMP. ONCE THE SOLUTION VOLUME IS DELIVERED, RUCOLA SOFTWARE SWITCHES OFF THE NDS PUMP AUTOMATICALLY

Figure 2: RUCOLA Main Display

Figure 3: Set Navigation Window

Figure 4: Nutrient Sampling Commanding Window

- 2.1 RUCOLA MAIN
Click on **SET** located (Fig. 2). A “SET Navigation Window” will open (Fig. 3)
- 2.2 In the “SET Navigation Window” click on the **Nutrient Solution Sampling** button. The “Nutrient Sampling Commanding Window” will open (Fig. 4)
- 2.3 In Nutrient Sampling Commanding Window click on “START Sampling” button

3410 ISPR Nutrient Solution Sample Collection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

- 2.4 Verify that the Nutrient Solution is pumped in the Sampling Bottle and that it flows through the QD fitting
- 2.5 When a dialog windows appears with the message “Sampling complete”, Click on the **OK** Button

Figure 5: Nutrient Sampling Commanding Window Updated

- 2.6 In the Nutrient Sampling Commanding Window Verify that the Nutrient Solution Level has decreased.
 - 2.7 Disconnect the female half QD from the sampling port.
 - 2.8 Disconnect/detach the Sampling Bottle from pipeline.
 - 2.9 Close the Sampling bottle
 - 2.10 Remove possible drops leakage using dry wipe.
- 3 CLOSEOUT**
- 3.1 Label the Sampling Bottle “ISPR/YYYY/MM/HH.MM
 - 3.2 Waste the used dry wipes

3410 ISPR Nutrient Solution Sample Collection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/SCIENCE/PRE)

Figure 6

- 3.3 Resume the operations. Click on **RUCOLA** (Fig. 6) and press **Start** button.

Rucola Software automatically disables nutrient solution sampling, enables the Rack automatic operations from the point where they were stopped.

4.530 ISPR CO2 Bottle Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Replace CO2 bottles in the Main Utility Module when they are empty

DURATION

15 min

TOOLS

M2,5 Allen Key

ITEMS

CO2 Bottle

Sticky Labels

Permanent red marker

NOTE

THIS ACTIVITY IS REQUIRED WHEN THE CO2 LEVEL INSIDE THE BOTTLES FALLS BELOW 1.5 BAR. THAT VALUE CAN BE ACQUIRED IN TWO WAYS:

- BY MEANS OF THE RUCOLA SW AND DISPLAYED AS NUMERICAL VALUE ON THE RUCOLA MAIN DISPLAY
- BY MEANS OF CO2 PRESSURE GAUGE MOUNTED ON THE CO2 BOTTLES

1 CO2 LEVEL VERIFICATION AND OPERATIONS STOP

Figure 1: RUCOLA SW Main Page

4.530 ISPR CO2 Bottle Replacement (ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 2: Configuration Parameters

- SS 1.1 On the ISPR Laptop
RUCOLA Main Page/SERVICES&CONTROL (Fig. 1)
Verify **CO2 Bottle Pressure** < 1.5 bar
- 1.2 RUCOLA Main Page: Initial Configuration: Current Values

Record **Level Flex Bags** values
 Record **Nutr. Solution properties** values
 Record **Flux Canalizer Status** values
 Record **Parameters GCS Phase 1** values
 Record **Parameters GCS Phase 2** values
 Record **Parameters GCS Phase 3** values
 Record **Parameters GCT Phase 1** values
 Record **Parameters GCT Phase 2** values
 Record **Parameters GCT Phase 3** values
 Record **Day After Planting** values

See Fig. 2

- 1.3 RUCOLA Main Page (Fig. 1)
Click on **STOP** Button

The ISPR operations will stop

4.530 ISPR CO2 Bottle Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 3: EDEN ISS Rack Power Switch

- 1.4 On the upper left panel of the ISPR Rack, switch Off the “Rack Power Switch” (Fig. 3)

Figure 4: Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel – ISPR Power Switch

- 1.5 On the EDEN ISS Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel, Switch OFF the ISPR Rack switches (Fig. 4)

FEG 2 CO2 BOTTLES REPLACEMENT

NOTE

THE MUM PANEL IS PLACED BELOW THE MUM CONNECTORS AND THEREFORE CAN BE REMOVED WITHOUT DISCONNECTING THE ELECTRICAL CABLES AND THE FLUIDIC HOSES

4.530 ISPR CO2 Bottle Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 5: Lower left side of the Main Utility Module: Front Panel

Figure 6: CO2 Bottles and Pressure Gauges

4.530 ISPR CO2 Bottle Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 7: CO2 Bottles – Outlet Valves and Fittings

- 2.1 Remove the front panel located shown in the Fig. 5 (M2,5 Allen Key)
- 2.2 On the pressure Gauges
Verify CO2 pressure < 1.5 bar and compare it against the telemetry value.
- 2.3 If the CO2 telemetry value differs from the Pressure Gauge value of 50% then:
 1. reload the RUCOLA SW
 2. close completely and then slowly open the CO2 outlet valves
 3. check again the Telemetry value against the manometer value. If the difference is still > of 50% stop the operations and report to MCC
- 2.4 Close the CO2 outlet valves
- 2.5 Disconnect the CO2 outlet fitting
- 2.6 Remove the CO2 bottles fixations (4) and temp stow it (Fig. 7). Use the M2,5 Allen Key to unscrew the bolts
- 2.7 Remove the CO2 empty bottles and mark them "EMPTY BOTTLE – DO NOT USE)

4.530 ISPR CO2 Bottle Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 2.8 Install the new CO2 bottles (2). Install the bottles fixations (M2,5 Allen Key)
- 2.9 Connect the CO2 outlet fittings
- 2.10 Slowly open the CO2 Outlet Pressure Regulation Valves. On the Pressure Gauge verify that the pressure is increasing
- 2.11 Regulate the CO2 Outlet Pressure Regulation Valves opening in order to have the pressure = 1.5 bar
- SS 2.12 On the ISPR Laptop
RUCOLA Main Page/SERVICES&CONTROL
Verify **CO2 Bottle Pressure** = 1.5 bar
- If the **CO2 Bottle Pressure** differs from the Pressure Gauge value of 50% then
1. reload the RUCOLA SW
 2. close completely and then slowly open the CO2 outlet valves
 3. check again the Telemetry value against the manometer value. If the difference is still > of 50% stop the operations and report to MCC
- FEG 2.13 Install the front panel (see Fig. 5)

3 CLOSEOUT

- SS 3.1 Restore the operations
- PERFORM 1.140 ISPR ACTIVATION AND CHECKOUT All Steps
- Remark: after RUCOLA SW reactivation, all EDEN ISS Rack "software-managed" operations restarts from the point they were before operations stop*
- 3.2 RUCOLA MAIN PAGE:Initial Configuration: Current Values
- Verify **Level Flex Bags** Parameters = as recorded in step 1.2
Verify **Nut. Solution properties** = as recorded in step 1.2
Verify **Flux Canalizer Status** = as recorded in step 1.2
Verify **Parameters GCS Phase 1** = as recorded in step 1.2
Verify **Parameters GCS Phase 2** = as recorded in step 1.2
Verify **Parameters GCS Phase 3** = as recorded in step 1.2
Verify **Parameters GCT Phase 1** = as recorded in step 1.2
Verify **Parameters GCT Phase 2** = as recorded in step 1.2
Verify **Parameters GCT Phase 3** = as recorded in step 1.2
Verify **Day After Planting** = as recorded in step 1.2
- 3.3 Stow the items and tools

4.540 ISPR Light Panel Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Replace the LED panel inside the Illumination Drawer

DURATION

60 minutes

TOOLS

Phillips-head screwdriver

Allen Key M2,5

Allen Key M5

ITEMS

Male Adapter (3/8 NPT Valved Coupling Insert - p/n HFCD24612)

Female Adapter (3/8 Hose Barb Valved Panel Mount Coupling Body - p/n HFCD16612)

Spare Led Panel

Sticky Labels

Permanent red marker

Dry wipes

Bucket / Beker with at least 1,5 liters of internal volume

NOTE

THIS PROCEDURE IS APPLICABLE TO BOTH THE ILLUMINATION DRAWER LEFT/GCS (ILL) AND TO THE ILLUMINATION DRAWER RIGHT/GCT (ILR)

SS 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

WARNING

THE LED PANEL REPLACEMENT HAS TO BE DONE WITH THE RACK POWERED OFF. IN FACT AN ELECTRICAL SHOCK HAZARD IS PRESENT HAS TO BE CONSIDERED FOR OPERATIONS DONE WITH THE RACK ACTIVE

- 1.1 Retrieve the tools and the items from stowage

4.540 ISPR Light Panel Replacement (ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 1: RUCOLA SW Main Page – Stop the operations

- 1.2 Click on the “STOP” button in RUCOLA SW main dialog window so that configuration parameters are saved and Rucola Software is switched off (Fig. 1)

Figure 2: ISPR Rack Main Switch

- 1.3 On the upper left panel of the ISPR Rack, switch Off the “Rack Power Switch” (Fig. 2)

4.540 ISPR Light Panel Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 3: Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel – ISPR Power Switch

- 1.4 On the EDEN ISS Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel, Switch OFF the ISPR Rack switches (Fig. 3)

ISPR 2 ILLUMINATION DRAWER EXTRACTION

WARNING

THE DRAWER EXTRACTION OPERATION HAS TO BE DONE BY TWO OPERATORS. ONE SINGLE OPERATOR CANNOT SUSTAIN THE DRAWER AND IN PARALLEL REMOVE THE FIXATION BOLTS, WITH A POSSIBLE RISK OF DRAWER FALL, AND THEREFORE OPERATOR INJURY OR DRAWER DAMAGE.

4.540 ISPR Light Panel Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

ILLUMINATION DRAWER LEFT/GCS

ILLUMINATION DRAWER RIGHT/GCT

Figure 4: Illuminations Drawers . Fluidic (red circle) and electrical (green circle) connections

- 2.1 Disconnect the COOL ILL/ILR IN water hoses (Fig. 4). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.
- 2.2 Disconnect the COOL ILL/ILR OUT water hoses (Fig. 4). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.
- 2.3 Disconnect the ILL-A/ILR-A cable (Fig. 4)
- 2.4 Pull Illumination drawer out of EDEN ISS Rack until the stop.
- 2.5 While the support operator is holding in place the drawer, unscrews the 6 bolts connecting the Illumination Drawer to the Rack rails (Allen Key M2.5)
- 2.6 Remove the drawer from the rail and put it on the workbench

S/S 3 WATER REMOVAL FROM THE LED PANEL COOLING CIRCUIT

CAUTION

4.540 ISPR Light Panel Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

1. BEFORE DISCONNECTING THE LED PANEL UNIT FROM THE COOLING LOOP, IT IS NECESSARY TO REMOVE THE WATER FROM IT IN ORDER TO AVOID WATER LOSS INSIDE THE ILLUMINATION WATER
2. THE AMOUNT OF WATER INSIDE ILL / ILR COOLING LOOP IS APPROXIMATELY 1 LITER

Male fitting (p/n HFCD24612)

Female Fitting (p/n HFCD16612)

Figure 5: Male and Female fittings

- 3.1 Install the Male fitting on the the COOL ILL IN / COOL ILR IN
- 3.2 Install the Female Fitting on the Male fitting
- 3.3 Open "Cool Degas Left" / "Cool Degas Right" valves on ILL / ILR (the blu ones in Figure 1) in order to let air enter inside ILL / ILR cooling loop.
- 3.4 Prepare the bucket

4.540 ISPR Light Panel Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 6: Water removal from the Illumination Drawer Cooling loop

- 3.5 Put ILL / ILR drawers in vertical position in order to let the water flow down by means of gravity inside the bucket / Beker (fig. 6)
- 3.6 Make sure that ILL / ILR cooling lines are empty.
- 3.7 Put ILL / ILR drawers in horizontal position again on the workbench.

4 LED PANEL UNIT REPLACEMENT

Figure 7: Illumination Drawer – Kapton Tape

- 4.1 Remove kapton tape that holds ILL / ILR cover in position.

4.540 ISPR Light Panel Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

4.2 Remove the ILL/ILR upper panel.

Figure 8: ILL / ILR Interior

4.3 Disconnect LED Lamp Power cable, named “power” in Fig. 8

4.4 Disconnect the cable named “LAN” in Fig. 8

4.540 ISPR Light Panel Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 9 Cooling Inlet Fittings inside ILL / ILR drawer

Figure 10: Cooling Outlet Fittings inside ILL / ILR drawer

- 4.5 Disconnect the "Inlet Plastic Fitting" from the "Inlet Brass Fitting" (Figure 9) by means of 2X TBD mm wrenches. Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops. DO NOT remove the Inlet Brass Fitting from the Led Lamp Unit
- 4.6 Repeat step 4.5 for the Outlet Plastic Fitting on the rear of the LED Lamp Unit

4.540 ISPR Light Panel Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 11: LED Panel Unit – Fixations Brackets

- 4.7 Unscrew and remove the 8 bolts (5mm Allen key) of the 4 U-Shaped fixations brackets (Fig. 11).
- 4.8 Remove the LED Panel Unit.
- 4.9 Label the removed LED Panel Unit as follows: **“DAMAGED LAMP UNIT- DO NOT USE”**
- 4.10 Remove the “Outlet Brass Fitting” and “Inlet Brass Fitting” from the damaged LED Panel Unit
- 4.11 Mount “Outlet Brass Fitting” and “Inlet Brass Fitting” on the new LED Panel Unit
- 4.12 Install the new LED Panel Unit in the Illumination drawer. Fix it to the U-Shaped Brackets by means of 8 removed bolts (5 mm Allen Key)
- 4.13 Connect the ILL/ILR cable named “power” in Fig. 8 to the new LED Panel Unit
- 4.14 Connect the “Outlet Brass Fitting” mounted on the new LED Panel Unit to the “Outlet Plastic Fitting” water hoses (Fig. 10)

4.540 ISPR Light Panel Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 4.15 Connect the “Inlet Brass Fitting” mounted on the new LED Panel Unit to the “Inlet Plastic Fitting” water hoses (Fig. 9)
- 4.16 Connect the LAN cable (Fig. 8) to the new LED Panel Unit
- 4.17 Install the ILL / ILR upper panel on the ILL / ILR as per Figure 7. Put Kapton tape to secure the ILL / ILR upper panel to drawer

5 DRAWER CLOSURE

WARNING

THE DRAWER CLOSURE OPERATION HAS TO BE DONE BY TWO OPERATORS. ONE SINGLE OPERATOR CANNOT SUSTAIN THE DRAWER AND IN PARALLEL SCREW THE FIXATION BOLTS, WITH A POSSIBLE RISK OF DRAWER FALL, AND THEREFORE OPERATOR INJURY OR DRAWER DAMAGE.

- 5.1 Lift the Drawer to the ISPR Rack rails
- 5.2 While the support operator is holding in place the drawer, screws the bolts connecting the Illumination Drawer to the Rack rails (M2,5 allen key)
- 5.3 Insert the Illumination Drawer inside the Rack enclosure.
- 5.4 Push the ILL / ILR drawer inside the Rack until the stop.
- 5.5 Connect the ILL-A/ILR-A cable on ILL/ILR frontal panel.

NOTE

ILL / ILR WATER COOLING LOOP DOESN'T NEED WATER REFILLING BECAUSE ALL EDEN ISS RACK IS DIRECTLY CONNECTED TO MTF COOLING LOOP. THIS MTF COOLING LOOP CONNECTS THE FEG AND THE ISPR WITH A RESERVOIR CONTAINING A SOLUTION OF WATER AND ETHYLENE GLYCOL. THE SOLUTION IS CONSTANTLY COOLED AND RECIRCULATED BY MEANS OF A PUMP (THE PUMP IS NOT PART OF EDEN ISS RACK)

- 5.6 Connect the COOL ILL/ILR IN and the COOL ILL/ILR OUT water hoses (Fig. 1) on ILL/ILR frontal panel. Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

6 STATIC IP ASSIGNMENT TO THE NEW LED LAMP UNIT

NOTE

1. THE NEW LED LAMP UNIT IS CONFIGURED WITH DEFAULT NETWORK PARAMETERS. AN ACTION IS REQUIRED TO CORRECTLY CONFIGURE THEM AND MAKE THE LED LAMP UNIT CONNECTED TO THE ISPR/EDEN ISS NETWORK.

4.540 ISPR Light Panel Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

2. THE LED LAMP UNIT NETWORK PARAMETERS ARE DEFINED IN THE DOCUMENT
"IP&Co_NEW_V2"

- 6.1 Reactivate the Rack. PERFORM 1.140 ISPR ACTIVATION AND CHECKOUT Step 1
- 6.2 Wait until the end of Windows initialization
- 6.3 Load the Heliospectra System Assistant
Path: Start/All Programs/Heliospectra System Assistant 1.3.0

Figure 12: Heliospectra SW Main Display

- 6.4 In the Heliospectra System Assistant Main Display
Press Scan Button(Fig. 12 – yellow box)

A list with all the LED Lamp Unit in the EDEN ISS network will appear as well as a list of Not Recognized LED Lamp Units.
- 6.5 In the Not Recognized Lamp Unit List
Select the new installed LED Lamp Unit
- 6.6 In the Heliospectra System Assistant Main Display
Press Blink Button(Fig. 12 – red box)
The new installed LED Lamp Unit will blink a couple of time

4.540 ISPR Light Panel Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 6.7 In the Heliospectra System Assistant Main Display
- Press** Launch Button (Fig. 12 – blue box)
The Settings Browser Interfaces pages appears.
- 6.8 In the Setting Browser Interface/Network Settings
- Disable** the DHCP
Input the static IP Address as per Document named “IP&Co_NEW_V2”
- 6.9 In the Setting Browser Interface/Main Settings
- Set** the lamp to be OFF at startup
- 6.10 **Cmd** Apply, then close the Setting Browser Interface
- 6.11 In the Heliospectra System Assistant Main Display
- Press** Scan Button(Fig. 12 – yellow box)
Verify the network parameters of the new lamp = have been changed as required
If not, stop the operations and inform MCC/TAS-I
- 6.12 **Close** the Heliospectra System Assistant SW
- 6.13 **Restart** Windows
- 7 CLOSEOUT**
- 7.1 Resume the operations.
PERFORM 1.140 ISPR ACTIVATION AND CHECKOUT Step 2 to the end
- Remark: after RUCOLA SW reactivation, all EDEN ISS Rack “software-managed” operations restarts from the point they were before operations stop*
- 7.2 Stow the damaged lamp
- 7.3 Stow the items and tools.

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Perform a periodic inspection of all EDEN ISS subsystems (drawers): ILL / ILR, GCS/ GCT, NDS and PCDH. It is aimed at the verification of the absence of water and/or nutrient solution leakage and to collect info for the definition of corrective actions in case of that occurrence.

DURATION

60 minutes (TBC)

TOOLS

2,5 Allen Key

ITEMS

Protective Nitrile Gloves

Protective Glasses

Dry wipes

Flashlight

Kapton Tape

HD Camera

NOTE

- A) THE FOLLOWING PROCEDURE APPLIES:
 - a. EVERY CROP CYCLE (3 MONTHS
 - b. WHENEVER A LEAK/FAILURE OCCURS

- B) PROCEDURE FORESEES THAT THE VISUAL INSPECTION / DRYING STARTS FROM UPPER DRAWERS TO LOWER ONES IN ORDER TO AVOID THAT, AFTER A FIRST DRYING, ANY GIVEN DRAWER COULD BE WETTED BY WATER FALLING DOWN FROM THE DROWERS ABOVE IT.

- C) EVERY DRAWER IS BUILT WITH A SLIGHTLY TILTED BOTTOM PANEL. HENCE ANY POSSIBLE WATER DROPS FALLING TO DRAWERS BOTTOM PANEL CAN SLIDE TOWARDS DRAWER INNER FRONT PANEL AND EASILY DETECTED AND REMOVED BY THE OPERATOR.

- D) PROCEDURE FORESEES BASICALLY FIVE MAIN STEPS:
 - a. ACTIVITY PREPARATION (SW SHUT DOWN)
 - b. SUBSYSTEM CONNECTION DETACHING
 - c. SUBSYSTEMS INSPECTION AND (IF NECESSARY) DRYING
 - d. SUBSYSTEMS CONNECTION RESTORE
 - e. CLOSEOUT (SW RESTART)

SS 1

ACTIVITY PREPARATION

NOTE

ALL THE REQUIRED ITEMS AND TOOLS, AND THE SPARE PARTS ARE AVAILABLE AT NMIII IN ANTARCTICA AND ARE CORRECTLY LABELLED AND STOWED

- 1.1 Retrieve the tools and the items from stowage

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 1 Rucola Sw Main Dialog Window

- 1.2 Click on the "STOP" button in RUCOLA SW main dialog window so that configuration parameters are saved and Rucola Software is switched off. (Fig. 1)

Figure 2 EDEN ISS Rack Power Switch

- 1.3 On the upper left panel of the ISPR Rack, switch Off the "Rack Power Switch" (Fig. 2)

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 3: Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel – ISPR Power Switch

1.4 On the EDEN ISS Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel, Switch OFF the ISPR Rack switches (Fig. 3)

2 FITTINGS DISCONNECTION

2.1 ILL / ILR connections detaching

Figure 4: Illuminations Drawers. Fluidic (red circled) and electrical (green circle) connections

2.1.1 Disconnect ILL and ILR fluidic and electrical connections (Figure 4)

2.1.2 Disconnect the “COOL ILL IN” water hoses (Fig. 4). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 2.1.3 Disconnect the “COOL ILR IN” water hoses (Fig. 4). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.
- 2.1.4 Disconnect the “COOL ILL OUT” water hoses (Fig. 4). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.
- 2.1.5 Disconnect the “COOL ILR OUT” water hoses (Fig. 4). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.
- 2.1.6 Disconnect the “ILL-A” and “ILR-A” cable (Fig. 4)
- 2.2 **GCS / GCT connections detaching**

Figure 5: Lines to be disconnected from the GCT and the GCS

- 2.2.1 Disconnect “GCS CO₂ inlet port” and “GCT CO₂ inlet port” (Fig. 5)
- 2.2.2 Disconnect “GCS Nutrient Solution Inlet Port” and “GCT Nutrient Solution Inlet Port” (Fig. 5). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops.
- 2.2.3 Disconnect “GCS moisture recovery lines (DX and SX)” and “GCT moisture recovery lines (DX and SX)” from THC (Fig. 5). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops.

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

2.2.4 Disconnect the electrical connections and Peltier cooling lines as follows (See Figure 5)

- 1) detach "GCS THC-SX Inlet Cooling Water" and "GCS THC-DX Inlet Cooling Water".
- 2) detach "GCT THC-SX Inlet Cooling Water" and "GCT THC-DX Inlet Cooling Water".
- 3) detach GCS THC SX and DX Outlet Cooling Water.

Remark: one of the THC of the GCT is missing in Figure 5

2.3 NDS connections detaching

Figure 6: NDS Fluidic Interfaces

2.3.1 Disconnect "GCS to NDS Condensate line" From NDS front panel (Fig 6). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

2.3.2 Disconnect "GCT to NDS Condensate line" From NDS front panel (Fig 6). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

2.3.3 Disconnect "NDS to GCS Nutrient Solution Line" From NDS front panel (Fig 6). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

2.3.4 Disconnect "NDS to GCT Nutrient Solution Line" From NDS front panel (Fig 6). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

2.3.5 Remove TCs From NDS front panel (Fig 6)

2.4 PCDH connections detaching

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 7: PCDH Drawer – Connectors to be disconnected

Figure 8: MUM SX Fluidic lines to be disconnected for PCDH opening

- 2.4.1 Disconnect all the electrical/data connectors (18) as identified in Fig. 7
- 2.4.2 Disconnect all MUM SX fluidic lines that could prevent PCDH openings as identified in Fig. 8
- 2.4.3 Once removed all the fluidic lines, pull out the drawer until the stop.

3 SUBSYSTEMS INSPECTION AND DRYING

WARNING

Cooling fluid is a solution of water and ethylene glycol that could be dangerous for skin and eyes. To minimize contact risk, protective equipment have to be weared before the operation starts

NOTE

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

WATER CAN BE PRESENT IN THE DRAWER AND/OR ON THE DRAWER COMPONENTS FOR TWO MAIN CAUSES:

- a) MOISTURE CONDENSATION
- b) LEAKAGE

IN THE FIRST CASE IT IS SUFFICIENT TO REMOVE THE DROPS USING DRY WIPES, IN THE SECOND FURTHER INVESTIGATION IS REQUIRED FOLLOWED BY A REPAIRING ACTIVITY

3.1 Wear the Protective Nitrile Gloves and Glasses

3.2 ILL / ILR Inspection

3.2.1 Pull Out ILL / ILR drawers from EDEN ISS Rack. Do not completely remove it.

Figure 9: ILL / ILR inner components

3.2.2 Perform a visual inspection on each component contained inside the ILL /ILR. In particular check whether any possible water droplets are detectable on the following components by means of flashlight (see Figure 9):

- 1) Water Cooling Outlet

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 2) LED Panel Unit (external case)
- 3) Water Cooling Inlet (also inlet brass fitting)
- 4) Power
- 5) LAN

Figure 10: ILL / ILR panel mount fittings

- 3.2.3 Perform a visual inspection also on both side of panel mount fittings (see Figure 10). In particular:
- 1) Outlet panel mount fluidic fitting
 - 2) Cool Degas panel mount fluidic fitting
 - 3) Inlet panel mount fluidic fitting
 - 4) ILL / ILR panel mount electric fitting

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 11: ILL / ILR rear side inner components

- 3.2.4 Perform a visual inspection of rear side of ILL / ILL drawers and, in particular, on the components listed below (see Figure 11):
- 1) Water Cooling Outlet
 - 2) Led Panel Unit (Rear Side)
 - 3) Outlet brass fitting
- 3.2.5 Perform a visual inspection of ILL / ILR drawer bottom.
- 3.2.6 If no water droplets are detected at all, move to step 3.1.10
- 3.2.7 If water is detected inside the drawer or on one or more of its components, remove it by means of the dry wipe. Wait for 5 minutes then repeat visual check.
- 3.2.8 If there is water again,
take one or more pictures of the affected components, call MCC/TAS-I
- 3.2.9 If no water droplets are detected,
S/S inspection is successful
- 3.2.10 Push the ILL / ILR Drawer into EDEN ISS Rack until the stop.
- 3.3 GCT/GCS Inspection**
- 3.3.1 Pull the GCT / GCS drawer out of EDEN ISS Rack until the stop.

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

NOTE

TO ACCESS THE INTERIOR OF THE GROWTH CHAMBERS (BOTH THE GCS AND THE GCT) A LATERAL PANEL HAS TO BE REMOVED. TO DO THAT:

- 1) 10 BOLTS HAVE TO BE UNSCREWED FOR THE GCS.
 - 2) 12 BOLTS HAVE TO BE UNSCREWED FOR THE GCT.
- SEE FIGURE 14 AND FIGURE 15.

Figure 12: GCS, later panel fixations bolts position

Figure 13: GCS, later panel fixations bolts position

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 3.3.2 Unscrew the bolts with 2,5 allen key that secure AI lateral panel to the drawer lateral structure of GCS/GCT.
- 3.3.3 Remove the AI lateral panel from GCS/GCT and temp stow them

Figure 14: GCS/GCT top view

- 3.3.4 Perform a visual inspection on each component contained inside GCS / GCT. In particular check whether any possible water droplets are detectable on the following components by means of flashlight (see Figure 14)
- 3.3.5 If no water droplets are detected at all, move to step 3.3.9
- 3.3.6 If water is detected inside the drawer or on one or more of its components, remove it by means of the dry wipe. Wait for 5 minutes then repeat visual check.
- 3.3.7 If there is water again,
take one or more pictures of the affected components, call MCC/TAS-I
- 3.3.8 If no water droplets are detected,
S/S inspection is successful
- 3.3.9 Install the AI lateral panel on GCS/GCT. Screw the M2,5 bolts using the Allen Key and tighten them

NOTE

- 1) THE POWER AND DATA ISPR/GROWTH CHAMBERS INTERFACES ARE LOCATED ON THE REAR PART OF THE GROWTH CHAMBERS AND ON THE REAR PANEL OF THE RACK ENCLOSURE.
- 2) TO ENSURE A PROPER CONNECTIONS THE DRAWER HAS TO BE FIRMLY GRABBED AND COMPLETELY INSERTED IN ITS ENCLOSURE

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 15: Power and Data Connectors on the Rear Panel of the Rack Enclosure

3.3.10 Push the GCT / GCS drawer in the EDEN ISS Rack until the stop.

3.4 NDS Inspection

3.4.1 Pull NDS Drawer outside EDEN ISS Rack.

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 16 NDS Drawer upper panel fixed by kapton tape

- 3.4.2 Remove kapton tape that holds NDS Drawer cover in position. See Figure 16.
- 3.4.3 Remove the NDS Drawer upper panel (no screws to be removed)

THE REMOVAL SEQUENCE IS THE FOLLOWING:

- 1) CONCENTRATED NUTRIENT TANK_C
- 2) SUPPORT PLATE_1
- 3) CONCENTRATED NUTRIENT TANK_B
- 4) SUPPORT PLATE_2
- 5) CONCENTRATED NUTRIENT TANK_A
- 6) SUPPORT PLATE_3

- 3.4.4 Disconnect QD on “Nutrient Tank_C”. Use dry wipes to remove any possible liquid drop
- 3.4.5 Remove the Nutrient Tank_C
- 3.4.6 Remove the “Support Plate_1”
- 3.4.7 Disconnect QD on “Nutrient Tank_B”. Use dry wipes to remove any possible liquid drop
- 3.4.8 Remove the Nutrient Tank_B
- 3.4.9 Remove the “Support Plate_2”

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(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 3.4.10 Disconnect QD on “Nutrient Tank_A”. Use dry wipes to remove any possible liquid drop
- 3.4.11 Remove the Nutrient Tank_A
- 3.4.12 Remove the “Support Plate_3”

Figure 18: NDS internal components:pumps, valves and gas traps

- 3.4.13 Perform a visual inspection on each component contained inside the NDS. In particular check whether any possible water droplets are detectable on the following components by means of flashlight (see Figure 18)
 - 1) Nutrient solution_A Pump
 - 2) Nutrient solution_B Pump
 - 3) Nutrient solution_C Pump
 - 4) Gas Traps
 - 5) TBD Pump
 - 6) Check valves
- 3.4.14 If no water droplets are detected at all, move to step 3.1.18
- 3.4.15 If water is detected inside the drawer or on one or more of its components, remove it by means of the dry wipe. Wait for 5 minutes then repeat visual check.
- 3.4.16 If there is water again,
 - take one or more pictures of the affected components, call MCC/TAS-I
- 3.4.17 If no water droplets are detected,
 - S/S inspection is successful
- 3.4.18 Remount “Support Plate_3”

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 3.4.19 Connect the removed "Nutrient Tank_A"
- 3.4.20 Remount "Support Plate_2"
- 3.4.21 Connect the removed "Nutrient Tank_B"
- 3.4.22 Remount "Support Plate_1"
- 3.4.23 Connect the removed "Nutrient Tank_C"
- 3.4.24 Remount "NDS Drawer Upper Panel"
- 3.4.25 Put Kapton tape to secure the NDS upper panel to the NDS drawer as per Figure 14
- 3.4.26 Push the NDS drawer inside the Rack until the stop

3.5 PCDH Inspection

- 3.5.1 Pull out the PCDH Drawer
- 3.5.2 Unscrew the 6 bolts that holds PCDH upper panel in position using the 2,5 mm allen key
- 3.5.3 Remove PCDH upper panel and temp stow it

Figure 19: PCDH Internal components

- 3.5.4 Perform a visual inspection on each component contained inside the NDS. In particular check whether any possible water droplets are detectable on the following components by means of flashlight (see Figure 19)
- 3.5.5 If no water droplets are detected at all, move to step 3.5.8

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

3.5.6 If water is detected inside the drawer or on one or more of its components, remove it by means of the dry wipe.

3.5.8 Push PCDH Drawers into EDEN ISS Rack until stop

4 SUBSYSTEMS CONNECTION RESTORE

4.1 GCS / GCT connection restore

4.1.1 Connect the electrical connections and Peltier cooling line as follows (See Figure 5):

- 1) Connect "GCS THC-SX Inlet Cooling Water" and "GCS THC-DX Inlet Cooling Water".
- 2) Connect "GCT THC-SX Inlet Cooling Water" and "GCT THC-DX Inlet Cooling Water".
- 3) Connect "GCS THC SX and DX Outlet Cooling Water".

remark: one of the THC of the GCT is missing in Figure 5.

4.1.2 Connect "GCS moisture recovery lines (DX and SX)" and "GCT moisture recovery lines (DX and SX)" to the THC (Fig. 5). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops.

4.1.3 Connect "GCS Nutrient Solution Inlet Port" and "GCT Nutrient Solution Inlet Port" (Fig. 5). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops

4.1.4 Connect "GCS CO₂ inlet port" and "GCT CO₂ inlet port" (Fig. 5)

4.2 NDS connections restore

4.2.1 Connect "GCS to NDS Condensate line" to NDS front panel (Fig 6). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

4.2.2 Connect "GCT to NDS Condensate line" to NDS front panel (Fig 6). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

4.2.3 Connect "NDS to GCS Nutrient Solution Line" to NDS front panel (Fig 6). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

4.2.4 Connect "NDS to GCT Nutrient Solution Line" to NDS front panel (Fig 6). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

4.2.5 Connect TC to NDS front panel (Fig 6)

4.3 PCDH connections restore

4.3.1 Connect all the electrical/data connectors (18) as identified in Fig. 7

4.3.2 Connect all MUM SX fluidic lines as identified in Fig. 8

4.550 ISPR Subsystems Inspection

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

4.4 ILL / ILR connections restore

4.4.1 Connect the ILL-A/ILR-A cable to ILL/ILR front panel.

4.4.2 Connect the COOL ILL/ILR IN and the COOL ILL/ILR OUT water hoses (Fig 4) to ILL/ILR frontal panel. Remove possible water drops with Drywipe

5 CLOSEOUT

5.1 Resume the operations.

PERFORM 1.140 ISPR ACTIVATION AND CHECKOUT, All Steps

Remark: after RUCOLA SW reactivation, all EDEN ISS Rack "software-managed" operations restarts from the point they were before operations stop

5.2 Stow the items and tools.

4.560 ISPR NDS concentrated nutrient tanks replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Replace the Concentrated Nutrient Tanks inside the NDS.

DURATION

60 minutes

TOOLS

N/A

ITEMS

New Concentrated Nutrient Tanks

Sticky Labels

Permanent Red Marker

Kapton Tape

Dry wipes

Nitrile Gloves

NOTE

1. THREE SOFT BAGS ARE CONTAINED IN THE NDS DRAWER ACTING AS CONCENTRATED NUTRIENT TANK_A, TANK_B AND TANK_C AS SHOWN IN THE BELOW FIGURE 1

Figure 1: Concentrated Nutrient Tanks A, B and C

2. TANK_A AND TANK_B ARE OPERATED IN PARALLEL AND THEY DELIVER THE SAME AMOUNT OF CONCENTRATED NUTRIENT SOLUTION WHENEVER REQUIRED. TANK_C IS OPERATED INDEPENDENTLY. AS RESULT OF THAT TANK_A AND TANK_B WILL BE EMPTY AT THE SAME TIME, WHILE THAT COULD NOT BE THE CASE FOR THE TANK_C
3. THEREFORE THREE REPLACEMENT CASES ARE ENVISAGED AS PER THE FOLLOWING TABLE

Case	Tanks to be replaced	
	A + B	C
1	no	yes
2	yes	yes

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3	yes	no
---	-----	----

4. TANKS REPLACEMENT FORESEES THE EXTRACTION OF THE NDS DRAWER AND THEREFORE THE DISCONNECTION OF ALL THE HOSES AND CABLES PREVENTING THAT

- SS 1 **ACTIVITY PREPARATION**
- 1.1 Retrieve the tools and the items from stowage

Figure 1 Rucola Sw Main Dialog Window

- 1.2 Click on the “STOP” button in RUCOLA SW main dialog window so that configuration parameters are saved and Rucola Software is switched off. (Fig. 1)

Figure 2 EDEN ISS Rack Power Switch

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- 1.3 On the upper left panel of the ISPR Rack, switch Off the “Rack Power Switch” (Fig. 2)

Figure 3: Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel – ISPR Power Switch

- 1.4 On the EDEN ISS Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel, Switch OFF the ISPR Rack switches (Fig. 3)

ISPR 2 NUTRIENT DELIVERY SYSTEM DRAWER EXTRACTION

Figure 4: Cables and hoses to be disconnected on the Illumination Drawer and on the GCS

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(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 2.1 Disconnect the COOL ILL OUT water hoses (Fig. 4). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.2 Disconnect the GCS CO2 Inlet Line (Fig. 4)
- 2.3 Disconnect the Electrical Lines (Fig. 4)

Figure 5: Cables and hoses to be disconnected on the NDS Drawer

- 2.4 Disconnect "GCS to NDS Condensate line" From NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.5 Disconnect "GCT to NDS Condensate line" From NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.6 Disconnect "NDS to GCS Nutrient Solution Line" From NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.7 Disconnect "NDS to GCT Nutrient Solution Line" From NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.8 Remove TCs From NDS front panel (Fig 5)
- 2.9 Pull NDS Drawer outside EDEN ISS Rack and put it on the floor

3 CONCENTRATED NUTRIENT TANKS REPLACEMENT

4.560 ISPR NDS concentrated nutrient tanks replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 6: NDS Drawer upper panel fixed by kapton tape

- 3.1 Remove kapton tape that holds NDS Drawer cover in position (Fig. 6)
- 3.2 Remove the NDS upper panel (lift it up – no bolts to be removed)

4.560 ISPR NDS concentrated nutrient tanks replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 7: NDS Drawer Internal - Tanks Position Layout

THE REMOVAL SEQUENCE IS THE FOLLOWING:

- 1) CONCENTRATED NUTRIENT TANK_C
- 2) SUPPORT PLATE_1
- 3) CONCENTRATED NUTRIENT TANK_B
- 4) SUPPORT PLATE_2
- 5) CONCENTRATED NUTRIENT TANK_A
- 6) SUPPORT PLATE_3

3.3 Wear Nitrile Gloves

3.4 Disconnect QD on "Nutrient Tank_C". Use dry wipes to remove any possible liquid drop

3.5 Remove the Nutrient Tank_C

3.6 CASE 1: Tank_C Replacement – No replacement of Tanks A & B

3.6.1 Label the removed Tank C: "**TANK_C EMPTY – DO NOT USE**". Temp stow it

3.6.2 Install the new "Nutrient Tank_C". Connect it to the QD

3.6.3 GOTO Step 3.9

3.7 CASE 2: Tanks A, B and C Replacement

3.7.1 Label the removed Tank C: "**TANK_C EMPTY – DO NOT USE**". Temp stow it

3.7.2 Remove the "Support Plate_1"

3.7.3 Disconnect QD on "Nutrient Tank_B". Use dry wipes to remove any possible liquid drop

3.7.4 Remove the Nutrient Tank_B and label it": "**TANK_B EMPTY – DO NOT USE**". Temp stow it

3.7.5 Remove the "Support Plate_2"

3.7.6 Disconnect QD on "Nutrient Tank_A". Use dry wipes to remove any possible liquid drop

3.7.7 Remove the Nutrient Tank_A and label it": "**TANK_A EMPTY – DO NOT USE**". Temp stow it

3.7.8 Install the new "Nutrient Tank_A". Connect it to the QD

3.7.9 Re-mount the "Support Plate_2"

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3.7.10 Install the new “Nutrient Tank_B” . Connect it to the QD

3.7.11 Re-Install “Support Plate_1”

3.7.12 Install the new “Nutrient Tank_C” . Connect it to the QD

3.7.13 GOTO Step 3.9

3.8 CASE 3: Tanks A & B Replacement – No replacement of Tank_C

3.8.1 Remove the “Support Plate_1”

3.8.2 Disconnect QD on “Nutrient Tank_B” . Use dry wipes to remove any possible liquid drop

3.8.3 Remove the Nutrient Tank_B and label it”: **”TANK_B EMPTY – DO NOT USE”**. Temp stow it

3.8.4 Remove the “Support Plate_2”

3.8.5 Disconnect QD on “Nutrient Tank_A” . Use dry wipes to remove any possible liquid drop

3.8.6 Remove the Nutrient Tank_A and label it”: **”TANK_A EMPTY – DO NOT USE”**. Temp stow it

3.8.7 Install the new “Nutrient Tank_A” . Connect it to the QD

3.8.8 Re-mount the “Support Plate_2”

3.8.9 Install the new “Nutrient Tank_B” . Connect it to the QD

3.8.10 Re-Install “Support Plate_1”

3.8.11 Re-Install the “Nutrient Tank_C” removed in step 4.5. Connect it to the QD
GOTO Step 3.12

3.9 Re-mount “NDS Drawer Upper Panel” . Fix it to the drawer structure with the kapton tape

4 CABLES AND HOSES RE-CONNECTION

4.1 Insert the NDS drawer in its rack enclosure. Push inside the Rack until stop

4.2 Re-connect the electrical lines (Figure 4)

4.3 Re-connect the COOL ILL OUT water hoses (Fig. 4). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops

4.560 ISPR NDS concentrated nutrient tanks replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 4.4 Re-connect the GCS CO2 Inlet Line (Fig. 4). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 4.5 Re-connect "GCS to NDS Condensate line" From NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 4.6 Re-connect "GCT to NDS Condensate line" From NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 4.7 Re-connect "NDS to GCS Nutrient Solution Line" From NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 4.8 Re-connect "NDS to GCT Nutrient Solution Line" From NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 4.9 Reinstall TCs From NDS front panel (Fig 5)

5 CLOSEOUT

- 5.1 Reactivate the Rack and resume the operations

PERFORM 1.140 ISPR ACTIVATION AND CHECKOUT, All Steps

Remark: after RUCOLA SW reactivation, all EDEN ISS Rack "software-managed" operations restarts from the point they were before operations stop

- 5.2 Stow the items and tools.

Procedure 4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Replace broken Fluidic Pumps located in the NDS and/or GCS and/or GCT

DURATION

60 minutes (TBC)

TOOLS

2,5 Allen Key

Screwdriver

Scissors

ITEMS (as required)

Pump - p/n 106921 (ESX04)

Pump - p/n 106103 (EMX08)

NOTE

- 1) TWO PUMPS SYSTEMS HAVE TO BE CONSIDERED FOR THIS MAINTENANCE PROCEDURES:

THE PUMPS LOCATED IN THE NDS DRAWER AS LISTED IN TABLE 1 BELOW

Table 1: NDS pumps

Pump ID.	Element/Component Name/Description	Qty	Part #
	Nutrient Storage Assy		
01	Conc. Nutrient solution piston pump	3	106921 (ESX04)
02	Nutrient solution delivery piston pump	1	106103(EMX08)
03	Water to nutrient piston pump	1	106103(EMX08)
04	Water delivery piston pump	1	106103(EMX08)
	Water Recovery Assy		
05	Condensate recovery piston pump	1	106103(EMX08)

THE PUMPS LOCATED IN THE GCT/GCS MODULE AS LISTED IN THE TABLE 2 BELOW

Table 2: GCT / GCS pumps

Pump ID.	Element/Component Name/Description	Qty	Part #
	Root Module - GCS		
06	Nutrient solution recirculation Piston Pump	1	106103(EMX08)
	Root Module - GCT		
07	Nutrient solution recirculation Piston Pump	1	106103(EMX08)

ALL OF THEM CAN BE REPLACED BY A NEW ONE IF NECESSARY

- 2) PUMPS REPLACEMENT FORESEES THE EXTRACTION OF THE NDS AND/OR THE GCT AND/OR THE GCS DRAWERS. THAT REQUIRES THE DISCONNECTION OF SEVERAL HOSES AND CABLES PREVENTING THIS OPERATION

Procedure 4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps replacement (ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

SS 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

NOTE

ALL THE REQUIRED ITEMS AND TOOLS, AND THE SPARE PARTS ARE AVAILABLE AT NMIII IN ANTARCTICA AND ARE CORRECTLY LABELLED AND STOWED

1.1 Retrieve the tools and the items from stowage

Figure 1 Rucola Sw Main Dialog Window

1.2 Click on the "STOP" button in RUCOLA SW main dialog window so that configuration parameters are saved and Rucola Software is switched off. (Fig. 1)

Figure 2 EDEN ISS Rack Power Switch

Procedure 4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 1.3 On the upper left panel of the ISPR Rack, switch Off the “Rack Power Switch” (Fig. 2)

Figure 3: Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel – ISPR Power Switch

- 1.4 On the EDEN ISS Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel, Switch OFF the ISPR Rack switches (Fig. 3)

2 PUMP REPLACEMENT IN THE NDS

2.1 NDS Drawer Extraction

Figure 4: Cables and hoses to be disconnected on the Illumination Drawer and on the GCS

Procedure 4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 2.1.1 Disconnect the COOL ILL OUT water hoses (Fig. 4). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.1.2 Disconnect the GCS CO2 Inlet Line (Fig. 4)
- 2.1.3 Disconnect the Electrical Lines (Fig. 4)

Figure 5: Cables and hoses to be disconnected on the NDS Drawer

- 2.1.4 Disconnect “GCS to NDS Condensate line” From NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.1.5 Disconnect “GCT to NDS Condensate line” From NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.1.6 Disconnect “NDS to GCS Nutrient Solution Line” From NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.1.7 Disconnect “NDS to GCT Nutrient Solution Line” From NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.1.8 Remove TCs From NDS front panel (Fig 5)
- 2.1.9 Pull NDS Drawer outside EDEN ISS Rack and put it on the floor
- 2.2 NDS PUMPS REPLACEMENT**
 - 2.2.1 Pull NDS Drawer outside EDEN ISS Rack and put it on the floor

Procedure 4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 6: NDS Drawer upper panel fixed by kapton tape

- 2.2.2 Remove kapton tape that holds NDS Drawer cover in position (Fig. 6)
- 2.2.3 Remove the NDS upper panel (lift it up – no bolts to be removed)

Procedure 4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 7: NDS Drawer Internal - Tanks Position Layout

THE REMOVAL SEQUENCE IS THE FOLLOWING:

- 1) CONCENTRATED NUTRIENT TANK_C
- 2) SUPPORT PLATE_1
- 3) CONCENTRATED NUTRIENT TANK_B
- 4) SUPPORT PLATE_2
- 5) CONCENTRATED NUTRIENT TANK_A
- 6) SUPPORT PLATE_3

- 2.2.4 Wear Nitrile Gloves
- 2.2.5 Disconnect QD on "Nutrient Tank_C". Use dry wipes to remove any possible liquid drop
- 2.2.6 Remove the Nutrient Tank_C
- 2.2.7 Remove the "Support Plate_1"
- 2.2.8 Disconnect QD on "Nutrient Tank_B". Use dry wipes to remove any possible liquid drop
- 2.2.9 Remove the Nutrient Tank_B
- 2.2.10 Remove the "Support Plate_2"
- 2.2.11 Disconnect QD on "Nutrient Tank_A". Use dry wipes to remove any possible liquid drop
- 2.2.12 Remove the Nutrient Tank_A
- 2.2.13 Remove the "Support Plate_3"

Fig. 8: NDS Drawer Internal – Pumps

Procedure 4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 9: Pumps tipology

2.2.14 Remove the broken pump

Detach inlet and outlet pipeline from the pump(s) to be replaced. Use dry wipes to remove any possible water drops

Unscrew the fixing screw on Pump Head and demount this last (Fig.9)

Remove the seal located between pump head and pump body. Don't waste it.

Remove pump body. Label it "PUMP OUT OF ORDER"

2.2.15 Install a new pump

Connect the pump to the pump head. Put the seal between them. Screw the fixing screw on the pump head.

Connect the inlet and outlet pipeline. Use a zip tie to secure the connection

Fix the pump to the drawer by means of a zip tie (come??)

Re-Install the "Support Plate_3".

Re-install the "Nutrient Tank_A". Connect it to the QD

Re-Install "Support Plate_2"

Re-Install the "Nutrient Tank_B". Connect it to the QD

Re-Install "Support Plate_1"

Re-install the "Nutrient Tank_C". Connect it to the QD

2.3 NDS Drawer reinstallation

Procedure 4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 2.3.1 Remount "NDS Drawer Upper Panel". Use Kapton Tape to fix it to the drawer structure (Fig. 6)
- 2.3.2 Insert the NDS drawer in the ISPR Rack enclosure. Push until the hard stop.
- 2.3.3 Re-connect "GCS to NDS Condensate line" to NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.3.4 Re-connect "GCT to NDS Condensate line" to the NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.3.5 Re-connect "NDS to GCS Nutrient Solution Line" To NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.3.6** RE-connect "NDS to GCT Nutrient Solution Line" to NDS front panel (Fig 5). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.3.7 Re-connect TCs to NDS front panel (Fig 5)
- 2.3.8 Re-connect the COOL ILL OUT water hoses (Fig. 4). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops
- 2.3.9 Re-connect the GCS CO2 Inlet Line (Fig. 4)
- 2.3.10 Re-connect the Electrical Lines (Fig. 4)
- 2.3.11 GOTO Step 4

3 PUMP REPLACEMENT IN GCT/GCS

3.1 GCS/GCT Extraction

NOTE

PUMP REPLACEMENT IN GCS AND GCT REQUIRES THE SAME OPERATIONS. THIS STEP DESCRIBED WHAT TO DO FOR BOTH OF THEM.

ILLUMINATION DRAWER LEFT/GCS

ILLUMINATION DRAWER RIGHT/GCT

Procedure 4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Fig.10: Illumination Drawers – Hoses to be disconnected

- 3.1.1 On the Illumination Drawer, disconnect the COOL ILL/ILR IN and the COOL ILL/ILR OUT hoses (Fig. 10). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops

Figure 11: Lines to be disconnected from the GCT and the GCS

- 3.1.2 Disconnect GCS/GCT CO₂ inlet port (Fig. 11)
- 3.1.3 Disconnect GCS/GCT Nutrient Solution Inlet Port (Fig. 11). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops.
- 3.1.4 Disconnect GCS/GCT moisture recovery lines (DX and SX) from THC (Fig. 11). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops.
- 3.1.5 Disconnect the electrical connections and Peltier cooling line from the THC of both GCT / GCS (Fig. 11) (remark: one of the THC of the GCT is missing in the picture)
- 3.1.6 Pull the GCT / GCS drawer out of EDEN ISS Rack until the stop.

NOTE

TO ACCESS THE INTERIOR OF THE GROWTH CHAMBERS (BOTH THE GCS AND THE GCT) A LATERAL PANEL HAS TO BE REMOVED. TO DO THAT 10 BOLTS HAVE TO BE UNSCREWED FOR THE GCS AND 12 BOLTS HAVE TO BE UNSCREWED FOR THE GCT AS PER FIGURE 12 AND FIGURE 13

Procedure 4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps replacement (ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 12: GCS, later panel fixations bolts position

Figure 13: GCS, later panel fixations bolts position

- 3.1.7 Unscrew the bolts with 2,5 allen key that secure Al lateral panel to the drawer lateral structure of GCS/GCT.

Procedure 4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

3.1.8 Remove the AI lateral panel from GCS/GCT.

3.2 GCS / GCT PUMPS REPLACEMENT

Figure 14 GCS / GCT inner panel configuration

Figure 15 : Nutrient Solution Recirculation Piston Pump (p/n 106103(EMX08)) demounting operations

3.2.1 Remove the broken pump

Detach inlet and outlet pipeline from the pump(s) to be replaced. Use dry wipes to remove any possible water drops

Procedure 4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Unscrew the fixing screw on Pump Head and demount this last (Fig.9)

Remove the seal located between pump head and pump body. Don't waste it.

Remove pump body. Label it "PUMP OUT OF ORDER"

3.2.2 Install a new pump

Connect the pump to the pump head. Put the seal between them. Screw the fixing screw on the pump head.

Connect the inlet and outlet pipeline. Use a zip tie to secure the connection

Fix the pump to the drawer by means of a zip tie (come??)

3.3 GCS / GCT CLOSURE

3.3.1 Install the AI lateral panel on GCS/GCT. Screw the M2,5 bolts using the Allen Key and tighten them.

NOTE

THE POWER AND DATA ISPR/GROWTH CHAMBERS INTERFACES ARE LOCATED ON THE REAR PART OF THE GROWTH CHAMBERS AND ON THE REAR PANEL OF THE RACK ENCLOSURE. TO ENSURE A PROPER CONNECTIONS THE DRAWER HAS TO BE COMPLETELY INSERTED IN ITS ENCLOSURE

Figure 16: Power and Data Connectors on the Rear Panel of the Rack Enclosure

3.3.2 Insert the GCT / GCS drawer in the EDEN ISS Rack. Push until the stop.

3.3.3 Connect the electrical connections and Peltier cooling line from the THC of both GCT / GCS (Fig. 11) (remark: one of the THC of the GCT is missing in the picture)

Procedure 4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 3.3.4 Connect "GCS/GCT moisture recovery lines (DX and SX)" to the THC (Fig. 11). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops
- 3.3.5 Connect GCS/GCT Nutrient Solution Inlet Port (Fig. 11). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops
- 3.3.8 Connect "GCS/GCT CO₂ inlet port" (Fig. 11)
- 3.3.9 Connect the COOL ILL/ILR IN and the COOL ILL/ILR OUT water hoses (Fig 10) on ILL/ILR frontal panel. Use the dry wipes to remove any possible water drops.

4 CLOSEOUT

- 4.1 Reactivate the Rack and resume the operations

PERFORM 1.140 ISPR ACTIVATION AND CHECKOUT, All Steps

Remark: after RUCOLA SW reactivation, all EDEN ISS Rack "software-managed" operations restarts from the point they were before operations stop

- 4.2 Stow the items and tools.

4.570 ISPR NDS D.I. Water Tank Refilling

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

To refill the NDS D.I. water tank when empty

DURATION

60 minutes

TOOLS

N/A

ITEMS (PROVIDED WITH THE RACK)

Filled Distilled Water Reservoir

Refilling Pipeline (length 60 cm)

Straight Fitting (p/n PI0408S)

1/4 Hose Barb Valved In-Line Coupling (p/n PMCD1304)

Dry Wipes

NOTE

- 1) THE NDS D.I. WATER TANK IS CONSIDERED:
 - a) EMPTY WHEN D.I.WATER LEVEL IS EQUAL OR LOWER THAN 350 ml
 - b) FULL WHEN D.I.WATER LEVEL IS EQUAL OR HIGHER THAN 7 liters.
- 2) "RUCOLA" SOFTWARE SHOWS A WARNING MESSAGE WHEN NDS D.I. WATER LEVEL FALLS BELOW 350 ML AS FOLLOW (FIG. 1):

Figure 1 : NDS D:I: Water Tank Warning Message

Remark: Figure 1 is only for reference. A similar window will be displayed on the Labview Display

SS 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

- 1.1 Collect the needed items and tools

4.570 ISPR NDS D.I. Water Tank Refilling (ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 2: Configuration Parameters

Figure 3: RuCola Main Window – Operations Stop

4.570 ISPR NDS D.I. Water Tank Refilling

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 4: Set Navigation Window

1.2 RUCOLA Main Page: Initial Configuration: Current Values

Record **Level Flex Bags** values
Record **Nut. Solution properties** values
Record **Flux Canalizer Status** values
Record **Parameters GCS Phase 1** values
Record **Parameters GCS Phase 2** values
Record **Parameters GCS Phase 3** values
Record **Parameters GCT Phase 1** values
Record **Parameters GCT Phase 2** values
Record **Parameters GCT Phase 3** values
Record **Day After Planting** values

See Fig. 2

1.3 Hold on the ISPR Rack Operations and save the configuration parameters

RUCOLA Main Page

Click on "SET" (fig. 3)

The ISPR operations will stop and the Set Navigation Window will open (Fig. 4)

2 RACK CONFIGURATION

4.570 ISPR NDS D.I. Water Tank Refilling (ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 5: Condensate Outlet Tee Fitting demounting schema

Figure 6: ISPR Water Tank to Water D.I. Reservoir Connection

4.570 ISPR NDS D.I. Water Tank Refilling

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

- 1.5 Disconnect the lower tube from the “Condensate Outlet Tee fitting” as per figure 4. Push the back collect while pulling the tube. Use dry wipe to remove any possible water drop

Figure 7: Straight Connector

- 1.6 Connect the tube to one end of the Straight Connector (Fig. 6 – A to A). Push the tube inside the straight connector until the pipe stop
- 1.7 Connect the Refilling Pipeline to the other end of the Straight Connector (Fig. 6 – B to B). Push the pipeline inside the straight connector until the hard stop.
- 1.8 Verify that the tube and the Refilling Pipeline are firmly connected to the Straight Connector. The tubes should remain connected when trying to pull them out (Fig. 6).

If one or the two tubes are pulled out, reconnect them again

- 1.9 Connect the 1/4 Hose Barb Valved In-Line Coupling Body (female) to the Refilling Pipeline (Fig. 6 – C to C)
- 1.10 Connect the 1/4 Hose Barb Valved In-Line Coupling Body to the 1/4 Hose Barb Valved In Line Coupling Body located on D.I. Reservoir Tank Top Side.

2 WATER REFILLING

NOTE

1. RUCOLA SOFTWARE IS PROGRAMMED TO DELIVER THE REQUIRED AMOUNT OF SOLUTION BY MEANS OF NDS INTERNAL PUMP AND TO STOP AFTER REFILLING COMPLETION. ONCE THE SOLUTION VOLUME IS DELIVERED, RUCOLA SOFTWARE SWITCHES OFF THE NDS PUMP AUTOMATICALLY.
2. IF RUCOLA SOFTWARE DOESN'T SWITCHES OFF THE NDS PUMP AUTOMATICALLY, OR FOR ANY OTHER ISSUES, THE EDEN ISS MAIN POWER SWITCH HAS TO BE SWITCHED OFF

4.570 ISPR NDS D.I. Water Tank Refilling

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 8: NDS D.I. Water Tank Status Window

- 2.1 In the "SET Navigation Window" click on the **D.I. Water Tank Refilling** button. The "NDS D.I. Water Tank Status Window" will open (Fig. 8)
- 2.2 **Cmd** "START Refilling"
- 2.3 Verify that NDS D.I. water tank levels grows up

Figure 9: Filling completion message window

Figure 10: Tank Level Final Status

4.570 ISPR NDS D.I. Water Tank Refilling

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

2.4 Wait until the a dialog windows (Fig. 7) appears with the following message: “NDS Water Tank Refilling Complete”..

2.5 Click on the **OK** button. A dialog windows appears with the updated N.I. Water Tank Level (Fig. 8)

3 CLOSEOUT

3.1 Disconnect the tube from the Straight Connector (Fig. 5, A from A)

3.2 Connect the tube to the “Condensate Outlet Tee fitting” (Fig. 4)

Figure 11: RuCola Main Window – Operations Restore

3.3 Restore the operations. In the RUCOLA Main Page
Click on **RUCOLA** button (Fig. 9)

3.4 RUCOLA MAIN PAGE:Initial Configuration: Current Values

Verify **Level Flex Bags** Parameters = as recorded in step 1.2

Verify **Nut. Solution properties** = as recorded in step 1.2

Verify **Flux Canalizer Status** = as recorded in step 1.2

Verify **Parameters GCS Phase 1** = as recorded in step 1.2

Verify **Parameters GCS Phase 2** = as recorded in step 1.2

Verify **Parameters GCS Phase 3** = as recorded in step 1.2

Verify **Parameters GCT Phase 1** = as recorded in step 1.2

Verify **Parameters GCT Phase 2** = as recorded in step 1.2

Verify **Parameters GCT Phase 3** = as recorded in step 1.2

Verify **Day After Planting** = as recorded in step 1.2

3.5 Disconnect the 1/4 Hose Barb Valved In-Line Coupling Body to the 1/4 Hose Barb Valved In

4.570 ISPR NDS D.I. Water Tank Refilling

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Line Coupling Body located on D.I. Reservoir Tank Top Side

- 3.6 Disconnect the 1/4 Hose Barb Valved In-Line Coupling Body (female) to the Refilling Pipeline (Fig. 6 – C from C)
- 3.7 Disconnect the Refilling Pipeline to the other end of the Straight Connector (Fig. 6 – B from B)
- 3.8 Clean and dry all the disassembled items. Store them

4590 ISPR Root Module Replacement in GCT

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

OBJECTIVE

Replace the Root Module in the Growth Chamber Tall (GCT) in order to overcome Root Module malfunctioning

DURATION

60 minutes

TOOLS

Screwdriver

L-Shaped Key

ITEMS

Spare Root Module

SS 1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

NOTE

ALL THE REQUIRED ITEMS AND TOOLS, AND THE SPARE PARTS ARE AVAILABLE AT NMIII IN ANTARCTICA AND ARE CORRECTLY LABELLED AND STOWED

1.1 Retrieve the tools and the items from stowage

Figure 1 Rucola Sw Main Dialog Window

1.2 Click on the "STOP" button in RUCOLA SW main dialog window so that configuration parameters are saved and Rucola Software is switched off. (Fig. 1)

4590 ISPR Root Module Replacement in GCT

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

Figure 2 EDEN ISS Rack Power Switch

- 1.3 On the upper left panel of the ISPR Rack, switch Off the “Rack Power Switch” (Fig. 2)

Figure 3: Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel – ISPR Power Switch

- 1.4 On the EDEN ISS Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel, Switch OFF the ISPR Rack switches (Fig. 3)

2 DRAWER EXTRACTION AND OPENING

NOTE

1. THE FOLLOWING STEPS APPLIES TO BOTH THE TALL GROWTH CHAMBERS (GCT) AND THE SHORT GROWTH CHAMBERS (GCS)
2. ALL THE FLUIDIC LINES ARE EQUIPPED WITH SELF LOCKING QUICK DISCONNECT COUPLING DEVICES, THEREFORE ONLY MANUAL ACTION IS REQUIRED FOR CONNECTION/DISCONNECTION

4590 ISPR Root Module Replacement in GCT

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

ILLUMINATION DRAWER LEFT/GCS

ILLUMINATION DRAWER RIGHT/GCT

Figure 4: Cooling lines to be disconnected from the illumination drawers

- 2.1 On the Illumination Drawer, disconnect the COOL ILL/ILR IN and the COOL ILL/ILR OUT hoses (Fig. 4). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

4590 ISPR Root Module Replacement in GCT

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

Figure 5: Lines to be disconnected from the GCT and the GCS

- 2.2 Disconnect CO₂ inlet line (Fig. 5)
- 2.3 Disconnect Nutrient solution inlet line (Fig. 5). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops
- 2.4 Disconnect moisture recovery lines from THC (Fig. 5). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops
- 2.5 Disconnect the electrical connections and Peltier cooling line from the THC of both GCT / GCS (Fig. 5) (remark: one of the THC of the GCT is missing in the picture)
- 2.6 Pull the GCT / GCS drawer out of EDEN ISS Rack until the stop

NOTE

TO ACCESS THE INTERIOR OF THE GROWTH CHAMBERS (BOTH THE GCS AND THE GCT) A LATERAL PANEL HAS TO BE REMOVED. TO DO THAT 10 BOLTS HAVE TO BE UNSCREWED FOR THE GCS AND 12 BOLTS HAVE TO BE UNSCREWED FOR THE GCT AS PER THE FOLLOWING FIGURES

4590 ISPR Root Module Replacement in GCT

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

Figure 6: GCS, later panel fixations bolts position

Figure 7: GCT, later panel fixations bolts position

4590 ISPR Root Module Replacement in GCT

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

2.8 Unscrew the bolts with 2,5 allen key that secure AI panel to the drawer lateral structure of GCS/GCT

2.9 Remove the lateral AI panel from GCS/GCT

3 ROOT MODULE REPLACEMENT

3.1 Root Module Pillow removal

Figure 8: Root Module

Figure 9: Root Module panels removal

4590 ISPR Root Module Replacement in GCT

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

Figure 10: Root Module Pillow

- 3.1.1 If a plant growth cycle experiment has already been completed, cut all the plants stems close to the Root module panels. Waste them.
- 3.1.2 Remove the Humidity Sensors (8) if installed
- 3.1.3 Disconnect the inlet water line QDs (Blue boxes in Figure 8)
- 3.1.4 Disconnect the outlet water line QDs (yellow box in Figure 8)
- 3.1.5 Remove the screw (16) by means of a Phillips-head screwdriver (Red Circles in Fig. 8)
- 3.1.6 Remove the panels (4) and temporary stow them
- 3.1.7 Remove and temporary stow the pillow (4)

3.2 Root Module Removal

NOTE

THE ROOT MODULE IS FIXED TO THE GROWTH CHAMBER BY MEANS OF VELCRO PLACED AT THE FOUR CORNERS. A SPECIAL TOOL (L-SHAPED KEY) IS PROVIDED TO DETACH THE ROOT MODULE FROM THE VELCRO STRIP ATTACHED ON THE GCT FLOOR

CAUTION

HARDWARE DAMAGE RISK: PAY ATTENTION DURING THE ROOT MODULE REMOVAL OPERATIONS

4590 ISPR Root Module Replacement in GCT (ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

Figure 11: Root Module Removal Steps Using L-Shaped Key –

- 3.2.1 Insert an L-shaped key between Root Module and GCT lateral side (Fig. 11). Pull down until it reached the GCT bottom (Fig. 11, Step 1)

4590 ISPR Root Module Replacement in GCT

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

- 3.2.2 Rotate the L-key with reference to the vertical axes and insert it between the Root Module lower panel and GCT bottom (Fig. 11, Step 2)
- 3.2.3 Shift the key as close as possible to the Velcro strips located at Root Module corners
- 3.2.4 Rotate the L-key with reference to the transversal axes so that it could be used as a lever to pull up the Root Module (Fig. 11, Step 3)
- 3.2.5 Repeat the steps 3.2.3 and 3.2.4 on the opposite corner
- 3.2.6 Remove the Root Module paying attention to not harm the other parts of the GCT
- 3.2.7 Remove the velcro strip from the Root Module
- 3.2.8 Remove the velcro strip from the GCT floor
- 3.2.9 Clean the Root Module
- 3.2.10 Install the root module panels (4). Screw the bolts (16) by means of a Phillips-head screwdriver
- 3.2.11 Label the Root Module "ROOT MODULE TO BE REPAIRED – DO NOT USE"

3.3 New Root Module Installation

NOTE

THE NEW ROOT MODULE SHALL BE CONFIGURED TO RESUME THE OPERATIONS. SHOULD BE THIS THE CASE NEW PILLOWS HAS TO BE PREPARED AND INSTALLED BEFORE THE INSTALLATION OF THE ROOT MODULE IN THE GCT

- 3.3.1 If a new Plant Growth Experiment has to be done, perform the following steps of the procedure 2.300 ISPR CONFIGURATION FOR PLANT GROWTH
 - Pillow preparation: Step 1
 - Pillow installation in the Root Module: From step 2.2.6 to step 2.2.9

CAUTION

HARDWARE DAMAGE RISK: PAY ATTENTION DURING THE ROOT MODULE INSTALLATION OPERATIONS

- 3.3.2 Prepare 8 velcro strips with the same size of the removed ones so that:
 - 4 strips are formed by the layer covered with tiny loops
 - 4 strips are formed by the layer with tiny flexible hooks.Don't remove the protective film
- 3.3.3 Assemble the tiny loop strips with the tiny hooks strips. Press the two layer very well.
- 3.3.4 Remove the protective film from one side of the Velcro Strips and attach them on the new Root Module

4590 ISPR Root Module Replacement in GCT

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

- 3.3.5 Remove the protective film from the other side of the Velcro Strips, and install the Root Module in the drawer, paying attention to not harm the other GCT items
- 3.3.6 Push strongly the Root Module to firmly attach it to the GCT bottom surface
- 3.3.7 Connect the inlet water lines (Fig.8 –blue boxes)
- 3.3.8 Connect the outlet water line (Fig. 8 – yellow boxes)
- 3.3.9 Insert the Humidity Sensors in their location

4 GROWTH CHAMBER CLOSURE

- 4.1 Install the lateral Al panel on GCS/GCT. Screw the M2,5 bolts using the Allen Key and tighten them.

NOTE

THE POWER AND DATA ISPR/GROWTH CHAMBERS INTERFACES ARE LOCATED ON THE REAR PART OF THE GROWTH CHAMBERS AND ON THE REAR PANEL OF THE RACK ENCLOSURE. TO ENSURE A PROPER CONNECTIONS THE DRAWER HAS TO BE COMPLETELY INSERTED IN ITS ENCLOSURE

Figure 12: Power and Data Connectors on the Rear Panel of the Rack Enclosure

- 4.2 Push the GCT / GCS drawer in the EDEN ISS Rack until the stop
- 4.3 Connect the electrical connections and Peltier cooling line from the THC of both GCT / GCS (Fig. 6) (remark: one of the THC of the GCT is missing in the picture)
- 4.4 Connect moisture recovery lines to the THC (Fig. 5). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops

4590 ISPR Root Module Replacement in GCT

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE/HC)

- 4.5 Connect Nutrient solution inlet line (Fig. 5). Use dry wipe to remove possible liquid drops (Fig. 6)
- 4.6 Connect CO₂ inlet line (Fig. 5)
- 4.7 On the Illumination Drawer, connect the COOL ILR IN and the COOL ILR OUT hoses (Fig. 4). Use the dry wipes to remove possible water drops.

5 CLOSEOUT

- 5.1 Reactivate the Rack and resume the operations

PERFORM 1.140 ISPR ACTIVATION AND CHECKOUT, All Steps

Remark: after RUCOLA SW reactivation, all EDEN ISS Rack "software-managed" operations restarts from the point they were before operations stop

- 5.2 Stow the removed Root Module waiting for repairing activities
- 5.3 Stow the tools and items
- 5.4 Waste the removed pillow (if any)

4600 ISPR PCDH Relays Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

Replace one or more relays inside the Power Command & Data Handling Drawer (PCDH)

DURATION

60 minutes

TOOLS

Phillips-head screwdriver
2.5 mm Allen Key

ITEMS

Spare Relays (the number is event dependent)
Labels
Permanent Red Marker

NOTE

1. THIS PROCEDURE HAS TO BE USED WHENEVER THE RELAY REPLACEMENT IS IDENTIFIED AS RECOVERY ACTION FROM A S/S FAILURE. AN OFFLINE TROUBLESHOOTING ACTIVITIES, CONDUCTED BY THE EXPERTS PANEL, WILL DEFINE THE RELAY(S) TO BE REPLACED
2. ALL THE RELAYS ARE UNAMBIGUOUSLY IDENTIFIED BY LABELS. EACH RELAYS HAS A NUMBER WRITTEN ON ITS LABEL AND OPERATES A SINGLE SPECIFIC COMPONENT (SEE SCHEMATIC)

1 ACTIVITY PREPARATION

- 1.1 Retrieve the tools and the items from stowage

Figure 1: RUCOLA SW Main Page – Stop the operations

- 1.2 Click on the “STOP” button in RUCOLA SW main dialog window so that configuration parameters are saved and Rucola Software is switched off (Fig. 1)

4600 ISPR PCDH Relays Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 2: ISPR Rack Main Switch

- 1.3 On the upper left panel of the ISPR Rack, switch Off the “Rack Power Switch” (Fig. 2)

Figure 3: Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel – ISPR Power Switch

- 1.4 On the EDEN ISS Power Control and Distribution Unit Front Panel, Switch OFF the ISPR Rack switches (Fig. 3)

2 PCDH DRAWER OPENING

4600 ISPR PCDH Relays Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

NOTE

A PREREQUISITE FOR THE PCDH DRAWER OPENING IS THE DISCONNECTION OF THE FOLLOWING CABLES AND HOSES:

1. THE POWER AND DATA CABLES ON THE PCDH DRAWER
2. THE FLUIDIC HOSES ON THE GCT AND GCS AND ON THE ILL

Figure 4: PCDH Drawer – Connectors to be disconnected

4600 ISPR PCDH Relays Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 5: MUM SX Fluidic lines to be disconnected for PCDH opening

- 2.1 Disconnect all the electrical/data connectors (18) as identified in Fig. 4
- 2.2 Disconnect "CO2 INLET TO GCT" line from GCT (Fig. 5 – Right)
- 2.3 Disconnect "CO2 INLET TO GCS" line from GCS. (Fig. 5 – Left)
- 2.4 Disconnect "COOL ILL OUT" from Left Illumination Drawer (Fig. 5 – Left)
- 2.5 Disconnect "Cooling Water to GCS THC-SX" from GCS. (Fig. 5 – Left)
- 2.6 Disconnect "Cooling Water to GCS THC-DX" from GCS. (Fig. 5 – Left)
- 2.7 Once removed all the fluidic lines, pull out the drawer until the stop.
- 2.8 Remove the upper panel. Unscrew the 6 bolts (2,5mm Allen Key)

3 RELAY REPLACEMENT

NOTE

THE RELAYS ARE LABELLED AS FOLLOWS:

4600 ISPR PCDH Relays Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Table 1: Relays List

Relay	Component	No
1	CO2_EV_GCT (+)	MUM B 12
2	CO2_EV_GCS (+)	MUM B 01
3	PA-NUT (+)	NDS 25
4	PB-NUT (+)	NDS 21
5	PNUT-RM (+)	NDS 27
6	PH20-NUT (+)	NDS 26
7	PH20-RM (+)	NDS 23
1D - 1	PCON (+)	NDS 17
1D - 2	PVAC (+)	NDS 29
8	STIR (+)	NDS 9
9	UVC (+)	NDS 42
10	EVIN (CH 1 to 4) (1+)	GCT A 02
11	EVIN (CH 1 to 4) (2+)	GCT A 03
12	EVIN (CH 1 to 4) (3+)	GCT A 04
13	EVIN (CH 1 to 4) (4+)	GCT A 05
2D - 1	PREC (+)	GCT A 06
2D - 2	PCTS (+)	GCT A 07
8D - 1	quadstepper_1	QUAD_GCS +
8D - 2	quadstepper_2	QUAD_GCT +
14	EVOUT (CH 1 to 4) (1+)	GCT A 21
15	EVOUT (CH 1 to 4) (2+)	GCT A 22
16	EVOUT (CH 1 to 4) (3+)	GCT A 23
17	EVOUT (CH 1 to 4) (4+)	GCT A 24
18	M1A (+) M1C (+) M2A (+) M2C (+) M3A (+) M3C (+) M4A (+) M4C (+)	GCT A 16
19	EV IN (CH 1 to 4) (1-) EV IN (CH 1 to 4) (2-) EV IN (CH 1 to 4) (3-) EV IN (CH 1 to 4) (4-)	GCT D 01
20	TCC 01O	TCC1 SV 31
21	HEATER (+) TCTEC (+)	GCT CA 4
22	FAN (+)	GCT F 01
23	TCC 01O	TCC_1 SV 31
24	HEATER (+)	GCT E A4
25	EV IN (CH 1 to 4) (1+)	GCS A02
26	EV IN (CH 1 to 4) (3+)	GCS A04
27	EV IN (CH 1 to 4) (2+)	GCS A03
28	EV IN (CH 1 to 4) (4+)	GCS A05

4600 ISPR PCDH Relays Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

3D - 1	P REC (+)	GCS A06
3D - 2	P CTS (+)	GCS A07
29	EV OUT (CH 1 to 4) (1+)	GCS A21
30	EV OUT (CH 1 to 4) (2+)	GCS A22
31	EV OUT (CH 1 to 4) (3+)	GCS A23
32	EV OUT (CH 1 to 4) (4+)	GCS A24
33	M1A (+) M1C (+) M2A (+) M2C (+) M3A (+) M3C (+) M4A (+) M4C (+)	GCS A16
34	FAN (+)	GCS D01
35	TCC.01O	TCC_2 SV 31
36	HEATER (+)	GCS CA4
37	FAN (+)	GCS F 01
38	TCC.01O	TCC_2 SV 31
39	HEATER (+)	GCS EA 4
40	Pc NUT (+)	NDS 15
41	CO2_EV_GCT (-)	MUM C2
42	CO2_EV_GCS (+)	MUM C1
43	DP 2 s+ GIALLO	MUM C7

Figure 7 PCDH Drawer electrical components and Relays Array

4600 ISPR PCDH Relays Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

Figure 8: Relay Finder 38.51.7.024.0050

- 3.1 Identify the Relay(s) as per MCC instructions and table 1
- 3.2 Once localized the Relay to be replaced, remove the electrical wires (use the Philip head screwdriver)
- 3.3 Remove the relay(s)
- 3.4 Label the removed relay(s) "DAMAGED – DO NOT USE"
- 3.5 Install the new relay(s)
- 3.6 Install the electrical wires (use the Philip head screwdriver)
- 3.7 Repeat step 3.4 to 3.8 as necessary until all the indicated relays have been replaced

4 CLOSEOUT

- 4.1 Reinstall the upper panel. Screw the 6 bolts (2,5mm Allen Key)
- 4.2 Close the drawer. Push until stop
- 4.3 Re-connect "CO2 INLET TO GCT" line from GCT (Fig. 5 – Right)
- 4.4 Re-connect "CO2 INLET TO GCS" line from GCS. (Fig. 5 – Left)
- 4.5 Re-connect "COOL ILL OUT" from Left Illumination Drawer (Fig. 5 – Left)
- 4.6 Re-connect "Cooling Water to GCS THC-SX" from GCS. (Fig. 5 – Left)
- 4.7 Re-connect "Cooling Water to GCS THC-DX" from GCS. (Fig. 5 – Left)
- 4.8 Re-connect all the power/data connectors (18) as indicated in fig.4
- 4.9 Resume the operations.
PERFORM 1.140 ISPR ACTIVATION AND CHECKOUT, All Steps

Remark: after RUCOLA SW reactivation, all EDEN ISS Rack "software-managed" operations restarts from the point they were before operations stop

- 4.10 Stow the items and tools

4600 ISPR PCDH Relays Replacement

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MAINTENANCE/PRE)

5.630 ISPR NDS Pumps Failure Management

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MALFUNCTION/PRE)

OBJECTIVE

NDS Pumps failure analysis and recovery

DURATION

Failure Dependent

TOOLS

N/A

ITEMS

N/A

REFERENCED PROCEDURES

4.550 ISPR S/S Inspection

4.560 ISPR NDS Concentrated Nutrient Tanks Replacement

4.561 ISPR NDS Pumps Replacement

4.600 ISPR PCDH Relays Replacement

5.630 ISPR NDS Pumps Failure Management

(ISPR RACK/CREW/MALFUNCTION/PRE)

